

WP3 - Synthesis Report

Return Migration Infrastructures

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List of abbreviations

ABH	Foreigners Authority (Germany)
AIDA	Asylum Information Database
AMIF	The Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund
AnkER	Arrival, decision and return facilities (Germany)
AVRR	Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration
AZC	Asylum Location (the Netherlands)
BAMF	German Federal Office for Migration and Refugees
CIB	Caritas International Belgium (Morocco)
CCAC	Closed Controlled Access Centre (Greece)
COA	Central Agency for the Reception of Asylum Seekers (the Netherlands)
DTenV	Dutch governmental agency de Dienst Terugkeer en Vertrek
DV&O	Transport and Support Service (the Netherlands)
ECCHR	The European Centre for Constitutional and Human Rights
ECRE	The European Council on Refugees and Exile
ERSO	European Reintegration Support Organisations
ETTC	European Technology and Training Centre (Iraq)
EU	European Union
EURP	European Reintegration Programme Frontex
GAS	Greek Asylum Service
GIZ	German International Cooperation Society
GOKSEM	Irregular Migrant Reception and Referral Centres (Turkey)
HHRO	Hammurabi Human Rights Organization (Iraq)
HRW	Human Rights Watch
ICMPD	International Centre for Migration Policy Development
ICTs	Information and Communication Technologies
IM	InfoMigrants
IOM	International Organization for Migration
IRMA	Integrated Return Management Application (Germany)
JRS	Joint Reintegration Services
KMar	Royal Police (the Netherlands)
LVV	National Alien Service / A shelter and return programme, hosted in five cities in the Netherlands
MDAs	Ministries, Departments and Agencies (Nigeria)
MMA	Ministry of Migration and Asylum (Greece)
MMP	Mobile Migration Points (Turkey)
MOH	Ministry of Health (Iraq)
MOI	Ministry of Interior (Iraq)
MOLSA	Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs (Iraq)
MTC	Migrant Transit Centre
N-AVRR	National Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration System (Turkey)
NCFRMI	National Commission for Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced persons (Nigeria)
NEMA	National Emergency Management Agency (Nigeria)
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NRM	National Referral Mechanism (Iraq)
OCAVRR	Open Centre for migrants registered for Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (Greece)
OFFI	The French Office for Immigration and Integration
PDMM	The Provincial Directorate of Migration Management (Turkey)
PMM	Presidency of Migration Management (Turkey)

PRDC	Pre-Removal Detention Centre (Greece)
RCMS	Readmission Case Management Electronic System (Georgia)
REAG/GARP	Reintegration and Emigration Programme for Asylum-Seekers in Germany/Government Assisted Repatriation Programme
RIAT	European Commission's Reintegration Assistance Tool
RIC	Reception and Identification Centre (Greece)
RMI	Return Migration Infrastructure
SEK	Police Special Unit (Germany)
SMA	Sweden Migration Authority
TCN	Third-Country National
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
WP	Working Paper

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Summary

This synthesis report is part of Work Package 3 of the GAPs ‘De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond’ project. The report focuses on the concept of ‘Return Migration Infrastructures (RMIs)’, aiming to thoroughly study how return migration governance is put into practice at the everyday implementation level. Following the infrastructural turn in migration studies, RMIs are understood to be constituted by a web of actors, their ‘doings’, as well as the places, materialities, and technologies that together shape returns. This perspective challenges the idea that return migration governance follows a linear procedure by insisting that RMIs are characterised by messy realities on the ground.

Instead of reproducing a simplistic binary of voluntary versus forced returns, this synthesis report investigates an axis of coercion that includes three types of RMIs; the assisted returns, forced removals, and pushbacks/pushforwards. The analysis is based on the research findings of 10 country dossiers referring to 11 GAPs country cases, including European Union (EU) countries (Germany, Greece, the Netherlands, Poland, and Sweden), and non-EU countries (Georgia, Iraq, Morocco, Nigeria, Tunisia, and Turkey); the former focus on RMIs returning people from the EU, the latter on RMIs receiving returnees from the EU.

Within the emerging continuum of coercion, three infrastructural dimensions are examined: First, we trace the wide variety of actors, their diverse roles, and their relations. The web of actors involved is discussed based on the political and geographical scales at which they operate, namely the international, the supranational, the national/federal, the sub-national, and the community/local level. The research on their complex web of relationships and interactions unfolds, among others, the emergence of asymmetric power relations, relations of competition, and informality.

Second, the report analyses the practices of these actors (their ‘doings’), and the ways these facilitate or contest the implementation of returns. Here, the doings are analysed around four axes: i) the detection and differentiation of return cases; ii) the preparation of returns during the pre-departure stage; iii) the carrying out of the actual return work; and iv) the post-return activities. Concerning these practices, our findings include the existence of approaches ranging between ‘one-size-fits-all’ and ‘case-by-case’ that often create unequal positions for those returned; the importance and constitutive character of informalities for the operation of RMIs; the importance of ‘non-doings’ as a form of governance or a policy of non-policy, with the issue of detention as of crucial importance; aspects of irregularisation as inherent part of the RMIs; and crucially, the emergence of soft power techniques and communicative practices of power in returns’ implementation, efforts of building trust at the same time that enforcing particular return options, the importance of the migrants’ ‘collaborative’ behaviour in determining the type of return, and the efforts of enforcing voluntariness through enforced collaboration.

Third, the report discusses the places, materialities, and technologies constituting the RMIs. Among other emerging issues, it unfolds the diversity and shifting character of RMIs’ geographies, the overlap observed between return (exit) and reception (entry) spaces and infrastructures, and the importance of funding.

Based on the synthesis of the findings, the report also provides a fresh conceptualisation of RMIs by highlighting three pivotal dimensions: the crucial role of mediation, the social-material dimension of migration, and the political dimension of infrastructures, thus framing them as a question of power. Last but not least, three main, cross-cutting conclusions are discussed, along with a number of policy insights and recommendations relating to each one:

the unbound character of RMIs which relates to the fact that RMIs are characterized by transnational and relational continuities and develop as crucial of a wider border control regime that seeks to 'purify' European societies from its unwelcome Others; RMIs as generators of informalities and the instrumentalisation of such informalities that emerge as constitutive characteristics of the ways RMIs are put into practice; and the force and power imbalances and dynamics that emerge.

The GAPs Project

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study on the drivers of return policies and the barriers and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by de-centring the dominant, one-sided understanding of 'return policymaking'. To this end, GAPs:

- examine the shortcomings of EU's return governance,
- analyse enablers and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explore the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its decentring approach with three innovative concepts:

- a focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance fissures,
- an analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU Member States and with third countries hinder cooperation on return, and
- a trajectory approach that uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is an interdisciplinary 3-year project (2023-2026), co-coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies with 17 partners in 12 countries on 4 continents. GAPs' fieldwork has been conducted in 12 countries: Afghanistan, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Iraq, Morocco, the Netherlands, Nigeria, Poland, Sweden, Tunisia, and Turkey.

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1. Introduction

This synthesis report is part of Work Package (WP) 3 of the GAPs ‘De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond’¹ project. WP 3 focuses on the concept of ‘Return Migration Infrastructures (RMIs)’, aiming to thoroughly study how return migration governance is put into practice at the everyday implementation level.

In terms of the type of returns we are focusing on, it is crucial to mention that WP3 does not reproduce a simplistic binary of voluntary versus forced returns (Şahin-Mencütek and Triandafyllidou 2025). Instead, it investigates an axis of coercion that includes three types of RMIs; the assisted returns, forced removals, and pushbacks. This threefold distinction is rather a prototypical divide, as reality may involve many grey zones and overlaps in return practices (Şahin-Mencütek and Triandafyllidou 2025).

- i. *Assisted returns*: Assisted returns are defined as (1) departures of migrants from the host country, (2) who formally comply/consent with their departure (even though there is often pressure to do so), and (3) receive a level of logistical, financial, administrative and/or interpersonal support in the process.
- ii. *Forced removal*: Forced removals are defined as (1) the removal of migrants from a particular state after the arrival of the migrant in that state, (2) without the migrant’s consent, but (3) within the legal framework and procedures of the state. Except for the actual transporting outside the territory of a particular state, infrastructures of forced removal, may include, pre-removal detention, arrests, and escorting.
- iii. *Pushbacks*: Pushbacks are defined as states and supra-states practices of (1) moving migrants, who are -usually- at or near the border², away from their territories (2) by force and (3) before they officially enter that territory, which implies that they are obstructing access to the applicable legal and procedural frameworks of that territory.

Following the infrastructural turn in migration studies (e.g. Xiang and Lindquist 2014), Return Migration Infrastructures are understood to be constituted by a web of relations and interactions between a wide variety of actors and their diverse roles, their implementation practices (‘doings’), as well as the places, materialities and technologies that together shape the daily operation of returns. These relations and interactions may create synergies, shared interests, and coherence, but also frictions, inconsistencies, and conflicts; thus, we also take into account how the above may both facilitate or undermine and contest returns on the ground. In doing so, the aforementioned perspective challenges the idea that return migration governance follows a linear procedure that is parallel to straightforward policy formations on paper. Instead, it recognises that RMIs are characterised by messy realities on the ground, which are created through complex practices (Koinova 2024). The main research questions on each infrastructural dimension examined are the following:

- i. *Actors, roles and relations*: What actors are involved in return migration governance, what are their prescribed roles and responsibilities, and how do different actors relate to each other?
While in most countries the issue of relations was treated as a separate dimension, we start in this synergy report by highlighting the multiple relations that exist.
- ii. *Doings*: What do these actors do in the everyday practice and how do they facilitate or contest the implementation of return migration governance through their daily practices?

¹For more information, see: <https://www.returnmigration.eu/about>

² Reported abductions from inland Greece may blur this definition, see Papatzani et al. 2025.

This dimension unpacks the daily reality of those actors working in the return migration infrastructure as a web of relations.

While this chapter is in terms of length the body of this report, it is still impossible to do justice to all the practices we encountered in each country. Hence, we sought to focus on three categories of doings: preparation and detection; the practice of actually returning somebody; and the post-return doings and looked for (dis)continuities and overlaps across countries.

- iii. *Materials and technologies*: What places/geographies, materialities, and technologies mediate return migration through the everyday doings of return migration governance?

The mediation of migration is certainly not only a human reality, but equally so a non-human reality of material objects such as pre-removal detention centres, airplanes, specialised vans, identity papers, etc. (e.g. Walters 2024). Additionally, surveillance techniques, software development, and datafication are inherent components of return migration governance (e.g., Leurs 2023). This dimension pays explicit attention to these non-human elements in the RMI.

The WP approached the RMIs by focusing on the so-called ‘crucial meso-level’ (Faist 2010), that is, the level of actors responsible for the everyday implementation of returns; those who literally put returns into practice. This implies that all that has to do with the macro-level of policy formation, law, international agreements, state agendas, and diplomacy is outside our scope (this is covered by WP2, WP4, and WP5). Equally so, all micro-level analysis on migrant agency, their aspirations, and experiences is out of our scope, even if we consider migrants as active agents whose practices may shape the implementation of returns (this aspect is mainly covered by WP7 and WP8).

The present synthesis report is based on the research conducted by the partner countries of the GAPs project within WP3. Our analysis was based on the ten country dossiers produced by partner countries referring to 11 country cases, which analysed research findings in different contexts. Specifically, research was conducted in European Union (EU) countries, such as Germany, Greece, the Netherlands, Poland, and Sweden, as well as in non-EU countries, including Georgia, Iraq, Morocco, Nigeria, Tunisia, and Turkey. EU partner countries focus on RMIs returning people from the EU to either the EU, in the case of Dublin, or non-EU, and non-EU partner countries focus on RMIs receiving returnees from the EU. This report’s analysis primarily aims to discuss how RMIs are constituted in different contexts. This is achieved by identifying commonalities between partner countries, as well as highlighting emerging differences and complexities.

The report is structured around four sub-sections, apart from the Methodology and the Conclusions. It begins by providing a conceptualisation of RMIs based on the research conducted in all partner countries. It discusses three pivotal dimensions of a RMIs’ approach: the crucial role of mediation, the social-material dimension of migration, and the political dimension of infrastructures, thus framing it as a question of power. The analysis that follows is structured based on our operational understanding of RMIs: First, section 4 discusses the state and non-state actors involved, the multiplicity of political and geographical scales at which they operate, and their relations. Section 5 analyses the implementation practices of the actors involved in returns, what we have called ‘doings’. It includes an analysis around four axes of doings: i) the detection and differentiation of return cases; ii) the preparation of returns during the pre-departure stage; iii) the carrying out of the actual return work; and iv) the post-return activities. In this regard, the section sheds light on cross-cutting issues emerging, including approaches between ‘one-size-fits-all’ and ‘case-by-case’, issues of informalities in RMIs, the importance of ‘non-doings’, aspects of irregularisation, and crucially, soft power

techniques on enforcing collaboration. Section 6 discusses the emerging materialities, places, geographies, and technologies that are constitutive of RMIs. Among other emerging issues, it unfolds the diversity and shifting character of RMIs' geographies, the overlap observed between return (exit) and reception (entry) spaces and infrastructures, and the importance of funding. The report concludes by providing some reflections on three main cross-cutting findings, namely the unbound character of RMIs versus the fragmented analysis, the instrumentalization of informalities, and the force and power imbalances and dynamics that emerge.

2. Methods

This synthesis report is based on the research conducted by the partner countries of the GAPs project within WP3 and aims to identify commonalities and emerging differences between the RMIs in the different contexts of the partner countries. Our analysis was based on the ten country dossiers produced by partner countries referring to 11 country cases. The empirical part of this report draws directly from these country dossiers of the partner countries³.

The WP3 research in each GAPs partner country was conducted between June 2023 and June 2024 and included two main tasks. The first was to provide an overview of existing RMIs, namely the infrastructures of assisted return, forced removals, and push-backs (if applicable), in each partner country. This overview was based on desk research and produced flow maps representing i) the actors involved, ii) their doings, and iii) the materials and technologies used in each RMI.

Second, the WP3 research focused on the selection of a particular RMI type (again among assisted returns, forced removals, or pushbacks) as a case study in each country. The research started from a specific 'entry point' on the ground related to the everyday workings of the RMI selected. It included the implementation of semi-structured interviews in each country with actors involved at the meso-level of the everyday operation of the return procedure that might either facilitate or contest return operations. All interviewees received an Information Letter and provided either written or oral consent for participating in the research. The WP3 partners were also encouraged to conduct ethnographic observations during the interviews or on other suitable occasions, on a voluntary basis.

In **Greece**, the Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) organized by International Organization for Migration (IOM) and state authorities was selected as a case study. The research's 'entry points' were the Open Centre for the accommodation of migrants registered in the programme (OCAVRR) located in Athens, and the IOM headquarters in Athens. The research included one preliminary discussion and sixteen semi-structured interviews with actors and stakeholders, including eleven IOM representatives, one with a representative of a devoted Directorate of the Ministry of Migration and Asylum (MMA), two with independent authorities, two with representatives of NGOs working on legal advocacy and human rights and three with immigrant organisations. Ethnographic material was collected through i) field visits and a guided tour by IOM representatives at the IOM headquarters in Athens, ii) a guided tour at OCAVRR where interviews with AVRR & OCAVRR participants⁴ took place; and iii) observation of a departure of Georgian AVRR returnees at the El. Venizelos Athens International Airport. IOM's willingness was crucial for implementing this part of the research (for more, see Papatzani et al. 2025).

In the **Netherlands**, a strong division between the assisted/voluntary returns on the one hand, and coerced returns/forced removals on the other was *not* made, as the actors, doings and materials that are involved strongly overlap. Twenty-two interviews were conducted that involved twenty-six people, eleven of which with representatives of state authorities, four from IOM, ten from NGOs and one from a local authority. Special attention was given to the role of

³ The country dossiers that formed the basis of this synthesis report can be found in the References section. As Sections 4, 5 and 6 draw directly from these dossiers, they are not cited continuously in order to not disrupt the flow of the text.

⁴ Interviews with immigrants, including AVRR and OCAVRR participants, were implemented in the context of the Work Package 7 of GAPs 'Return Aspirations and Trajectories of Migrants'. Their experiences, practices and perceptions are discussed and analysed in the WP7 country dossier of Greece.

the ‘regievoorders’, i.e. the case workers who are personally responsible for the ‘coordination and direction’ of every return operation, i.e. for each returnee. An information desk of the LLV programme, a pilot shelter-and-return programme operated by five local authorities in collaboration with civil society organisations and the central state administration, was used as the first entry point to the country’s research on RMIs (for more, see Schapendonk et al. 2025).

In order to reduce complexity, in **Germany**, the focus was on North Rhine-Westphalia, one of the country’s 15 federal states. As in the Netherlands, it was soon evident that potential returnees are exposed to an ‘axis of coercion’ that includes both assisted returns and forced removals. Twenty-two interviews were conducted, including with state authorities’ representatives, counsellors, the church, civil society organisations, and one written communication with Frontex. The research team also took part in several specialized training sessions, workshops, and conferences dealing with or closely related to the issue of return migration infrastructure (for more, see Mielke et al. 2025).

Both assisted returns and forced removals are also examined in the case of **Sweden**. The research encompassed fourteen in-depth interviews with various stakeholders, particularly focusing on authorities (including case officers and staff working at the Migration Agency, detention centres, the Border Police), civil society organisations active in the protection of the returnees’ rights (such as Caritas and Save the Children), one international organisation (UNHCR) and one private lawyer. The research team visited two detention centres under strict security measures (for more, see Barthoma and Tommos 2025).

In **Poland** the selected RMI was that of forced removals. The research team analysed the issuance and execution of the removal orders by the Border Guard as the competent authority. A total of 20 individual in-depth semi-structured interviews were conducted with representatives of public administration, international organisations, social organisations, and other experts and meso-level practitioners with knowledge and expertise regarding the return migration and return policy. The Border Guard authority preferred to participate through written communication. The research material was also enriched from two hybrid meetings (Polish) GAPs Stakeholder Expert Panel and several thematic events (conferences, workshops, seminars, and debates) in Poland and abroad dedicated to migration, asylum, and return issues (for more, see Krępa et al. 2025).

The RMI in **Georgia** was treated as the extension of the Polish one, with a focus on how Georgian nationals are received in their home country and what they are offered after return. Twenty-five individual in-depth interviews (in English, Russian and Polish) were conducted with representatives of international organisations, public institutions (including ministries), non-governmental organisations, and other experts (also Polish nationals specializing in the Southern Caucasus) (for more, see Krępa et al. 2025).

In **Turkey**, the research was designed as a multi-sited ethnography, which allowed for the examination of pushbacks and pushforwards within five different local contexts. In total, 29 semi-structured interviews were conducted with key informants and non-state actors, including government officials, NGO representatives, legal experts, and community leaders. Observation visits were made to 14 border villages and other significant border-crossing points. Two focus group meetings were also held with over 20 participants, including legal experts, practitioners, and scholars from the selected cities and with Syrian and Afghan NGOs. Despite extensive efforts, the securitized and centralized nature of the state apparatus has posed challenges to accessing state actors (for more, see Gökalp Aras et al. 2025).

In **Nigeria**, assisted returns and forced removals were treated as parts of a common RMI. The fifteen interviewees included both state and non-state actors, such as representatives from government agencies, civil society organisations, journalists, international organisations, and

repatriated migrants. A local NGO was used as an ‘entry point’ in order for the research team to build relationships of trust with potential informants, many of whom were skeptical initially (for more, see Uzomah and Madu 2025).

Forced deportations were selected as a case study in **Iraq**. The focus was on the case of the National Referral Mechanism as well as the Baghdad International Airport as the exclusive reception point designated by Iraqi authorities to receive returnees. The research team conducted interviews with fifty Iraqi returnees from EU countries, in addition to nine individual meetings with stakeholders, including governmental and non-governmental bodies. The researchers also benefited from meetings with international and local organisations such as the IOM and the European Technology and Training Centre (ETTC), as well as the outcomes of a roundtable conducted by the Hammurabi Human Rights Organization (HHRO). Some stakeholders were restricted from sharing information due to government regulations and several returnees were reluctant to participate in the research for social and security reasons (for more, see Warda and Al-Bayati 2025).

In the **Morocco** snapshot report, the main focus is on assisted returns, but certain aspects of forced removals to the country are also discussed. Both RMIs are examined through deskwork consisting of document and policy analysis, and of secondary analysis of field research conducted for older research projects on return migration to the country (for more, see Lahlou and Belhaj 2025).

In **Tunisia**, forced removals and assisted returns are considered together. The Tunisian report draws mainly on statistical data and previous publications, while two interviews were conducted, one with a representative of the German Agency for International Cooperation and one with a local civil society organisation (for more, see Boubakri et al., 2025).

Table 1. List of methods used and particular focus in each partner country.

No	Partner countries	RMI	‘Entry point’	No of interviews
1	Georgia	Forced removals & assisted returns	Reintegration to Georgia	25
2	Germany	Forced removals & assisted returns	The federal state of North Rhine-Westphalia	22
3	Greece	AVRR	OCAVRR & IOM headquarters, Athens	16
4	Iraq	Forced removals	National Referral Mechanism & Baghdad International Airport	9
5	Morocco	Assisted returns & forced removals	-	-
6	The Netherlands	Forced removals & assisted returns	DTenV Regievoerders & the LLV programme	22
7	Nigeria	Forced removals & assisted returns	Local NGO	15
8	Poland	Forced removals	Multi-sited fieldwork	20
9	Sweden	Forced removals & assisted returns	Märsta and Gävle detention centres	14
10	Tunisia	Forced removals & assisted returns	-	2

11	Turkey	Pushbacks and pushforwards & EU-Turkey Statement	Multi-sited ethnography in Ankara, Edirne, İstanbul, İzmir, Kırklareli	29
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Reflecting back on the WP3 methodology, few points should be mentioned, that are related, among others, with the present research's challenges and limitations.

As the WP3 coordinating team, we made substantial efforts to offer common guidelines on the organisation of the work of partner countries. Yet, although we organized methodological and conceptual work group sessions to co-construct the methodological approach, the entire idea of infrastructures came from migration studies with its strong epistemological bias to current migration debates at European institutes. As a consequence, as coordinators of this WP, we followed the principle of not imposing too much of the research design and guidelines on local research teams, but to permit a degree of differentiation. Even if we discussed and constructed a joint interview guide, all research teams at partner countries could use it to their own liking. Moreover, even if we asked to create flowmaps to make insightful the relations between actors, doings and materials and technologies, we deliberately did not propose a standardized template. Last but not least, we designed a common template for the country dossiers that partners had the opportunity to alter, based on their needs. All these flexibilities created a variety of insights, methodological choices, and research outputs that is rather difficult to 'synthesize'.

In relation to this latter point, it is crucial to note that interpretations of the concept of RMIs, its value, and the actual methods on the ground to study it varied considerably across different country teams. While some researchers had worked with the concept before, others were unfamiliar with it. While some of us are ethnographers by training, others had no explicit work experience with qualitative approaches. While some of us managed to arrange access with state and non-state actors, other research contexts made this simply impossible despite the efforts of the local research teams. It follows that this report is a synthesis of country dossiers that varied considerably. In some ways, this can be seen as a loss for the lack of comparative potential, at least to a particular extent, but on the other hand, it can be seen as an asset as it diversifies insights, methods and knowledges. In other words, it puts the decentring of migration studies into practice.

3. Conceptual framework

Conceptually, the notion of RMIs speaks to a larger debate in migration studies on how migration governance works out in practice. In this regard, this is a substantial body of literature that relates to the design of migration policies, both from the perspective of single countries (often being positioned as countries of origin, host, or transit countries) or from the perspective of a transnational or multi-level governance arena. Interestingly, many studies already acknowledge the diversification of actors involved (Andersson 2014). Van Riemsdijk, Marchand, and Heins (2021), for example, articulate the existence of a particular architecture behind the existing global migration governance arena. As they write, this architecture is by definition fragmented as it consists of international institutions that may have different agendas, policy priorities, and policy capacities (p.2). Koinova et al. (2024) foreground the ‘polycentric character’ of migration governance, pointing to the reality that ‘many centres’ address policy concerns regarding migration scattered over multiple sectors or domains (see Triandafyllidou 2022b for a similar argument).

Interestingly, while there has been a longstanding research tradition to focus on street-level bureaucrats or frontline workers, there is less of a street-level view regarding how this polycentric and complex governance character translates into more or less simultaneous governance-related practices of multiple actors causing relations, synergies, alignment, but possibly also disconnect and friction (see for a notable exception: Infantino 2023). Our conceptual operationalisation of RMIs seeks to exactly address this relational component of making migration governance work (or not) in practice. By moving away from the idea of singled out bureaucratic actors, it seeks to enrich both the fields of migration governance literature as well as the more critical debates on mobility/migration regimes. Based on the so-called ‘infrastructural turn’ in migration studies, and inspired by other contributions (most notably Leurs 2023, Lin et al. 2017), we foreground three main dimensions that in our view are pivotal to the RMIs’ approach: the crucial role of mediation; the social-material dimension of migration; and the political dimension of infrastructures, thus approaching it as a question of power.

3.1 Migration infrastructures and the question of mediation

Arguably, one of the most significant starting points for the infrastructural turn in migration studies is the intervention by Xiang and Lindquist in 2014. Their paper defines migration infrastructures as ‘the systematically interlinked technologies, institutions and actors that facilitate and condition mobility’ (2014, p.S122). It is a productive lens to understand how migration processes are not only a question of migrant decisions or the outcome of an autonomous government agency. The infrastructural approach underlines that migrants do not only move by themselves, but their movements are constantly mediated by a wide variety of actors – some actors facilitate their movements while others control them (Xiang and Lindquist 2014). In other words, infrastructures do not only produce mobility, but actually mediate or negotiate it (Meeus et al. 2019). These processes of mediating migration have become the central concern of the migration infrastructure approach (Kleist and Bjarnesen 2023). This *mediation* is crucial to understanding the power-ridden character of migration and mobility across the globe (Lin et al. 2017), including its dynamic and at times contradictory processes at play. With regard to the latter, we question the systemic starting point of infrastructures, as put forward by Xiang and Lindquist (2014) as we build in significant

analytical space to the disconnects, frictions, discontinuities, and inconsistencies that may emerge, as we articulate in the next section.

To sharpen our conceptual interpretation of migration infrastructures as forms of mediation further, it is good to position our view vis-à-vis other applications of the concept. Some scholars relate the notion of infrastructures explicitly to the question of how people migrate, and consequently limit the notion of infrastructures to networks that facilitate migrant movements (e.g. Düvell and Preiss 2022). We see this narrowing of the concept as problematic for particular reasons. First, in our view, the question of facilitation cannot be disconnected from the question of bordering, hampering, fragmenting, blocking, and preventing migrant movements from happening. To restrict migration in certain places, times, and trajectories is almost necessarily to produce migration of other/different spatialities, temporalities, and mobilities. Second, it tends to limit the empirical and conceptual discussion to brokers and facilitators located outside the state. The idea of forced returns shows that many state agencies are actually seeking to stimulate, broker, and facilitate forms of migration as well. Third, this reductionist approach looking at infrastructures as a network of brokers and facilitators, position migrants to a large degree outside the spaces of infrastructures, as if they are only passive users of pre-existing semi-structures and do not co-create their own infrastructuring practices and mediate their movements (e.g. see Wajsberg 2025 for an elaborative argument).

3.2 Migration infrastructures as socio-material platforms

It is of crucial importance to acknowledge both the non-human and human dimensions of infrastructures. We unbound the common notion of infrastructures – as roads, train tracks, ports – in three very different dimensions and see them instead as socio-material platforms. The first direction is that we incorporate the idea of people-as-infrastructure (Simone 2004; Wajsberg and Schapendonk 2022). Returns are also negotiated in very social spaces – such as asylum-related interviews, counselling sessions, community discussions, or shelters. Without conversations, emotions and expressions, social pressures *or* support, return operations would work out very differently. The second direction is that infrastructure not only relates to the surfaced hardware of mediation, but also the vehicles and instruments involved. Here we are inspired by the notion of *viapolitics* as developed by William Walters and colleagues (Walters 2015; Walters, Heller and Pezzani 2021; Teunissen 2020). We think that this discussion also corresponds with the invitation to study migration through migrants' attachment and relations with moving objects, i.e., to get involved in a process of 'thinking migration consistently through things' (Lauser et al. 2022, p.3). In addition, it is worthwhile to mention how some scholars bring dimensions of landscape and nature into this infrastructural discussion. This might at first sight seem to be far-fetched, but there are convincing examples of how riverbanks (Teunissen 2025) and islands (Morris 2021) are used as modes of controlling migratory movements. Thirdly, infrastructures always bring a dimension of logistics that take increasingly form in digital spaces. Consequently, an entire sub-debate has emerged around digital infrastructures, in both aspects of borders (Broeders and Dijkstra 2015, Pollozek and Passoth 2019, Frowd 2024) as well as migration processes (Sanchez-Querubin and Rogers 2018, Godin and Donà 2020) (see Leurs 2023 for an elaborative overview on digital migration studies).

As a result of all these elements it is worth to state that the socio-material dimensions of return migration infrastructures can translate both in a very concrete, tangible, and locatable

geography in terms of where and how infrastructuring take place (borders, islands, airports, roads, detention centres, migrant encounters with the state, etc.), but also in a very floating, intangible, and transnational geography of digitisation, databases, software systems, and diasporic atmospheres.

3.3 Migration infrastructures as a political space

As many contributions to the infrastructural turn suggest, notions of infrastructure can be best approached as a political space. While literature on regimes or deportation states start from spaces of domination (De Genova 2018), the relational dimension of infrastructure starts from the idea that infrastructures emerge from social-material practices (Meeus et al. 2019, p.17). To delve into this theoretical approach a bit further, it is important to understand its starting point that the world is shaped ‘through what entities *do* (with or to) each other in complex time/space constellations’ (Landau-Donnelly, Carlsson, Legendijk 2024, p.4). In the ontological sense, this implies that there is ‘no essence to objects or practices other than *their relational constitution and performance*’ (ibid., emphasis added). In other words, the infrastructure approach is much messier as it acknowledges how practices of mediation may be slowed down, contradicted, and contested. This is not to say that we approach processes of deportation, pushbacks, and migrant returns as less violent; it is rather to acknowledge that *what happens* is a consequence of political relations, and thus, power relations.

Seeing migration infrastructures as a political space thus emphasizes that ‘multiple platforms co-exist, within, beyond and against the state’ (Meeus et al. 2019). This co-existence of multiple platforms creates ‘spaces of intermediation’ (Shrestha and Yeoh 2018) that altogether (re)produce patterns of social inequality. Infrastructures are thus spaces of relational politics. In this regard, to articulate counterhegemonic dynamics that bypass mechanisms of migration control, some authors disentangle two types of infrastructures; infrastructures as modes of control and alternative infrastructures of transgression (Wajsberg 2025; Wajsberg and Schapendonk 2022). While this could be a very insightful approach, we lean with this report more towards the infrastructure as modes of control and seek to understand where and how formal and informal practices create contestation and resistance (see for some in-depth cases Mielke et al. 2025; Schapendonk et al. 2025). In the report below, for example, autonomous shelter organisations for migrants destabilise practices of the ‘deportation state’, advocacy groups may strive for collective regularisations for particular groups and lawyers may contest return decisions.

The localised politics of mobility often carry longer histories. In this respect it is worthwhile to stress a focus on detention and containment spaces, as inherent components of return migration infrastructures, reveal rather explicit post-colonial storylines (e.g. Davies and Isakjee 2019; Morris 2021). Asylum spaces and migrant camps in Western Europe are often former military terrains. The case study in the Netherlands addresses an asylum location which used to be a military terrain for ‘colonial troops’. Thus, those spaces that produced displacement in the past, are now spaces to contain the displaced in certain ways. This geography, however, expands considerably through other ‘imperial formations’ (Hom 2019). With transit and detention centres popping up in many parts of the Sahel region, the British plan of institutionalising the deportation centre in Rwanda, the use of prisons of El Salvador to detain deportees from the US during the contemporary deportation and criminalisation wave. The places where undesirable migrants are sent back to, are often the same spaces where resource extraction by Western powers unfolds (M’Charek 2020). It is important to highlight

that these infrastructures go beyond the material dimension. Through different financial channels, powerful (supra)states invest in better border technologies in places where unwelcome migrants depart from, including mobility control through biometric passports (Iwuoha and Doevenspeck 2025), the deployment of information systems (Uzomah 2024), and other forms of datafication (see for example Pollozek and Passoth 2019, Broeders and Dijkstra 2015, Yilmaz-Elmas and Schapendonk forthcoming). There is a strong coloniality involved in these developments. As Uzomah writes for the African contexts, these developments prioritise the expansion of European border protection over African interests (Uzomah 2024) and create ‘new problems’ and policy challenges.

4. Actors & relations

RMI involve multiple actors operating in a multiplicity of scales and performing a large variety of activities. Instead of a typology based on the positions the various actors possess in regards to return processes and procedures (see section 5 on doings), this section provides a classification of actors according to the political-geographical scale at which they operate.

A general summary of this classification for analytical purposes is presented in Table 4.1. In real life, various actors operate across scales, as for example happens with national and local branches of international organisations and NGOs, and with consulate authorities. To take only one example, IOM is an *intergovernmental* organisation but maintains national units (e.g. IOM Germany, IOM Greece, IOM Turkey, etc.) which may be responsible to run *national* assisted return projects; in turn these national units may have *local* teams responsible for outreach activities in specific places of interest and *individual* IOM officers working within other collective actors, as liaisons.

Certain differences among countries obviously exist. To some extent, they reflect the countries' position in the general geopolitical patterns of return migration in our times. Thus, we can distinguish the countries of migrants' origin (and of destination for that matter), i.e. Nigeria, Georgia, and Iraq, from the EU member-states. Among the latter, we can distinguish those that belong to the European core (Germany, Sweden, the Netherlands) from those of the European border (Greece, Poland). Turkey, Tunisia, and Morocco may be included in another category, since, apart from countries of migrants' origin, they are also major transit countries right outside the European gateway. Again, in what follows, we avoid focusing too much on these differences to show better the cross-national landscape of RMIs actors.

Table 2. Overview of main actors in RMIs by level of operation

Level	Examples
<i>International</i>	International organisations (IOM, UNHCR, ICMPD) INGOS (International Red Cross / Crescent, Caritas etc.) Private companies (e.g. airlines)
<i>Supranational</i>	EU institutions EU devoted agencies (Frontex, EU Return Coordinator, High-Level Network for Returns, FRA) European Court of Human Rights Court of Justice of the European Union
<i>National/Federal</i>	Governmental departments (devoted Ministries) National authorities (devoted agencies, such as the Greek Asylum Service and the Swedish Migration Agency) Law enforcement (Police, Border Guard, Coast Guard etc.) Consulates National courts External monitoring mechanisms NGOs and CSOs Private companies (e.g. security, medical services)
<i>Sub-national</i>	Regional and local authorities NGOs and CSOs Private companies

	Private lawyers
<i>Community/local society</i>	Family members Individual activists Human smugglers Other

4.1 International level

At the international level, IOM has a unique position as a major intergovernmental organisation specializing in managing voluntary returns in the countries of residence, transit, and countries of origin and has developed an integrated approach to the full spectrum of return, readmission and reintegration, supported by globally applying guidelines⁵. IOM sees *'safe and dignified return and sustainable reintegration [as] an indispensable part of a comprehensive approach to migration management'*. The organisation has established several Country Offices around the globe, which are responsible for developing national plans of action offices, according to guidelines provided by (superior) Regional Offices⁶. Such country offices operate in all the countries reviewed for this report.

Other international organisations include UNHCR that in some countries (e.g. Turkey and Iraq) collaborates with IOM monitoring the voluntary character of returns, and international development agencies that although based in specific national territories, are intrinsically involved in return procedures in the receiving countries (often in the field of returnees' reintegration, see for example Mielke et al. 2025 for the case of Germany), underpinning the (coerced) relationship of returns with development. The following description from the Nigeria case, aptly presents this constellation of international actors involved in the return processes there.

'IOM (International Organization for Migration) is pivotal in managing the entire process of Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR), providing essential support for returnees. ICMPD (International Centre for Migration Policy Development) offers policy advice and financial assistance to the Nigerian government [...]. It is known for sponsoring migration workshops aimed at enhancing the capacity of stakeholders involved in the reintegration process. The role of FRONTEX (European Border and Coast Guard Agency) has been controversial, with many viewing its activities as an infringement on human rights. [...] The GIZ (German Agency for International Cooperation) (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit) provides technical cooperation and funding for various return activities in Nigeria, including stakeholder meetings and reintegration support in key cities [...]. GIZ has been successful in providing necessary support packages to returnees from Germany, facilitating smoother transitions and reducing the likelihood of conflict or dissatisfaction. But these are usually for returnees from Germany. There are also critiques regarding the need to

⁵ IOM's Policy on the Full Spectrum of Return, Readmission and Reintegration (2021). Available at: www.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbd1486/files/documents/ioms-policy-full-spectrum-of-return-readmission-and-reintegration.pdf

⁶ For a further discussion on IOM and UNHCR discourses and role in returns, see Ahouga 2024.

extend support to other underserved regions in Nigeria' (Uzomah and Madu 2025, pp.17-18).

On the other hand, some big international NGOs (INGOs) also deal with various aspects of return. Red Cross for example is variously involved in legal advice and representation, psychosocial support and counselling. Interestingly, albeit participating in the wider international Red Cross and Red Crescent movement, it is generally the national Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies that undertake specific activities in contexts as diverse as the Swedish asylum system and the 'Syrian Crisis Humanitarian Relief Operation' in Turkey. NGOs also engage in networking with each other. This is the case of the ERSO platform which was established already in 2007 by nine European NGOs with the mission 'to improve the quality and effectiveness of counseling and return assistance for migrants returning to their countries of origin'⁷.

4.2 Supranational level

Undoubtedly, the EU, as a supranational organisation in the sense of its 'autonomous regulatory power' (Lindseth 2014), is one of the major – if not the most important – actors regarding migration governance (including returns). Yet, its role might be explicit or implicit, concerning the formulation of directives and policies, the relations with diplomatic and governmental actors, including the agreements with third countries, the support in the national and international security apparatus and, crucially, the funding it distributes to the respective EU and Third Countries. In Morocco, the Emergency Trust Fund established in 2015 is a good example of how the EU negotiates return and reintegration with countries of migrants' origin (see GAPs' WP5). There is a power-geography impacting the role of the EU in returns (Stel et al. 2025). EU's power and significance increases in EU border countries which are tasked with apprehending migration as well as in relation to Third countries that enter into negotiations with the EU concerning the implementation of returns (identifying and accepting returnees) and the currently debated establishment of return hubs (the externalisation of returns) (Şahin-Mencütek and Barthoma 2025).

This power-geography can be vividly illustrated through the formulation of the EU-Turkey common Statement in 2016 which, although it is not the only such Statement has been extensively debated. Similarly, the importance of the EU-Iraqi government negotiations in formulating, and later signing, the Association Agreement are crucial. Similar bilateral agreements also emerge with specific (often wealthier) countries which also feature prominently in the international system of returns.

More specific tasks are undertaken by devoted EU agencies, as -among others- Frontex, the EU border agency that assists with the management of the EU external borders and is a key actor in coordinating return operations by flight (see also Ben Othmen 2025). Frontex has been also recently tasked with return counselling and reintegration issues. Frontex is particularly active in border countries such as Greece and Poland, supporting the national authorities with border control, despite being sometimes judged as insufficient, as by several Polish stakeholders. Moreover, Frontex is also relevant in other countries, like in the Netherlands and Germany, since apart from activities directly connected with border control, it is crucially involved in the organisation of return flights and in the development and maintenance of data

⁷ For more details, see the ERSO network's web page at: www.ersonetwork.org

management tools, such as the RECAMAS reference model. For this reason, the role of Frontex is significant in ‘enabling the exchange of information between entities involved in the return procedure regarding logistic aspects’, as the Border Guard representatives in Poland put it (Krepa et al. 2025, p.25). Agencification (for more, see section 4.3) has been expanding in the EU, including in the area of migration, raising several questions and critiques over the soaring power and lack of accountability of certain agencies (Carrera et al. 2019; Chiti 2025; Gliati 2024; Schmeer 2022).

Though incomplete yet, a level of Europeanisation of return migration infrastructures is pursued, as for example with training programmes in return and reintegration counselling. Characteristically, one of the informants representing the specialized Dutch governmental agency that is responsible for the governing of return processes (DtenV), noted that colleagues of his meet with similar staff of several other countries to offer training in ‘motivating techniques for return conversations’ and show best practices. These trainings are organized under the umbrella of Frontex. Sweden also maintains an active role in these trainings, among others, through the development of training material and by supplying trainers.

Additionally, the European Court of Human Rights decides on cases of human rights violations lodged by individuals or groups and the Court of Justice of the European Union deals with requests for preliminary rulings from national courts. There have been pivotal cases impacting return migration decisions and practices concerning both EU-Third countries as well as intra-EU returns, as for example was the case of *M.S.S. v. Belgium and Greece* (2011) and the more recent case of *H.T. v. Germany and Greece* (2024).

Nevertheless, it is important to note that the EU (and its agencies) has its own internal power-dynamics that reflect national political priorities and interests, and as such it can be considered both as an actor as well as a relational apparatus of different actors.

4.3 National level

National governments clearly reflect this multi-scalar actors’ involvement described in the introduction. They have already been present at the international level, through their bilateral agreements, diplomatic services and, in some cases, their international development agencies. Yet, their role is immensely more significant at the national level (as well as in the local). The national governments (or federated state governments in the case of Germany) with their devoted departments/ministries play a very proactive role regarding returns even before the actual process of individual return is initiated for a given migrant. They are tasked with:

- *Setting the legislative terrain including incorporating EU directives.*
- *Defining the desired/undesired nationalities* through their Safe Country of Origin lists but also, implicitly, through practices that hinder international protection or even claiming asylum for certain nationalities or at specific times. The latter has been the case during the 2020 tensions at the Greece-Turkey border (Gökalp Aras et al. 2025; Papatzani et al. 2025) and in 2021 at the Poland-Belarus border (Krepa et al. 2025).
- *Negotiating and formulating bilateral agreements between host countries and countries of origin.*

Diplomatic services, including both the embassies and consulates (and liaison officers) in Third countries as well as the embassies and consulates of Third countries in EU ones, are

increasingly involved in different aspects of return procedures. Such involvement might entail negotiating higher level diplomatic agreements among sending and receiving countries, providing identification documents for returnees, collaborating in day-to-day procedures in both forced and assisted returns, as well as gathering information about specific countries and communicating information both about migration and returns (forced or not). Sweden for example has a targeted body of officers placed overseas –the liaison officers– who constitute a kind of ‘returns intelligence’ body that informs the respective national government departments. More particularly, ‘return liaison officers are mid-level officials stationed abroad to enhance law enforcement efforts by leveraging local expertise and networks to verify the identities of irregular migrants and assisting in Joint Return Operations coordinated by Frontex’ (Barthoma and Tommos 2025, p.34).

- *Addressing the security issues and concerns through their police, army and navy bodies*

The role of law enforcement authorities is important in all European countries. This does not solely concern forced removals, as it might seem evident, but also for assisted returns. In the case of Greece, migrants who register in the AVRRE programme are requested to visit the Aliens’ Directorate of the Hellenic Police and ask for an interoffice note that is equivalent to a return decision. Also, in case returnees participate in the AVRRE but are held in detention, the police escort them to the airport. Law enforcement may be shared by multiple actors as characteristically in the Dutch case, where the Royal Police, the National Police, Custodial Institutions Agency and the transportation service of the Ministry of Security and Justice are all involved at various parts of the return procedures. In Germany both the State Police and the Federal Police are involved. The dominant power exerted by these law enforcement authorities can be bodily (as in the case of arrests and detention), bureaucratic (in terms of a strict set of rules to be followed without exceptions or not allowing for the involvement of other CSO or monitoring actors) or soft (such as persuasion).

Besides police authorities, the Army (and Navy), the Coast Guard and specialized Border Guards where they exist are also crucial for returns as they commonly are the first ‘face’ of the respective national authority a migrant encounters when arriving at a given country. Whilst tasked with the duty to guide people to safety and to procedural route for applying for asylum (or similar), especially in peripheral, border EU countries, these bodies are also involved (as stated or alleged) in overt or covert pushback and pushforward operations. On the other hand, law enforcement agencies are also significant in the countries of return. In Tunisia, returning migrants are frequently subjected to excessive identity checks, which may include detailed interrogations and, in some cases, mistreatment.

- *Agencification*

Although the central government administration and the respective ministries and judicial bodies play a key role in managing returns (for more, see Gökalp Aras et al. 2024), in the last decades we have witnessed the increasing powers of specific national agencies which are either established or enlarged in order to address and implement specific parts of return migration processes. In most of the EU countries researched in this WP, we discern an increased centralisation of the return process and at the same time an augmenting of powers of specific national agencies, indicating that states should not be seen as monolithic entities but as complex fields where sovereign power is performed.

For example, the Swedish Migration Agency (SMA) has a pivotal role in the return process, including decision making on migrants' detention and transportation. The Agency collaborates closely with the Police Authority and the Prison and Probation Service, marking the increased significance of national law enforcement agencies as central actors.

Similarly in the Netherlands, Dienst Terugkeer en Vertrek (DtenV), translated as Repatriation and Departure Service, is the specialized Dutch governmental agency responsible for the governing of return processes since its establishment in 2007. It puts the Dutch return policy in practice and consists of several units, showing an internal division of labour between harder and softer measures, as indicated by the Directorate of Supervision and Punitive Measures and the Directorate of Return Counselling and Preparation, respectively. The bulk of the work is performed by the individual *regievoerders* who combine a role of return counselors with coordinating and monitoring duties.

Likewise, Greece has established a Directorate for Returns and Withdrawals since 2020, as a unit of the Ministry of Migration and Asylum. It is the country's main authority responsible for migrants' returns at the national scale, but in comparison with its Dutch 'equivalent', it seems to be more occupied with coordination and monitoring rather than with counselling at the everyday level. In both Greece and the Netherlands, procedures initiated by other state agencies (like the Asylum Service and the Immigratie en Naturalisatiedienst (IND)), affect return processes. In Turkey, the restructured Presidency of Migration Management (PMM) also plays a pivotal role in coordinating returns:

'Working in collaboration with international bodies such as IOM, UNHCR, and ICMPD, the PMM administers return programs, manages technical assistance for reintegration, and coordinates legal frameworks with a focus on maintaining adherence to international standards of refugee protection. Additionally, the removal centres and Temporary Accommodation centres are crucial components of the institutional framework' (Gökalp Aras et al. 2025, p.28).

Perhaps nowhere is this more evident than in Poland where the Border Guard is the competent authority for the implementation of the return policy, and in particular for actions related to organising voluntary and forced returns of third-country nationals.

'The leading institution in the management of returns in Poland is Border Guard. The Commander-in-Chief of the Border Guard is the key state authority entitled to issue administrative decisions resulting in an obligation of the foreigner to leave the territory of Poland. At the same time, the Border Guard remains the competent authority for the implementation of the return policy, and in particular for actions related to organising voluntary and forced returns of third-country nationals to their country of origin. [...] In practice, the Border Guards cumulates almost overall power regarding both deciding and enforcing forced removals' (Krepa et al. 2025, p.20).

From the different country cases, it becomes apparent that 2016, just after the peak of the so-called refugee crisis, is a turning point for the restructuring of national agencies concerned with returns and for the expansion of their remit and powers for most EU countries as well as for Turkey. At the other end of the spectrum, receiving countries also reorganised their migration ministries and agencies accordingly, as in the case of Iraq. However, the importance of critical moments should not be exaggerated. Some countries did have significant progress

in building their RMIs during previous cycles of institutional transformations, as is the case of EU countries changing their legal frameworks in accordance with European law. In general, although some actors emerge in the short run of specific ‘crises’, the crystallisation of the most powerful actors takes time.

The shift towards more restrictive migration policies has resulted in a further institutionalisation of return processes, characterized by expanded roles for various authorities, the reorganisation of existing governance structures, and improved cooperation and coordination among governmental and non-governmental entities.

The terrain of actors active at the national level also includes the national branches of international NGOs (such as the Red Cross and Crescent) as well as national NGOs that operate both nationally and locally. Thus distinguishing the national-level actors from the international-level ones involved in returns can be complicated as their remit crosses the different scales. In the case of Sweden, governmental agencies engage with CSOs in return efforts primarily through ad hoc initiatives and short-term projects, reflecting the constrained opportunities afforded to CSOs, which often necessitates alignment with governmental policies. Nevertheless, NGOs/CSOs play a significant role in the returns process, not least in terms of support (legal and psycho-social) and communication as well as monitoring.

This cross-level cooperation (and its challenges) is evident in most countries, both receiving and sending. As characteristically described for the case of Iraq:

‘The most important of these [actors] are the Ministry of Migration and Displacement, the Ministry of Interior, the Iraqi National Security Service, the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), the International Organization for Migration (IOM), the German International Cooperation Society (GIZ), United Iraqi Medical Society for Relief and Development, the European Technology and Training Centre, the Women Empowerment Organization, the International Centre for Migration Policy Development, and the Hammurabi Human Rights Organization’ (Warda and Al-Bayati 2025, p.11).

In other cases, large international NGOs with their national branches may cooperate and exchange knowledge and resources and provide guidance to national/local partners, in an environment of poor state intervention, as for example with the partnership between Caritas International Belgium and Orient-Occident Foundation in Morocco, where a national policy on Moroccan returnees remains elementary.

When migrants appeal against return decisions, national courts of law in countries of residence emerge as important actors in reviewing these decisions. The same applies separately to detention decisions for returnees. As institutions of the juridical system and independent from executive power, the courts act in practice as a monitoring mechanism vis-à-vis the conformity of individual returns with legal standards.

Lastly, actors responsible for the external evaluation and monitoring of return infrastructures are also often organized at the national level to assess the functioning of the entire system of returns (rather than performing case-based assessment). As an independent authority, the Greek Ombudsman is the country’s official mechanism for the external monitoring of forced returns and oversees human rights issues. Another body, the Greek National Commission for Human Rights has established a Recording Mechanism of Informal Forced Returns (pushbacks). In Germany, a state parliamentary committee, the Petitions Committee, can review state authorities’ decisions on forced removals. Therefore, it can organise case hearings and based on special rights giving it access to all authorities and

administrations under state control, it can inspect files, request information and order on-site visits to control and eventually suggest correcting administrative decisions. The case of Sweden seems different, since the monitoring of return operations is under the responsibility of the SMA which is the same primary governance actor within the country's RMIs.

Another important issue to mention is the involvement of service providers, particularly with regard to the practical steps necessary for the implementation of returns. Characteristic examples include the commercialised healthcare providers hired by the authorities, particularly in Germany and the Netherlands, for medical assessments, and public hospitals and public health services provided to migrants.

4.4 Subnational level

The sub-national level of returns procedures is also constituted by a shifting constellation of actors, including both subnational state administration (local and regional authorities) and humanitarian actors (local NGOs and civil society organisations, volunteer groups) as well as private entities, such as security firms and companies providing various services from medical care to catering to transportation to legal aid.

Regional and local authorities are usually responsible for implementing specific administrative procedures rather than developing their own autonomous return policies and initiatives. For example, in Poland, the tasks of the Departments for Foreigners at Voivodeship Offices include, in particular, administrative proceedings in matters concerning temporary residence permits, permanent residence permits and long-term resident permits for citizens of the European Union. At the provincial level in Turkey, the Provincial Directorates of Migration Management (PDMs), are the primary institutions responsible for implementing national migration policies. While they receive applications for voluntary returns and oversee deportations, they cannot undertake independent actions without prior authorisation from the central administration, highlighting the top-down governance model in Turkey's migration management.

On the other hand, local municipalities in the Netherlands have a main coordinating/chair role in the LVV programme (Landelijke Vreemdelingenvoorziening) that aims at coordinating accommodation for migrants with no right to stay. Apart from providing services, municipal authorities proved active in negotiating the continuation of the programme and in developing their objectives and priorities. In Germany, already a federalisation, local (municipal) Foreigners' Authorities below the level of the federal state are responsible for the enforcement of returns. Although their offices seemingly have a merely executive mandate, internal interpretations of their duties lead to different decision outcomes in one jurisdiction from the other.

Local NGOs and CSOs play a crucial role, both direct and indirect, in the whole process of return. They may provide information and emergency support for those in need (including legal advice), they may contest juridical decisions, policies and practices through their monitoring and advocacy of protection and return procedures (such as the Greek Council for Refugees or some Regional Bar Associations in Turkey or NGOs specializing in legal support for foreigners and activist groups in Poland, etc.) or, through tiny practices to indirectly smoothen these processes at the same time. In Germany, various refugee councils at the municipal level, welfare organisations (Caritas NRW, AWO, Diakonie Rheinland-Westfalen-Lippe) and their representatives/social workers in various places (central and communal

accommodation facilities, detention facility) as well as counselling services (psychosocial centres and counselling offices for victims of human trafficking) offer advice and assistance for potential deportees, legal literacy and possibly options to avoid removal.

Unfortunately, this is not always the case, since the state might impose its power upon local and regional NGOs and limit their involvement, deter them from getting involved or silence them. Limiting NGOs' role solely to *'invited' space has been the case in Sweden, where NGOs were 'given space to the extent they are found "useful". Otherwise, return discourse is very rigid, [...]. Therefore, there is not much room to manoeuvre'* (Barthoma and Tommos 2025, p.35). According to Barthoma and Tommos (2025), this situation has resulted in 'a largely accepted 'silence' about return operations, restrictive measures introduced in the field'. Comparably, in Turkey, the Edirne Bar Association, despite holding a significant position, has *'limited engagement in certain areas' to the point that one interviewee described it as being 'almost like The Silence of the Lambs – there's no one, no lawyers'* (Gökalp Aras et al. 2025, p.75).

Local NGOs and CSOs are also important in the countries of return if it is to improve safety and reintegration prospects. In Nigeria, CSOs are often more focused in returnees' demands compared to government agencies, but they face challenges such as funding limitations. Many CSOs are faith-based organisations (FBOs), which can make their training programmes less sustainable, particularly when they are run by individuals with limited resources.

Interestingly, even actors of the international or the national level present local variations in their activities and depend upon local underpinnings they may develop. One characteristic example is the open accommodation centre for AVRRR in Athens. While it is run by an *international* organisation such as IOM as part of a *national* assisted return programme, OCAVRR can be seen as a quasi-autonomous local actor, not only because of its specific location but also because of its administration's understanding of it as an innovative accommodation solution and an alternative to detention. In a very different and unique context, several church communities in Germany have been active in providing church asylum for many years. Based on their volunteers and local support networks, both catholic and evangelical parishes evolve into local actors that exploit the nationwide agreement of their parent ecclesiastic authorities with the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (BAMF) on church asylum. Sometimes they even go further, by deviating from the official ecclesiastic rhetoric that sees no connection between church asylum and civil disobedience

Local dynamics are also important in contesting return policies on the ground. Various human rights organisations have raised concerns about the legality and ethicality of deportations (let alone pushbacks), including Amnesty International (AI), the Asylum Information Database (AIDA), the European Centre for Constitutional and Human Rights (ECCHR), the European Council on Refugees and Exile (ECRE), the Human Rights Watch (HRW), InfoMigrants (IM), and the Aegean Boat Report (ABR), among others. Their international character is certainly important but as the German case shows, proactive opposition to deportations depends on protests organized at the local level, e.g. by blocking roads to and runways at airports.

Moreover, local (and local branches of international) NGOs and CSOs are extremely important on the receiving end of the returns process. In cooperation or not with the state, they are responsible for a range of issues returnees face: from psycho-social and/or sustenance support, to mobility transfers as well as to an array of re-integration options. In Nigeria, local CSOs are involved in a multitude of tasks:

‘Nigeria CSOs support the provision of reintegration assistance, in coordination and collaboration with relevant partners and monitor and evaluate the returnees’ reintegration progress. They also assist in the monitoring of returnees’ associations and engage in advocacy to improving RRR [return, readmission, and reintegration] of returnee migrants. The CSOs are often more focused in their demands compared to government agencies, but they face challenges such as proliferation, funding limitations, and capacity building. Many CSOs are faith-based organisations (FBOs), which can make their training programmes less sustainable, particularly when they are run by individuals with limited resources’ (Uzomah and Madu 2025, p.18).

As expected, within this migration – humanitarian nexus, which has soared in the past 10-15 years, some actors provide crucial work while others exploit funding opportunities for their own individual profit. Migrants, whether in the asylum procedure or in other conditions of regular and irregular residence in a country, often rely on private lawyers who can legally challenge rejections of asylum applications or attempt in other ways to regularise a stay. Private lawyers are all the more important in places and in times that legal aid is missing or fragmented, as has been reported for Greece.

Besides sub-national non-state actors (such as NGOs and CSOs), return operations increasingly involve a number of private sector actors – both companies and individual entrepreneurs – who are tasked with the rather ‘mundane’ aspects of return operations (albeit very lucrative ones). First and foremost, return mobilities cannot take place without airline and coach companies which literally enact the return from one territory to another. Adding to them, are the array of local drivers and taxis that may transport returnees - before, during and after their return – when necessary. Private companies are also tasked with taking care of the cleaning and catering services provided in pre-departure centres and in detention facilities. On the receiving end, local private entrepreneurs are crucially involved in handling re-integration funds and charging for the promised goods (in the case of AVR or other return programmes). These private entities further accentuate the multitude and diversity of actors involved in return processes.

Nevertheless, the system of private entrepreneurs cannot be complete without reference to the ‘shadow’ apparatuses that informally ‘accompany’ people on the move. Diverse businesses and freelancers ‘cater’, profit and exploit people who are caught within pushbacks and pushforwards as well as who wish to move under the radar during a given time as mentioned in the Greek and Turkish country-cases.

4.5 Community/local society level

Although their autonomy and agency are restricted by multiple layers of governance institutions, various individuals can develop their own initiatives and doings regarding return policies and implementation. Evidently, migrants themselves have their own important share, but since migrants’ agency is further studied in WP7 we do not deal with them as separate actors here.

The community/local society level also include a variety of both formal and informal agents. Local networks of support and extended families may embody diverse roles, from support and re-integration to shaming. Family members in the country of origin play an important role in what concerns the returnees’ reintegration. While families can be a key source of support in

terms of material assistance, guidance, psychological relief and so on, they may also be sources of shame and stigmatisation, especially for returnees who already experience their returns as personal failure. The Georgian case shows that strong family ties are important especially in safeguarding access to housing but at the same time family members expectations from returnees can be burdensome (Krepa et al. 2024, 2025).

Informal facilitators play a major role in shaping migration patterns and they are often organized in large smuggling networks with inter-local connections. Greece and Turkey offer interesting examples of informality, along with the connections of informal and formal actors. In Greece, the role of balaclava-clad, black uniformed and/or paramilitary in carrying out pushbacks has been repeatedly attested. In the past years, reports pinpoint to the involvement of other migrants who are either coerced in doing so (Lighthouse reports 2022) or play a more active role (i.e. as translators, ‘commandos’, etc.) in direct contact with the Greek police. In Turkey, a similar informal network of pushforwards exists, involving local villagers, taxi and bus drivers etc. The Turkish state’s approach reflects a calculated non-enforcement stance, in which smuggling networks are not actively dismantled, effectively enabling migrants to attempt crossings into Greece.

4.6 A complex landscape

Non-linearity and complexity are evident in all types of RMIs in all examined countries. It is of crucial importance to understand that RMIs have, by definition, a multileveled and multi-scalar character, from the translocal to the transnational, and this brings ‘uncertain political geographies that are simultaneously produced at the configurations of power relations at various levels’ (Aparna and Schapendonk 2020, p.232). For instance, European administrations rely first and foremost on the cooperation of the governmental representatives of migrant countries of return in the phase of identification and documentation.

To start with, procedural complexities may be caused by the legal framework defining the governance of returns, as for example in the case of forced removals in Greece where two different legal frameworks are in force simultaneously. In other cases, the structure of specific state administration increases legal complexities from the beginning. Such an example is Germany, where the federal law assigns the local government the responsibility for the enforcement of returns. This contributes to the higher complexity of institutions and actors involved and creates substantial levels of autonomy on the federal level.

Another issue is the fragmentation of funding schemes. This creates particular uncertainties for NGOs in terms of the size of the organisations as well as the design of their practices. Next to these institutional dimensions, the complexity of procedures relates to ‘legal fragilities’ that are lived realities of both professionals working in the RMIs as well as migrants subjected to them (Gill et al. 2025, p.13).

A third, and related, reality that intensifies the complexity of RMIs is the dynamic and antagonistic relationality involved. This means that the doings of one actor are related to, if not dependent on, the doings of other actors. Yet, this interdependency also implies that the doings of one actor can be made undone by others in this web of actors. As one case worker in the Netherlands tellingly indicated:

‘Every move we make will result in a countermove [made by others] in the opposite direction. The only thing we can do, is that whatever we do, we do in a very detailed way’.

His colleagues from Germany had similar readings and used the metaphor of a game –where some players don't cooperate– or perhaps play soccer, where one team cannot always win. This undoing of other doings is more often than not associated with migrants, their collective agency and their 'alternative infrastructuring practices' (Wajsberg and Schapendonk 2022); with legal contestation by lawyers; and with the role of NGOs and communities that seek to prevent migrant returns.

4.7 Relations among actors

Asymmetric power relations

Within this complex and multi-scalar system that shapes returns migration, relations among actors take many forms that are not necessarily stable throughout time – besides, temporality is crucial in the understanding of RMIs. Since returns have become a highly politicized topic, power relations and negotiation among actors thrive and constitute an apparatus of asymmetric power relations and influence, that tend to fluctuate according to political interests and 'crises'. Such asymmetries of power relations reproduce established and cross-cutting inequalities among Global North and Global South, among wealthier and poorer countries, among heartlands (of EU) and peripheries (Greece, Poland, Turkey). This is clearly manifested in the negotiations and formulations of EU and bilateral agreements with Third countries that tend to coerce returns in exchange of development and trade assistance, which, one could argue resemble or reproduce (neo)colonial relations (see for example Achiume 2019; Gutiérrez Rodríguez 2019; McNeill 2023; Rajaram 2024).

Asymmetric power relations run through the whole terrain of return migration, be they among National Migration and Border agencies and migrants or CSO organisations, law enforcement bodies and migrants or at times, among migrants who are categorized as desired or undesirable based on their nationalities. The dominant role of law enforcement authorities is further confirmed in some countries. In Poland for example, there is a significant asymmetry among actors involved in the procedures of forced removals. After a legal amendment ceding to the Border Guard the responsibility for determining appeals, the issuing and implementation of return decisions became an internal matter of this body, and the role of other actors was reduced to a minimum. Nevertheless, this does not mean that the Border Guard controls the migration policy or possesses the power to fully determine the situation of a foreigner.

On the other hand, 'soft' power strategies are also employed in persuading migrants to cooperate and return voluntarily – especially in Northern European countries examined (Germany, Netherlands and Sweden) as this fits with the portrayed liberal - humanitarian – effective approach they claim to endorse. Establishing or promoting a looser, conversational relationship between officers and migrants becomes thus an implicit strategy that operationalizes informality as guise.

In addition, equally common are restrictions imposed on organisations (NGOs and CSOs) or individuals or even on monitoring organisations, regarding assisting and monitoring the return operations. This is particularly the case for forced returns, but it is also encountered in 'voluntary returns'. Specifically at the national and sub-national levels, local NGOs and CSOs may find themselves involved in relations of dependency (or co-dependency) with the larger INGOs and national agencies. For example, in Sweden, local NGOs/CSOs are given a limited remit, and they are at times concerned with being associated with returns. In Poland on the

other hand, local NGOs/CSOs may find themselves in a difficult position if they become too critical of certain doings. Although some may argue that they facilitate state-coerced returns, it seems that NGOs / CSOs play a pivotal intermediary role that somehow ‘humanizes’ the return process and monitors violations and wrong doings. At the same time though, they are vulnerable to relations of dependency (and possibly pacification).

On the other end of the return process, in the receiving countries, local NGOs/CSOs are central in building relations both with national and international authorities as well as with migrants and their families/communities. The importance of technical coordination among such actors is reflected in IOM’s initiative to establish joint working groups, as for example the Reintegration Working Group in Morocco. Once again, relations of dependency (especially in terms of aims, funds and programmes) and co-optation can be identified, with the EU and certain EU States playing a pivotal role in setting the agenda (Lahlou 2021) of returns and categorizing people as deserving, desirable and undeserving. Yet, despite this restrictive and imposing context, the realities and practicalities of local contexts inevitably entail degrees of informality that allow local NGOs and CSOs to negotiate their practices according to their understandings. And overall, especially in the subnational level where things need to be done, relations often tend to be rather collaborative – albeit with complaints of lack of proper coordination and instances of corruption among the numerous authorities involved (especially from Iraq, Tunisia and Nigeria). Yet at the same time, there are ‘cracks’ from where different actors manage to challenge existing relations – especially regarding migrants’ support and human rights protection.

Relations of competition

Key informants from Greece and the Netherlands, pointed to manifestations of competition among actors in their attempts to be more effective in the return programmes they run. Competition may occur among various programmes of assisted return but also between assisted and non-assisted returns. The former case is evident in the Netherlands, where for some NGOs that offer return assistance, the Europeanisation of assisted returns through the EURP/ Joint Reintegration Service (JRS) programme caused some significant shift, as state actors may use this programme and take over the role these NGOs play. The latter case was marked by a representative of IOM Greece, involved in the AVRR programme, who commented that the police authorities are also interested in increasing the number of forced removals. By adding that some migrants may actually ‘prefer to depart with Frontex’ (e.g. because a Frontex flight is scheduled earlier than an AVRR one), he also seemed to describe the competition among actors almost in terms of attracting clients for return who act as rational decision makers.

However, competition is only one aspect of the complex relations among actors, since, from other points of view, an effective return is the desired outcome no matter the level of enforcement and assistance. This may be the point of view of the Dutch DTenV regievoorders who, as case workers, have the dual role of promoting assisted returns and implementing forced ones.

Informal relations

Informality inserts itself in all aspects of the return system; it seems to be interwoven with it, on all scales, and affecting most actors implicitly or explicitly. From ‘classified’ high-level negotiations and power-plays within the EU and among the EU and Third countries, to the

materialities of pushbacks and pushforwards and the affective infrastructures at the places of return, a spectrum of informality ‘escorts’ most aspects of return processes (see for example, Şahin-Mencütek et al. 2025). Informal relations might entail relations of support of migrants before, during and after the return process but, on the other hand, they might also entail illegal processes such as pushbacks/forwards, arbitrary detention, kidnapping or smuggling of various forms. In between, there is a vast field of informal practices embedded in legal ambiguities and in the gray areas of return procedures.

In Turkey, diverse informal relations can be observed in border places (villages) from where migrants pass en route to crossing the borders. While these informal networks are rooted locally, they also have links with major urban centres such as Istanbul and Izmir. Although these informal relations and practices become more apparent in border areas, underscoring the importance of geography in the migration and returns process, their links are multiscalar, hinting at a less visible informal system of relations that intertwines (sometimes) with the institutional ones.

Location, from a different perspective, becomes important in the process of returns also through the practice of co-location. Instituted via the ‘hotspot’ approach for Greece and Italy in 2016, co-location is a practice increasingly adopted by several countries. Its main aim has been to put the key returns (and identification) actors in ‘one place’ to facilitate coordination and make more efficient the overall process. While it is not clear how this approach has worked –for a number of reasons– it may possibly facilitate greater cooperation between actors in formal and informal ways.

5. Doings

As we have already argued, the different types of RMIs discussed in this report (AVRR, forced removals, and pushbacks), are characterized by a continuum of coercion rather than strict dichotomous division (e.g. Şahin-Mencütek and Triandafyllidou 2025). Besides the question of coercion, there are other categorical aspects that matter greatly, especially in non-European contexts. In line with our conceptual and theoretical framework, the modes of implementation of all RMI types, what we have called ‘doings’, are not characterized by a linear sequence, but by increased complexity and a dynamic circuit that includes multiple steps, different temporalities, cul-de-sacs, points of exit, circularity, and feedback loops. These doings may relate to different types of activities, such as administrative and legal work, counselling work, operational work, medical and care work, among others. In this section, we create analytical cross-overs between different country cases as well as different types of infrastructures by following a fourfold categorisation that is deliberately kept broad. The first category is *detection and differentiation* of return cases and discusses different ways to-be-returned migrants are to be known and categorized through administrative processes. The second category is preparing returns, and it addresses all the activities related to the pre-departure preparation of return cases. The third category is *doing the actual return work* and highlights the actions of different actors on the day migrants are returned. The final category is *post-return doings*, and here we focus on the presence and absence of post-return care and reintegration, among others.

5.1 Doings across different RMIs

In this section, we discuss the aforementioned four phases of doings: detection, pre-departure, doing/implementing the return and post-return. However, we deliberately do not work with clear-cut boundaries that would restrict us from finding continuities, so as to do justice to the complexities involved, the grey zones that emerge, and the transnational character of these daily practices.

5.1.1. Detecting returnees and differentiating returns

Return migration governance starts with the *identification* of a to-be-returned migrant. The way that the respective authorities *obtain knowledge* about the foreigner’s lost title of stay and thus identify a to-be-returned migrant is of crucial importance in defining the next steps included. Moreover, it may vary from the detection of an irregularised border crossing in the case of pushbacks to the complex paperwork that is involved in confirming the identity of a person in cases of assisted or coerced returns for those irregularised in reception centres or detention centres. Thus, the identification of a to-be-returned migrant may take place through diverse procedures, in different geographical areas of a country, and also at different times, *revealing a multiplicity of temporalities and spatialities* even in this early stage of returns’ implementation.

The question of identification emerges as a real challenge for operational workers. This was clearly illustrated by one DTenV case worker involved in forced removals in the Netherlands, who responded to the question, ‘*who do you need to put your work in practice*’ as follows: ‘I need an “alien”. Now you can start laughing, but I do need an alien... I do not only need an alien, I also need confirmation regarding the question of who the alien actually is’ (Schapendonk et al. 2025). With this response, the man shared two important realities related

to his daily work of forcibly removing someone. The first is that many of the to-be-returned migrants actually disappear from the radar of the authorities before they can deport them; the second is that accurate documentation about the migrant's identity is often lacking. In other words, they can only materialise returns if the identity, including the nationality, of the person is confirmed by the authorities of the country of return, which is a similar challenge for the migration authorities in Sweden and Germany, among others.

However, the process of defining a to-be-returned migrant also entails various legal procedures and phases, throughout which the to-be-returned migrant has the right to stay legally in the country. Although the right to appeal is secured, some countries (such as Sweden) employ persuasive techniques to encourage the rejected applicant to accept the decision.

In the following, we outline the various ways in which migrants become identified as to-be-returned subjects. *First of all*, some migrants express a wish to return, to particular state authorities, to the IOM or specialized NGOs working in the field of assisted voluntary return. They are often informed about return assistance by the outreach activities of the different organisations involved. In the Greek case of AVRRE, the IOM has an 'outreach department' that implements regular visits and information campaigns at different places of migrants' accommodation and concentration, including asylum/reception camps and detention centres. Interested migrants contact IOM to arrange an appointment for registering in AVRRE. In the Netherlands, the same global actor is present at asylum and detention locations, trying to mobilise migrants regarding assisted returns. The smaller NGOs are very active with information campaigns as well. Registering for AVRRE may happen while migrants still have the right to remain in the particular country, i.e. as asylum seekers, or even as migrants with regular status. Migrants with regular status are also included in this category. In the case of Turkey, the individuals interested in voluntarily returning may include persons under international or temporary protection; they also must apply to the PDMM office in their city of registration. Next to these assisted voluntary returns, some migrants plan to leave on their own, falling under the type of voluntary return (non-assisted), i.e., returning on their own means during the period specified in the return order.

Second, both in cases of assisted and forced removal, a return process commonly starts with a return decision that follows, most often, after a rejected asylum application. The administrative doings of each case study differ substantially. In the Swedish, Dutch, and German cases, the return process usually emerges as a step directly related with the rejection of an application. The type of return is determined through the process of counselling by case offices who assess the migrants' degree of *collaboration* and decide on their trajectories. In the case of Greece, rejection usually is followed by migrants' obligation to leave the country 'voluntarily' within one month. Simultaneously, he/she has to leave the reception/accommodation centres (one month after the rejection decision) and subsequently move 'freely' anywhere in the country subject to regular police controls and detention. In this case, the implementation of return gets disconnected from asylum examination, and it is reactivated either in case of arrest and detention, or in case a migrant addresses him/her self to AVRRE to leave the country. In Turkey, it is possible to deport international protection applicants to a safe third country or first country of asylum if their applications are deemed inadmissible, while if removal is not possible, the international protection process continues. In the case of the EU-Turkey Statement which is seen as an informal readmission tool, facilitating forced returns of migrants and asylum seekers from Greece to Turkey, is directly connected to Syrians, via the 'one-to-one' formula.

Particularly, in the Netherlands and in Sweden, right after the rejection decisions, targeted return conversations are held with migrants by state authorities. In Sweden, for example, there

exist three phases of counselling meetings implemented by case officers of the SMA in which officers provide information about which options are available. If a voluntary return is not achievable, especially when individuals do not comply with return orders or remain absent, the SMA generally refers cases to law enforcement, and the individual may face detention. In the Netherlands, even though it is not a set guideline, case workers of the DTenV also usually work with a minimum of three return conversations with the aim to let the to-be-returned migrant navigate two options: to either cooperate and return ‘voluntarily’ or face detention and forced deportation. The returnees’ ‘cooperative attitude’ ‘that does not prevent a return’ is assessed as a crucial determinant of the next return steps to be followed (see also Section 5.2.5).

Textbox 1: Temporalities and overlaps with the asylum phase

Although the focus here is on situations that follow after a return decision, the timelines may be very fuzzy, as the preparation work on returns often starts early, even before the issuance of a return decision. In many cases, return-related doings begin directly at the asylum application stage, as the latter involves systematically categorizing applicants to identify so-called potential returnees from the outset. Through such practices of bureaucratic categorisation, involved actors operationalise deportation and *effectively pre-construct deportability*, transforming asylum seekers into legible and accessible subjects for the facilitation of future enforcement actions.

What emerges is a significant interplay of return and asylum infrastructures even before the rejection decisions or the return order, evident also due to the places where the particular doings unfold, as discussed in the Section ‘Materials and Technologies’. For example, in the Netherlands, COA case managers (Centraal Orgaan Opvang Asielzoekers - responsible for the accommodation of asylum seekers) implement conversations on returns with asylum seekers, even those staying at asylum accommodation, with a ‘what if they reject you’ scenario. Likewise, in Sweden, information on returns is provided even at the time of registering asylum applications. In Germany, information about assisted return is provided before and during the asylum application process and assisted return is offered independently of an ending or unlikely right to remain. Important criteria for having these conversations may be a) a wish to return expressed by the migrant or b) an income below the seizure limit. In Greece this is the case of AVRR programme for the implementation of which IOM gives particular importance in the information outreach stage and implements information campaigns at different places of migrants’ concentration including reception centres/camps in mainland Greece, where accommodation is provided to registered asylum seekers, or even Hotspots at the border islands, where asylum seekers register their claims and wait for asylum decisions.

It should be also mentioned that in Greece, and in particular in the case of border islands it has been observed that expulsion decisions are issued pre-emptively against migrants entering Greece, even before their identification, even if they subsequently apply for international protection and obtain a permit to stay in the country. Seemingly, in Turkey, for individuals violating or attempting to violate entry requirements, deportation decisions are typically issued; this applies even when the violation occurs at border points lacking official gates.

The temporal fuzziness becomes also very clear in cases where migrants have stayed for years underground, living lives without residence rights, or may have been irregularised even if they have had some form of documentation in the past, something common in the case of Greece.

A *third* way to be identified as a to-be-returned migrant is when migrants are apprehended or handed over by law enforcement such as police officers. In some settings, this happens through active search operations in public spaces especially in urban centres. In Greece, such police controls are regular and often take the form of ‘sweep operations’ and raids. In Poland, controls can be carried out in markets, immigration offices, and centres for asylum seekers. As one of the interviewed lawyers said: ‘there are places where the Border Guard deliberately goes for inspections in order to collect the greatest possible “harvest” [sic]. And it is organised like a round-up instead of some planned rational action’ (Krępa et al. 2025, p.21). In both Poland and Greece, identifying a person without the right to stay via such controls may lead to arrest and immediate detention after which the procedures related to forced removal usually follow. While in detention, there is the possibility that the detainees declare their will to register in AVRR and return voluntarily to their country; something plausible in Greece and the Netherlands, where AVRR information outreach and registration is also implemented in detention centres. Hence, detention, usually prolonged in the case of Greece, does not necessarily lead to deportation (also because authorities have to release detained migrants after a successful appeal). Similarly, in Poland, if the foreigner declares an interest in voluntary return, the Commander-in-Chief of the Border Guard organises assistance, upon the foreigner’s application, which, in practice, is submitted directly to the IOM.

Fourth, migrants may be detected during, or just after, the act of border crossing. It is characteristic that a lot of forced removals happen at international airports after a shorter or longer period of detention (border procedure at Schiphol, for example). In Turkey, deportation decisions are issued for individuals irregularly entering the country. In Greece, in the case of border islands, expulsion decisions are issued pre-emptively even before migrants’ subsequent application for international protection. Moreover, in different places, there are specialized infrastructures that aim at detecting those who arrive and at categorizing them through a process of identification and screening, particularly evident in the operation of the Hotspots in Greece which at the same time constitute part of the asylum system.

Related to this fourth way of detection, the pushbacks and pushforwards are the most characteristic practices of en mass tracing of to-be-deported migrants. Regarding pushbacks, in the case of Poland in 2021, they were increasingly noted at the Belarus-Polish borders targeting people from countries such as Iraq and Syria for whom Belarus had started to issue visas. In Greece, pushbacks, which have been a well-known practice for over three decades, are mainly directed towards Turkey occurring at the East Aegean borders and at the Evros land/river border. Pushbacks from Greece commonly take the form of apprehension of border-crossers from reaching Greek territory. On the other side of the border, in Turkey, pushforwards from Turkey to Greece and Bulgaria is the other side of the coin. The concept of pushforward, referring to the strategic facilitation of migrant movement toward Greece and Bulgaria, is implemented through a combination of selective non-enforcement, indirect incentives, and logistical facilitation to encourage migrants to cross into the EU. In the case of pushforward from Turkey, the initial detecting processes include the intercepting migrants at the border, particular administrative processes, and their transfer either to removal/detention centres or funnelled toward the border.

5.1.2 Pre-departure preparations

After the detection of return cases, further preparations start. In terms of doings, we distinguish identification and logistical preparations in the phase prior to departure. Moreover, detention emerges as a crucial aspect of all RMIs and can be the case either before or after identifying a to-be-returned migrant.

Identification

When a to-be-returned migrant is detected –in the sense that the return case is known to the authorities or return organisation– the identity of the migrant is not necessarily identified yet. Identification is a crucial condition of all types of return, except for the illegal pushbacks and pushforwards, and requires a wide variety of preparatory steps.

For the case of forced removal, for example, there is a lot of identity-related research prior to the often necessary ‘diplomatic confirmations’. Many case workers actively start their own investigations to identify a particular person. Finding proof in the asylum dossiers, looking for copies of passports, IDs, police files, fact checks, all assist in convincing consular representative that a particular person should be readmitted by them. For deportees in Germany, BAMF may employ so-called open-source intelligence and investigate the social media sites and accounts the person might have (used), invite the person for a talk, and possibly confiscate and search their mobile phone. In the Netherlands, similar data collection techniques are used at the beginning of asylum cases, and this information may later be used by return case workers. In Sweden, a range of ID validation methods exist, including among others, the informal use of social media, contacting the person’s relatives or friends to validate country of origin, following the money transfers with the help of Swedish tax office, inviting embassy personnel, even delegations from certain countries to attend interviews with whose ID documents are missing. In the case of forced removals in Poland, identification may be determined by a mechanism of interviews conducted in Poland by officials of a potential country of origin with a person who does not have documents, which results in issuing a travel document if a person is identified as a citizen of this country.

After identification, migrants’ freedom of movement can be restricted through their assignment to specific places by the authorities. This is the case of the so-called ‘geographical restriction’ in the Aegean islands, where persons subject to the EU-Turkey Statement are officially required to stay. Albeit different from detention, this restriction can be said to transform whole areas into spaces of limited freedom of movement for the purpose of a potential (actually never implemented since the suspension of the Statement) return. The natural isolation of the islands is used as a physical asset to enhance prospects for return for the individuals affected.

For the case of assisted voluntary returns, after enrolment in assisted return programmes, migrants are then assisted in their preparations related to identification and documentation. In case of AVRR, IOM takes a prominent role in the diplomatic paperwork. This does not only mean arranging travel papers. In Greece, if an irregular migrant has not received a return decision, IOM provides him/her with a referral document and makes an appointment at the Aliens Directorate/Immigration Service (of the Hellenic Police) in Athens for fingerprinting and issuing an ‘exit permit’ interoffice memo, namely a return decision to be executed within approximately one month, necessary for the departure at the airport.

It is crucial to mention that legal procedures needed for returns’ preparation also include resigning from a regular legal status for those interested in returning voluntarily to their home

countries. In the case of AVRR in Greece, the enrolment in AVRR presupposes that the applicants withdraw their asylum applications, and refrain from any rights coming with a real or potential regular status – either of an international protection beneficiary or a migrant with a valid stay permit or even the temporary ‘regularity’ of an asylum seeker. In the case of the National Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (N-AVRR) Programme in Turkey, the voluntary return mechanism facilitates the return of individuals under international or temporary protection to their country of origin. Upon exiting Turkey, the returnees’ Temporary Protection Identity Cards are collected and destroyed, and a relevant restriction code is registered within Turkey’s electronic GöçNet system to officially document the termination of protection. Next to these assisted voluntary returns, some migrants plan to leave on their own. In Sweden, these migrants are asked to visit the nearest SMA reception unit to get an ‘exit certificate’ which needs to be handed in at a Swedish passport control when they leave the country.

The sharing of information between different migration-related authorities appears to be crucial, and thus, officers of different actors share the same spaces in many occasions (see the Section Materials). Despite the information collected, representatives of the countries of return need to confirm that the prospective returnee is their citizen. For this reason, ‘migrant presentations’ to state representatives are frequently organized. Case workers in Sweden, Germany, and the Netherlands, for instance, often send migrants to embassies, and at times, consular representatives are invited to locations like a detention centre to confirm the nationality of particular people. Yet, in some cases, these presentations may be contested by migrants as they refuse to enter a vehicle that brings them to the embassy or consulate. This resistance may go quite far, as in the Dutch case, migrants may hide in their bed sheets as they know that the staff working in detention centres are legally not allowed to intervene in these cases. In Germany, however, so-called embassy hearings can be enforced by means of an ‘administrative act’ and the costs of this hearing are to be paid by the designated returnee. If there is still no confirmation about the identity of a person, this process of face-to-face presentations is likely to repeat itself with another country of return (and embassy staff might actually hint at the origin country of the presented migrant). This underlines that implementing a return process require the collaboration of the authorities of return countries, revealing the transnational character of return infrastructures.

As regards travel documents, especially in the case of AVRR, when there is no valid passport, the embassies issue the so-called ‘laissez-passer’, a temporary travel document which is valid for 30 days and for the particular route to the country of return. No interest or ‘unwillingness’ in collaboration in verifying the identity of their citizens by the respective countries, or to accept them by issuing travel documents, may result in very long and ineffective procedures. Such processes are affected by diplomatic relations between countries and may cause frustration in the everyday work of return actors in different settings. At the same time, it should be acknowledged that this reading of unwillingness and non-collaboration originates from a strong Eurocentric position. Interestingly, however, when we take the viewpoints of the countries of return, we see a more complex picture. This is, for instance, illustrated by the Nigerian case study outlining the complexity of obtaining travel documents from a de-centred perspective:

‘The process for obtaining a travel certificate or an Instrument of Safe Passage for undocumented migrants preparing to return is notably complex and fraught with difficulties. One of the main barriers is the inadequacy of civil registration in Nigeria [...] Many individuals lack essential identification documents, such as a

National Identification Number or a Bank Verification Number, which complicates the issuance of identity cards necessary for their return in Nigeria missions abroad. Moreover, many Nigerian migrants are apprehensive about approaching Nigeria embassies abroad because rather than supporting them, embassy staff collaborate with host country officials to facilitate their deportation' (Uzomah and Madu 2025, p.23).

Countries of return insist on the tangible and formal identification and documentation in order to prevent wrongful deportations. In this line, it is telling that for the Moroccan case, collaborations between the Moroccan administration and particular European countries vary considerably. For example, Denmark (50%) and Croatia (42%) have rather high rates of return enforcement of Moroccan nationals, while Belgium and Austria have very low rates, with 1.2 % and 1.1%, respectively (Lahlou and Belhaj 2025). For us, these discrepancies can only be explained by taking into account the notion of migration diplomacy that is scrutinized in WP5 of the GAPs project. The doings of return migration governance – and the efficacy of these doings – rely to a large extent on particular 'political momenta'. To tackle this, the EU and its member states increasingly use the so-called return liaison officers who can be best described as mid-level officials stationed in the countries of return to enhance law enforcement efforts by leveraging local expertise and networks to verify the identities of irregular migrants and assisting in Joint Return Operations coordinated by Frontex.

Textbox 2: NGOs, travel papers, and flights

In cases of assisted returns in the Dutch setting, NGOs generally arrange the travel documents and the ticket through the IOM. As an international institution, they are considered to have more diplomatic power. It might happen that IOM is unsuccessful in obtaining the right paperwork to obtain a travel document. Then NGOs might turn to the DTenV, but administratively this makes a great difference as then an 'assisted return' turns (in the administrative sense) into a forced removal. It also happens that NGOs themselves do some of the necessary paperwork. One NGO return assistance representative stated:

'My colleague is much more effective than IOM or DTenV when it concerns obtaining the right documents. For instance, in case a small paper needs to be added from a school or church in a little village somewhere, she really makes this happen' (Schapendonk et al. 2025, p.66).

We spoke to one NGO that had a proximate relation with several embassies directly, and could easily arrange the paperwork without the involvement of IOM or DTenV.

'Definitely, definitely yes. I know a person at the embassy. And this person likes to have particular source documents, like birth certificates. If we have it, it will at least be arranged, that information goes to the embassy. One of my colleagues can arrange this and the Laissez-Passer is taken care of. At least that is the strength of my colleagues, it certainly is'.

This indicates that the paperwork does not always involve the powerful states and supra-states institutions.

Detention & ‘alternative’ accommodation practices before return

All the aforementioned procedures for detecting and differentiating a to-be-returned migrant are interrelated with detention. Yet, detention practices are different in the Netherlands, Sweden, and Germany compared to the cases of Poland and Greece. In the former, detention is usually a potential consequence after the final return decision and the counselling sessions during which the migrant did not ‘collaborate’ with migration authorities for ‘assisted’ return. Thus, detention is employed as the other edge of the dipole ‘cooperation and voluntariness versus coercion and detention’ and is mainly used for reasons of implementing forced removal or to incentivise further ‘assisted’ return decisions (see below). In Greece and Poland, detention may be the first step for those found undocumented and without the right to stay anywhere in the country, even those without a decision for return. Particularly in Poland, the Border Guard may immediately, after capturing a person, apply to the court to impose detention. In the Dutch case, this is only possible at Schiphol Airport. Seemingly, in Turkey, foreigners violating or attempting to violate entry laws are likely to face administrative detention and expedited processing. Detention, thus, may be the case either before or after identifying a to-be-returned migrant.

More particularly, in Poland, long-term detention seems to be used as a tool to force acceptance of return with insufficient identification of vulnerable groups in detention (faulty identification of unaccompanied minors). In Greece, apart from the reasons for detention prescribed in the Return Directive, detention decisions are very often based on public security and public order reasons, pertaining to sentences for the possession of forged documents or non-possession of documents (Greek Ombudsman, 2019). As a result, third-country nationals often end up in detention for the sole reason of entering the country, and various forms of deprivation of liberty may occur even before a return/expulsion decision. In Greece, prolonged detention is also observed after a return decision has been issued, for periods that reportedly exceed 12 months or even when their deportation is not feasible. It is worth mentioning that both in Greece and in Poland, returnees are kept together with asylum seekers in detention centres.

In Sweden, during the counselling meetings, the rejected asylum seekers may be offered a place at a return (detention) centre where they will stay until departure. According to the law, the rejected asylum seekers can choose to live in a return centre or their own accommodation until they leave Sweden. A detention decision is made if the case officers determine that the existing supervision measures are insufficient. The latter is also the case in Germany. Detention is seen as a legally justifiable solution in case it is plausible that the person in question would otherwise disappear from the authorities’ radar.

In the Netherlands, the potentiality of abscondence also informs detention decisions. A potential returnee may be transported to a detention centre from regular asylum accommodations after his/her rejection of the asylum application if he/she is deportable and show no collaboration with assisted returns. In these cases, DTenV regievoorders request detention, which is legally formalized by the DTenV Uitvoerend Ambtenaar (executive legal servant) or a representative of the Aliens Police (AVIM). On the day of detention, DV&O and/or the police hold an order of entry, enter the migrant’s room at an unexpected moment, and the migrant is transported to the Rotterdam detention centre. This secrecy is also an important element of forced return in other countries. For example, in Germany, planned removal measures are deliberately not shared with social workers working in particular accommodations. A remarkable difference is that in the Netherlands, pickups for detention are organized in the early mornings to surprise the migrant in question, in Sweden this is a Police

procedure, thus pickup and transport times are regulated, and in Germany, particular subdistrict authorities have restricted timings for similar pick-ups of families.

Apart from detention, other types of accommodation before return exist for returnees. In Germany, the ABH works with so-called desk removals as a variation of detention, meaning that migrants are summoned to the social welfare office in order to increase the likelihood that they will sleep in the accommodation during the days of return. In the Netherlands, there exist the freedom-restricted centre for cases of potential assisted returns as well as the so-called family centres, relatively open locations with the obligation to report. Next to this, the Dutch government had run the LVV-programme 5-year pilot programme that aimed to coordinate on a national level the accommodation facilities for undocumented migrants without the right to stay in five cities in the Netherlands. Even if this is certainly not a detention facility, it built-in a strong conditionality to shelter programmes, as migrants who enter the shelter spaces first need to agree to ‘work on their return cases’. Where the LVV is an important setting for the Netherlands, church asylum is more common in Germany and generally disrupts processes of forced removal that are initiated by the authorities. Interestingly, Swedish return infrastructures also include methods of obligatory supervision for individuals staying in their own accommodation to ensure that they remain accessible to authorities; they are obliged to visit either the police or the SMA at specified locations at designated times to report their presence.

In Greece, the case of the OCAVRR in central Athens is considered by IOM an ‘alternative measure to detention’ (IOM 2023, p.32). It offers accommodation to the most vulnerable AVRR participants and is currently the best-organized, accommodation facility in Greece (see section 6.1.4).

The interrelations between AVRR and detention are another aspect of the continuity of coercion in returns. In the case of the Netherlands, assisted voluntary return options are offered within the detention centres and regarded as the preferred option in detention settings. In other words, in a context of detention migrants opt for the ‘assisted return’ option, and this usually runs via the IOM, as one interview indicated: ‘The standardized practice then is that IOM arranges the return and books a flight for the to-be-returned migrant, but as a ‘back-up’ the DTenV books a second flight a few days after the ‘assisted return flight’ arranged by the IOM (Schapendonk et al. 2025, p.39). So in these particular cases, migrants may board a plane with IOM, which would be considered an ‘assisted return’. If s/he is in the end not boarding that flight, s/he will still be removed with the flight that was initially booked by the DTenV.

Similarly, AVRR in Greece, run by IOM, is also implemented in detention, meaning that the different steps of the procedure are implemented for detainees, and IOM employees are instructed to continue the process uniformly, as for those out of detention. Implementing AVRR for detainees directly challenges its voluntary character. Moreover, registration and participation in AVRR do not preclude the possibility of arrest and detention of migrants, even though they may possess documents that prove their participation. Thus, as part of the different procedural steps, detention, the threat of detention remain fundamental components of AVRR in Greece. In a similar way, in Poland, IOM cultural assistants are present in the detention centre, responsible for explaining the legal status of detainees and promoting voluntary returns. As Khosravi (2009) notes, the introduction of better cultural sensitivities in the return infrastructures might enhance its efficiency.

Logistical preparations

The logistical preparations include a multifold of activities. In AVRR programmes, they may include social as well as medical support by organisations in the host countries, protection assessments, professional training, financial support through reintegration budgets, and forms of counselling when people still have their uncertainties. Several consultation sessions are used to evaluate the health situation, exploring people's family situation and potential risks upon return. In case of the latter, it regularly happens that organisations in the country of origin are contacted to 'convince' or 'ease' migrants about the possible scenarios upon return. This happens usually through phone calls or online meetings. Occasionally, however, there are site visits organized. In April 2025, for example, a range of local partners (from Morocco, Iraq, Nigeria) of the ERSO network travelled to the Netherlands, visited crucial sites (e.g., asylum locations), and engaged in outreach and counselling work. As the Nigerian report notes: 'local NGOs partnering with both the IEOs, and refugee networks abroad (like those from European Refugee Support Organisation network) travel to preach the benefit of AVR to migrants with failed asylum claims' (Uzomah and Madu 2025, p.13). In a similar vein, Mielke et al. note that 'a country delegation from Guinea had been invited to Germany in September 2024 for two weeks to aid ZAB Essen for seven days to identify suspected nationals from Guinea and issue PEP. The delegation also stayed for the same purpose, one day in Bremen' (Mielke et al. 2025, p.43).

In terms of forced removals, the organisation of pick-ups, escorts, and transfers are important elements. This organisation is based on risk assessments and the sharing of security-related information (e.g., police reports, suicide risks, perspectives on potential resistance) between different actors. Whereas in the Netherlands and Sweden it mainly considers deportations organized by state authorities, Germany is 'the most active user of both Frontex charter and scheduled flights mechanisms' (Mielke et al. 2025, p.46). Nevertheless, the transport to the airport is coordinated with the Federal Police.

In these preparations of both assisted and forced returns, *vulnerability and health* are important parameters that often impact the temporalities of the procedure. In the case of Greece, vulnerability has been an emergent factor in asylum governance since 2015-2016. Consequently, it is also a criterion relevant in different steps of AVRR. Official data for Greece reveal that AVRR gives 'special care and priority' to 'beneficiaries in a situation of vulnerability': the latter counted for 8% of total beneficiaries of the 2016-23 programme (nearly 70% on medical grounds), but increased to over 18% among returnees during 2019-23. Also, vulnerability is a criterion for accommodating AVRR participants in OCAVRR, from the time of their registration in AVRR until their return flight. This also aligns with the wide range of vulnerability criteria that are in place for asylum seekers' placement in particular types of reception facilities (Papatzani et al. 2022). Health can be a serious concern in cases of both assisted returns and forced removals, as many migrants in precarious situations face health challenges. In the Netherlands, there is a special department, 'Extraordinary Departures', dealing with forced removals with strong medical indications. A large part of their preparations is to examine the accessibility of health care in the countries of origin.

An important part of the return procedures, related to the above medical/health aspects, is the '*fit-to-travel*', or 'fit-to-fly' confirmation, which ensures that even in cases of medical issues, the persons concerned can safely fly to their country. No ticket is booked before the medical condition has been improved, in case the medical condition of the returnee is not improved to align with the 'fit-to-travel' rules. For Germany and the Netherlands, fit-to-fly assessments in the framework of deportations are conducted by commercialized health actors hired by the authorities. Health can be an important reason that would hamper return processes in these cases, too. In the Netherlands, there is the so-called Artikel 64 application

which basically means a legal application to postpone a departure based on health risks. These applications can be submitted a few days before departure, which is known as the ‘Vliegtuigtrapaanraag’ [applications from the stairs of an airplane]. In Sweden, Germany, and the Netherlands, state authorities can arrange a wide range of medical support, and as such, health-related risks are often no longer an obstacle for forced removal.

This rather stretched notion of ‘fit-to-travel’ also raises deep concerns in countries of return regarding the way vulnerable migrants are treated during deportation. In Nigeria, there was a press conference of Civil Society Organisations devoted to ‘sound alarm’ about the deepening crisis of human rights violations for Nigerian deportees. This was particularly illustrated by the case of Bright Obasuyi, a deportee who faced severe state violence in Germany while suffering from mental health diseases that were well documented and known by the authorities. ‘The CSOs condemned the alarming lack of effective consular intervention from Nigerian officials. Obasuyi’s own testimony revealed that Nigerian representatives prioritised the verification of his citizenship for deportation, effectively acting as facilitators rather than protectors of his rights’ (Uzomah and Madu 2025, p.25)

Logistics are an inherent part of pushbacks, too. In Poland, pushbacks were increasingly noted at the Belarus-Polish border targeting people from countries such as Iraq and Syria for whom Belarus had started to issue visas. International protection requests from these nationalities were not always accepted by the Polish border guards, and they often pushed them back to the Belarusian side multiple times. In Greece, an ‘informal’ logistics facilitates the actual pushbacks through the organization of a network of reconnaissance operations and temporary capture in buildings at the border, which is often accompanied by inhuman, violent and torturous treatment (see for example GNCHR 2024).

In the case of pushforwards from Turkey to Greece, logistical facilitation is employed by Turkish authorities –in particular during the Pazarkule events in 2020– to encourage migrants to cross into the EU. This may include coordinated transportation, relaxation of security patrols, and a strategic easing of border restrictions, and cooperation with local actors, including smugglers and transportation networks. The systematic character of the pushforwards and the logistics required permit to argue that, albeit informal, such practices have been transformed into organised ones (Gökalp Aras et al. 2025).

Textbox 3: Smuggling as a community-based and history/geography rooted doing at the local level

In Turkey, in the border villages of Edirne, human smuggling has long been embedded within local economies and social structures, with longstanding community involvement in irregular border crossings. Unlike large-scale transnational smuggling networks, which operate through complex logistical chains spanning multiple countries, local facilitators in rural areas play a more direct and intimate role in guiding migrants across the border. In this way, they can be regarded as an important actor contesting return migration governance infrastructures as they make the work of assisted and coerced returns undone in many cases. In other words, states aspire to create definite return practices, while these networks create more cyclical pathways as part of turbulent migratory trajectories.

With their intimate knowledge of the terrain, security patrol patterns, and informal crossing routes, these local actors often function as small-scale service providers, arranging safe passage, temporary shelter, and transportation for migrants attempting to cross into Greece or Bulgaria. While the identities of those involved are often well-known within the villages,

enforcement actions against them remain limited and sporadic, reflecting a degree of local normalisation and tacit tolerance of these activities.

The economic dimension of smuggling in these villages cannot be overlooked. Many rural communities near the border experience limited economic opportunities, making migrant facilitation a lucrative alternative source of income. Participation in smuggling varies widely, ranging from individual guides who personally lead groups across the border to larger informal networks that coordinate with urban-based smugglers in Istanbul or Edirne. These localized actors sometimes operate independently, while in other cases, they are integrated into broader smuggling infrastructures, working under mediators who distribute payments and organise logistics.

Furthermore, the social fabric of these villages allows for collective involvement in human smuggling. In some cases, entire families or community groups participate, with different members specializing in various roles, such as providing food and shelter, monitoring security forces, or serving as lookouts during border crossings. This distributed nature of participation makes smuggling less visible and more resilient to law enforcement crackdowns, ensuring its continuity despite state efforts to curb irregular migration.

Ultimately, the role of local villagers in human smuggling in Edirne's borderlands highlights the blurring of formal and informal migration infrastructures. These actors function not only as facilitators of movement but also as key intermediaries between migrants, transnational smuggling networks, and state migration enforcement mechanisms. Their long-standing presence in the region underscores the deeply rooted, community-based nature of border economies, where migration control policies, economic survival strategies, and historical patterns of cross-border movement intersect (Gökalp Aras et al. 2025).

5.1.3 Doing the actual returns

The actual days of return illustrate the full continuum of coercion. Some migrants return in a cooperative and frictionless way, for others, the return day is a dystopian moment whereby the (supra-)state reveals its full power.

In cases of *assisted returns*, migrants may either go independently to the airports or be brought to the airport by the IOM or, in case they are involved, smaller NGOs offering return counselling. In the case of AVR in Greece, migrants in detention are driven to the airport by the police with whom IOM collaborates for the implementation of return. IOM representatives have requested that those transferred from detention centres should not wear handcuffs, and this has been respected by the officers in Greece. At the airport, the IOM is usually in charge of the last steps of this return process. In some cases, the returnees have to indicate who would pick him/her up from the airport after landing and the IOM office in returning countries contacts the receiving persons.

At European airports, IOM officers explain the border procedures and make sure that the Customs and Border control sign the departure declaration. Returnees must carry their AVR card (see section 6.2), their passports, the 'exit permit' interoffice memo (return decision), and the bag with IOM insignia. A considerable number of migrants receive an entry ban, and this is handled by the immigration authorities at the airport. During the cross-check/identification check and the stamping of passports/documents, there are cases of people for whom the system alerts about a possible warrant or other measure pending against them in their country, in which case their departure is cancelled. In rather rare cases, migrants decide not to board the plane in the end due to mental pressures. In this case, for some of them the process of

forced removal will commence resulting in their return to the airport. Usually, the financial assistance is handed over to the returnee immediately after the documents' check or at the airport gate from the IOM accounting team in the presence of an airport security police officer.

Apart from airplane departures, there also exist the land returns. In Turkey, individuals under international or temporary protection who want to voluntarily return, after obtaining particular documents, may freely travel to the appropriate border crossing points.

Forced removals often start from a pre-removal detention setting. The continuum of coercion materializes in very different doings, also in forced removals. To discuss two extremes, in case there is little resistance or complications to be expected, the caseworker guides the to-be-deported migrant to the exit of the detention centre and arranges a transfer by the police or specialized state-related transport services. In some cases, particularly in the case of the Netherlands, a return case might be rather last-minute and be 're-labelled' as a voluntary return, which creates some hurry in terms of arranging a flight by the IOM instead of state authorities. At the other extreme of this continuum, migrants can be considered 'dangerous', 'resistant', expected to panic, and/or harm themselves. This creates all kinds of 'bookings' as escorts and specialized transport to the airport need to be arranged. To indicate the volume of these escorts, it is reported that in 2023, 1000 of 6500 forced removals in the Netherlands were guided by Kmar. In roughly 100 of these cases, a body cuff was used to forcibly take the migrant on the plane. In similar cases in Germany, federal special police forces (Sondereinsatzkommando [SEK]) become involved in the 'pick-up' of returnees. In 2024, 13,243 Federal Police officers and 570 state police or state authority representatives escorted 7,607 forced returnees (Deutscher Bundestag 2025, p.16). Next to this, Airline security staff can play an important role in securitizing the forced removal. For 2024, there are 468 registered cases in which airline security staff accompanied a return flight in the case of Germany (Deutscher Bundestag 2025). Usually, forced removal escorts sit with the returnees in the back rows of the aircraft; a blanket might cover possible insignia so that other passengers do not notice it (Rose and Schießl 2024, p.99). In Sweden, the Swedish Border Police is responsible for enforcing deportations. To prepare for a coerced return in Sweden, the Border Police coordinate travel logistics through the Prison and Probation Service. The two institutions maintain a continuous dialogue with detainees to encourage compliance with return orders, making individual assessments for each case.

It should also be mentioned that in some cases, detainees are not informed well in advance about their return. As it has also been noted in Greece, the police frequently transfer detainees to the Airport Police Station as 'alternates'. This means that in case some of the returnees assigned to a specific return operation are exempted from the procedure (for example, due to unexpected health conditions or due to last-minute legal issues), then those 'alternates' replace them. There are also certain steps in the procedure that are characterized by a lack of transparency. The German report, for instance, indicates that conflicts are likely to arise when migrants lack knowledge of the procedures (e.g., concerning a security deposit or the actual destination of the airplane).

In the case of Germany, returnees in need of medical assistance ought to be handed over to qualified personnel, and unaccompanied minors to family members or entrusted legal guardians upon arrival. The available grey literature on these topics documents numerous cases where, in particular, the aspect of medical care was not met as foreseen. The final decision on who can board an aircraft lies with the airline, and passengers can be rejected by the airline personnel regardless of all preparations (e.g. 'fit to fly'), for example, based on health or security risks. For this reason, medically trained personnel appointed or subcontracted by the airlines assess forms and reports on the health of a returnee in parallel with the REAG/GARP

application process, when this is relevant, to determine if and under what conditions the person can be taken on board. The permission to fly can be revoked by the pilot even after boarding.

Regarding *pushbacks*, they include a range of practices and doings depending on their geography, among others. In Greece, sea pushbacks may take different forms and target incoming boats, pushing them further from Greek waters or by not rescuing them. They may also take place after migrants have disembarked and are on their way to a village or to filing an asylum claim; in such cases, people are initially detected, arrested, detained at an undefined facility, and then transferred to the shores, and pushed to the open sea. Land pushbacks, mainly at the Evros river border, but also from the mainland, may take place either upon arrival on Greek territory or from further inland (even from villages in the area). Practices of detention are also included, as well as apprehensions and abductions of migrants (by force or by false promises) who are en route, in villages, or even from official detention centres (Greek Ombudsman, 2023; GNCHR, 2024). Migrants are then driven to an unidentified facility, detained, and then driven back to the Evros river where they are forced to cross it. Land pushbacks from the mainland may also concern people who were intending to file an asylum claim, but also people with international protection or other legal documentation (Karamanidou and Kasperek 2020). In the case of pushbacks in Poland, it is reported that the most difficult time is winter and then, NGOs providing humanitarian assistance face the need to help with hypothermia but also such unusual injuries as trench foot.

Concerning pushforwards, in Turkey there emerge three types of pushforward practices: i) Pushforwards followed pushbacks, that is redirecting migrants who have been pushed back from border countries such as Greece or Bulgaria to internal regions or alternative border crossing points, ii) Relocation of migrants to third countries, including also the redirection of individuals who are already present irregularly in Turkey and do not belong to the above category, iii) Forced pushforward including indirect pressure that compels migrants to enter a third country, including denying legal status, withdrawing basic services, detaining migrants in precarious conditions, or applying security and administrative pressures that render staying impossible (Gökalp Aras et al. 2025).

5.1.4 Post-return doings

An important number of doings continue after the day of return of the migrant to the respective country. Reintegration, care work, and monitoring are some of the main procedures that follow.

Reintegration is a complex process that is heavily debated and questioned in academic work. It commonly refers to the processes that unfold after the return of migrants, refugees and internally displaced persons to their country of origin or place of residence as they set about trying to re-establish their lives (Şahin-Mencütek 2023). Some states articulate the duty of the state to reintegrate returned migrants. According to Georgia's Migration Strategy, for example, 'it is the country's priority to encourage the return of Georgian citizens from abroad and facilitate their reintegration upon return' (SCMI 2020, p.36). In line with this, the State Programme for Supporting Reintegration of Returned Georgian Migrants offers medical services, social projects, vocational education, and temporary livelihood to Georgians irregularly residing abroad for more than one year and rejected or accepted asylum applicants. Despite this articulation, the actual *reintegration work* is mainly executed by international organisations, development cooperation agencies, and NGOs. To start with the latter, NGOs

operating from European countries offer training programmes and counselling that already seek to work towards ‘sustainable reintegration’ for unwelcome migrants. Many NGOs involved claim to work with tailor-made programmes for potential returnees. It is, for example, common for NGOs’ employees to work closely with beneficiaries to write or correct the business plans. In these kinds of programmes, the IOM is usually involved as a main funder of return programmes. In some settings, as was the case in the Netherlands, return and reintegration budgets could be matched by local municipalities or the state return authority (DTenV).

It is worth mentioning that reintegration spans from a pre-departure phase to a long time after return, and as one Georgian NGO worker said, ‘reintegration starts before they [migrants] even are deported. That the first, you know, information about the opportunities in Georgia is given back’ (Krepa et al. 2025, p.30). This is also visible in other cases, as actors in the country of return often seek to intervene very early in return counselling procedures in Europe (for instance, in the Nigerian, Tunisian, Iraqi, and Moroccan cases).

‘Assistance in the reintegration of returning Moroccans is a process that begins, for IOM, before return through coordination with host country missions, through the organisation of virtual sessions with potential returnees; the exchange of information on the economic and social context in Morocco; the study of the feasibility of reintegration plans developed by the missions of the host countries; and, finally, family members research’ (Lahlou and Belhaj 2025, p.10).

Yet, despite this early presence, return and reintegration processes tend to depart from a very Eurocentric social work setting (see also Lietaert 2017).

In contrast to what the binary forced/voluntary return divide suggests, we have come across many instances in which reintegration assistance is offered to those migrants who are forcibly removed from European territory. For instance, Tunisian migrants residing in a European country that is a partner of the Tounesna project and who are required to leave the territory or are subject to forced return procedures are eligible for reintegration assistance upon their arrival in Tunisia. Moreover, in some European countries, reintegration assistance was offered to migrants in forced return procedures. In other words, deportees may also obtain reintegration assistance.

As mentioned above, the *actual reception* of returnees is an important step both in forced removals and voluntary assisted returns. For forced removals, a person concerned is only ‘returned’ when she/he is handed over to the authorities of the country of return, that is, when the returnee has left the transit zone of the airport and entered the sovereign territory of the country of destination as emerged by several interviews in the Dutch case. It is reported that some countries of return –including Iraq, Nigeria and Georgia– have built in sophisticated practices to arrange a ‘careful landing’. In Iraq, for example, reception by a committee is the first ‘doing’ upon arrival at Baghdad International Airport. The committee makes an initial assessment of the returnee’s case by checking his/her identity, passport, and other travel documents, as well as whether any arrest warrants or pending legal cases exist. This assessment may include contacting the EU country authorities to confirm the details of the deportation. The information and data of the returnee are put into the database of the National Referral Mechanism (NRM), and he/she is given a mobile chip that can easily be used to contact him/her in the future, and also gives him/her their serial code in the NRM. During this assessment, the immediate needs of the returnee are determined, for example, if he/she is

suffering from a medical emergency, medical procedures will be provided by the Baghdad International Airport Medical Clinic.

Later on, particular referral procedures to the competent authorities follow, including the referral to the Ministry of Health (MOH) if the person has health issues, to the Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs (MOLSA) if the person needs social or economic support, such as providing shelter or financial assistance, and to the Ministry of Interior (MOI) if there are legal issues related to the person's status. Following this, the particular respective services and support are provided, including health support, social and economic support, as well as legal support. Later on, follow-up procedures and evaluation are implemented to monitor the socio-economic situation of the returnee and a final assessment is conducted after a certain period to ensure that the person has been successfully integrated into the community in Iraq.

In Nigeria, both deportees as well as returnees who are assisted in the return process from Europe are received at the airports by government officials and NGOs, which then conduct a profiling process. After the initial profiling, returnees are referred to the IOM for further assistance, including medical evaluations and in-kind financial support. This process aims to ensure that returnees receive necessary care and resources to facilitate their reintegration into society (Uzomah and Madu 2025, p.27). Many of the return processes are marked with stigma and shame. In those cases, returnees are often brought to a hotel, shelter, or the so-called Migration Transit Centre in Ikeja, where they are housed for a maximum of five days for the needs assessment and profiling. For Morocco, it is reported that there are no special services for voluntary returns, which are considered 'normal mobility' to Morocco. Moreover, there is no special system for reception for Moroccan returnees at the borders (ports and airports) of the country. The authorities only carry out an investigation on them if the return is motivated by an expulsion linked to a conviction or suspicion of committing a crime or offence abroad. However, NGOs do step in to assist migrants. For example, Caritas International Belgium (CIB) participates in reintegration activities in Morocco with the support of a local partner: the Orient-Occident Foundation, including offering psychosocial support to returned migrants and support in the development of reintegration plans. The assistance services mainly focus on airport pick-ups; in-country onward travel assistance; temporary accommodation (max 7 days); referrals for urgent medical care, and reintegration services. For the Tunisia case, no structure or organisation is authorized to welcome or assist returning migrants (whether forced or 'voluntary') upon their arrival at one of the Tunisian airports. Once questioned and identified by border police, they are often left to their own devices and return to their families on their own.

The topic of reintegration also raises questions regarding *monitoring*. The question is often who is responsible and entitled to monitor. For instance, the Dutch authorities claimed that post-return monitoring of a precarious health situation was considered to be a very edgy practice as it would mean the Dutch state would intervene in the sovereign space of a particular country. The German report states in similar ways that in cases of deportations, monitoring basically stops at the German airport, and the subsequent steps are not monitored, which means that there is no documentation of occurrences that could violate or have already violated the fundamental rights of forced returnees. In Poland, only particular civil society organisations are entitled to monitor return operations. Significantly, the monitoring functions performed by NGOs and the costs incurred by these monitoring institutions are not financed from the state budget. This means that monitoring has a rather limited character, mostly covering the airport phase of the return operation.

Yet, monitoring individual return processes was definitely a practice conducted by NGOs offering return and reintegration assistance. Some organisations monitored for six months up

to a year, and this monitoring was often done by local actors in the form of written reports, and occasionally, field trips were organized for NGO staff to evaluate return and reintegration processes. Understandably, NGO representatives expressed a satisfied feeling in cases of successful returns, i.e., when people manage to get back on their feet again. Occasionally, it happens that former ‘clients’ are, in the end, unhappy with the return (and the process of return itself). Very few interviewees touched upon this, one notable exception is a NGO Return Assistance representative, who stated:

‘We had a case of a family, coming here with their passports, and saying, we really want to go back. But once they arrived there, feelings of regret started to emerge. It did not go well. That is a confrontation with ourselves. Sometimes – and this is the other side of the coin, returns do not work well. You have to be aware of that, and ask yourself, how far do we go? That is a confrontation with ourself (Schapendonk et al. 2025, pp.70-71).

The ‘how far do you go’ question raised above is particularly interesting for its reflexivity. The question, of course, is to what extent this reflexivity leads to the actual changing of practices.

In post-return settings, there is another doing of NGO workers that is of crucial importance: the accountancy work. In other words, the administrative work for NGOs often begins as they need to justify their spending. Or as one interviewee in the Netherlands indicated: ‘from the moment somebody has returned, the administrative maze starts’ (Schapendonk et al. 2025, p.70). In this justification of the costs made, the local partner in the country of origin plays a crucial role. We came across instances where the local partners accompany the returnee to make sure all the receipts and proofs are in order. This is part of a European system of accountability in relation to subsidies.

It is relevant to note that, also in the context of pushbacks, monitoring and care practices are part of post-push realities. A range of services is provided to migrants being pushbacked from Greece to Turkey, or pushed forward from Turkey to Greece, on the part of NGOs. These may include legal assistance, psychological support, and humanitarian assistance, such as food, clothing, and interpretation services, while simultaneously documenting human rights violations. Moreover, in terms of resisting and reporting pushbacks from Greece, appeals to the European Court of Justice for an injunction are the main doings recently emerged on the part of NGOs and lawyers assisting victims of pushbacks, while also a range of reporting and monitoring activities, by reporters or even GIS experts for part of the post-pushbacks contestation doings.

As far as it concerns return assistance from the IOM, it is relevant to note that the IOM divides the reintegration process into three parts: development of a reintegration plan with the IOM in the country of residence (which includes counselling on the reintegration plan), implementation in collaboration with IOM of the return country, and monitoring under the responsibility of the returning country. The above illustrates aspects of transnational collaboration, at least between IOM offices in returning and return countries, while it is of particular importance that the IOM office in Greece maintains responsibility for the implementation of reintegration in the country of return. IOM offices in countries of return conduct two surveys (the Reintegration Programme Monitoring and the Reintegration Satisfaction Survey), three and six months after the implementation of the reintegration plan. IOM Greece collects the data as part of its mandate. IOM Greece also organizes several visits in countries of return, where they discuss with small samples of beneficiaries.

In Sweden, in the case of AVR, SMA offers financial and practical support. The financial support is either in terms of a ‘cash support’ given in the pre-departure phase or a ‘reestablishment grant’ given after return. The reestablishment support is given to individuals from particular countries, who voluntarily intend to return to a certain country where the conditions for re-establishment are limited due to the security situation. According to the SMA, a person who does not ‘cooperate’ with authorities upon receiving a rejection decision/expulsion order is not entitled to benefit from reestablishment support. In Morocco, financed by the EU trust fund, the IOM offers cash assistance, assists Moroccan returnees with income-generating activities, social assistance and vocational training. Next to these mainstream activities of the IOM, a variety of (European) NGOs are involved offering assistance to returnees of Moroccan nationality as well as sub-Saharan Africans who are returned to Morocco.

In Georgia, IOM has operated since 2003 a separate EU-funded programme for those who have unlawfully stayed abroad or rejected asylum applicants (SCMI 2020). The programme offers consulting, temporary accommodation provision, necessary medication purchase, training and job placement, and assistance in income-generating activities (together with funding). Moreover, Frontex supports Georgia in providing reintegration assistance in formal partnership with Caritas International Belgium, which cooperates with Caritas Georgia. Also, reintegration programmes run by actors in EU countries returning migrants to Georgia are something that returnees can benefit from simultaneously. For benefiting from such programmes, it is common for NGOs employees to work closely with beneficiaries to write or correct the business plans, which otherwise would be difficult to do effectively because of the lack of proper know-how by returnees. Also, the returnees must meet eligibility criteria, like the minimum time spent abroad; thus, the number of reintegration beneficiaries is a small proportion of the number of returnees. The multiplicity of reintegration programmes in the country, even if it provides a range of opportunities, may also raise concerns, due to the project-based and often short-term mode of work.

In the case of the AVRR programme in Greece, as a country returning migrants, the reintegration scheme is only a small portion of AVRR, functioning more as a motive for eligible migrants to participate. In the case of AVRR returnees from Greece, the reintegration scheme has an in-kind character (reaching the amount of 1.140 euros) and may include the setting up of a small business in the country of return, job placement, temporary accommodation, professional training programmes, coverage of materials goods, medical assistance and treatment. In such cases, the IOM office in Greece maintains responsibility for the implementation of the reintegration phase, in collaboration with the IOM office in the country of return. The above choices are also related to the profile of the returnees. For example, there’s a possible contrast between the profile of Georgians (‘voluntarily’) returning from Poland (or even other EU countries) and those returning via AVRR from Greece. In the former case there’s much focus on economic development in Georgia, while in Greece a good proportion of elder/retirement age people seem to participate in the AVRR.

Apart from the in-kind reintegration assistance, the post-return doings may include *financial assistance* for the returnees. For example, Sweden also offers a repatriation grant to stimulate immigrants who are legally residing in Sweden to voluntarily return to their home countries. In the Netherlands, the standard reintegration budget reaches 1800 euros per case through the IOM. The JRS programmes of Frontex, the implementation of which varies among examined countries, also provide financial incentives for to-be-returned migrants. For example, in the Netherlands and Sweden, it has widened the scope of instruments and financial spaces that case workers can use in their efforts to return migrants. A particular doing related

to this financial assistance is the act of bargaining and negotiating return assistance. This is done by individual case workers when they negotiate higher return assistance for particular cases with their superiors. In addition, NGOs may be very active in stretching the financial means by applying for matching funds at the national (DTenV) and subnational (local municipality) level. They are particularly successful in cases of to-be-returned migrants who caused a ‘nuisance’ in society.

In default assisted return procedures, migrants only receive a very limited sum of money in cash. As the Dutch case reveals, this money can be put on a credit card to avoid further financial exploitation of migrants at the airport of return (e.g., the confiscation of cash by border guards). In Greece, cash assistance in the period of our research amounted to €1.000 per individual or €500 for those residing on the Aegean islands and was handed to the returnees right after their travel documents’ control at the airport. In the German case, this provision of cash assistance is provided by a subcontracted actor. The largest share of the return assistance, however, is transferred to a local counterpart in the country of return. Hence, the financial assistance is also an important issue in the countries of return. In Morocco, for example, individual financial assistance offered by the IOM is up to €1000 per beneficiary, to which €400 can be added if the reintegration project is part of a collective or community approach. In Tunisia, as part of its partnership with the Tounesna programme, the French Office for Immigration and Integration (OFII) offers both technical and financial support to migrants returning to Tunisia, whether they are coming from France, another European country, or a third country used as a transit point. These reintegration aids are designed to facilitate the sustainable resettlement of migrants and are provided based on specific eligibility criteria and the availability of programme funding. Depending on the needs and profiles of the beneficiaries, the support can include social reintegration assistance, employment-based reintegration, or assistance for creating a business.

Overall, the above described complexities and shortcomings, bring to the forefront, among others, the limitations of the notion of ‘reintegration’ per se, as understood by IOM (IOM 2022), and the need for a more nuanced understanding and implementation of reintegration that apart from the economic, social and psychosocial aspects, pays attention to the political context and governance structures in the origin country for returnees’ reintegration as well as to other complex factors that shape their experiences, sense of belonging, and aspirations (Şahin-Mencütek 2023).

5.2 Cross-cutting issues

The complexity described above, as an inherent characteristic of the doings in the different types of RMIs, is interrelated with a range of other issues that emerge as cross-cutting themes, as they may refer to different types of doings mentioned earlier. Before we outline these cross-cutting issues, it is crucial to note that there is a mushrooming of activities and a pluriformity of the actual doings of these activities that can only be explained by the European shift towards more restrictive migration policies. This has institutionalized return processes, expanded roles for various authorities and introduced new governmental and non-governmental actors in this field, bringing their own instruments and expertise (e.g. Barthoma and Tommos 2025).

5.2.1 Between ‘one-size-fits-all’ and ‘case-by-case’ approaches

First and foremost, it should be mentioned that in most of the doings, and especially in AVRR programmes, a *double process* usually emerges. It is constituted by both seemingly standardized, uniform, and ‘one-size-fits-all’ regulations, services, and procedure for all and a ‘case-by-case’ and individualised assessment framework. This paradox brings inherent tensions and implementation gaps. In Germany, for instance, return migration governance is fragmented, overly complex, and full of discrepancies due to federalism. This inherent discrepancy starts from the overarching standardized migration laws that are considered to be ‘overly abstract, inflexible and bureaucratic, which dehumanizes migrants, turning them into numbers, objects and statistics rather than individuals with (dis)abilities and needs’ (Mielke et al. 2025, p.79). This abstract centralized reality is, in the case of the federalist German state, supplemented by regulations at the federal state and sub-state district levels, creating not only a need for institutional interfaces but also variations in terms of doings across states and sub-states. This discrepancy of practices within an EU member state is particularly important to acknowledge in the light of the continued emphasis on ‘harmonisation’ of migration policies on the EU level.

The double process of uniformity and case-by-case approaches relates, among others, to the sequences of the doings that usually may depend on the legal status of returnees, possession of identification and travel documents, vulnerabilities, places of stay while awaiting return, and varying types of encounters with relevant authorities. All these may result in different versions of the AVRR process. Moreover, further differentiations in the doings emerge due to the particular actors in charge and their usual practices, ranging from ‘tailor-made services’ with room for ‘creativity’ and ‘discretionary power’ to the case workers to uniform approaches that do not relate to individual trajectories. Such differentiation can be encountered not only among different migrants-to-be-returned but also concerning the same migrant when his/hers file moves from officer to officer.

Upon returns, there emerges both an ‘one size fits all’ and a case-by-case examination approach at the same time. In Nigeria and Iraq, we noticed processes of assessment that impact –in very different ways– returnees’ positions in the return procedure and create different –and usually unequal– overall return experiences for returned migrants.

5.2.2 Informalities in RMIs

Informality, usually accompanied by a lack of transparency, is also a characteristic of different doings in the RMIs of all types. The continuum between individual assessments and uniform processes mentioned earlier strengthens such aspects of informality. Moreover, informality crosscuts many types of doings, from the diplomatic negotiations between state representatives to the crucial role of informal relations between networks of NGOs in the field of assisted returns. In other words, informal practices are vital elements in all settings we investigated, from the setting of deportability in Europe to the reintegration practices in the countries of return. To illustrate the latter, the Tunisian report writes how informal alliances emerge between NGOs and public agencies to overcome bureaucratic delays and respond quickly to migrants’ needs (Boubakri et al. 2025). For Nigeria, it is reported how IOM at times bypasses the National Commission for Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced (NCFRMI) when they involve local NGOs or business partners. Furthermore, the same report foregrounds

the pivotal role played by religious networks, family, communities, and friends in reintegration processes.

To shift the attention to Europe again, informality may emerge in relation to the consultation meetings defining the type of return to be followed. In the case of both AVR and forced returns in Sweden, the counselling meetings, and especially the motivational interviews, are characterised by the lack of transparency, clarity, and the fostering of informality, as information is communicated in a 'semi-informal' manner (Barthoma and Tommos 2025). The fact that soft power strategies are employed to persuade migrants to voluntarily return, the exact content of which is not clear, permits informal practices and strategies to emerge both regarding the content of the discussion and the number of the meetings that depend on 'the number needed to enforce the return decision or the circumstances of the return' (EMN 2023, p.64). The role of regiovoorders in the Netherlands also involves informal practices not strictly legally defined, as they are asked 'to take initiative' in the procedures they are involved in and, if necessary, to find 'creative solutions', usually to promote the assisted return option. As it has been mentioned for the case of the Netherlands, there is a governance architecture (Van Riemsdijk et al. 2021) behind this RMI that can be seen as a form of 'ordered chaos' by design (Koinova et al. 2024) that *allows for informal practices to make the formal rules work* (Borrelli and Lindberg 2025). In the case of AVR in Greece, IOM staff and OCAVR managers may also adopt informal practices and temporary 'exceptions' from particular requirements on a 'case-by-case basis' to facilitate different procedural steps, especially if the to-be-returned migrants are considered vulnerable, with particular health situations. Moreover, the work of Embassies, needed for the implementation of returns, may include informal practices, or -as argued for the case of Sweden- embassies of countries of origin have become part of Sweden's RMI through formal, quasi-formal, and informal cooperation methods around returns.

Informal practices and doings also concern particular 'pilot' programmes in return operations. Pilot programmes allow for experimentation, with the latter playing a crucial role in return and reintegration governance (Vollmer and Şahin-Mencütek 2023). We have noticed a particular tendency in this respect to interrelate more closely forms of detention with return practices. This concerns the case of a *de facto detention practice* for North African asylum seekers in the Netherlands and the case of the so-called 'pilot project' implemented since 2017 in Greece. As regards the first, apart from the existing migrant detention centres, in February 2024, the Dutch media reported about fenced-off spaces in the Ter Apel location as *de facto* detention facilities targeting North African asylum seekers that are often considered to be little-chance applications or seen as 'nuisance asylum seekers', even if there was no legal ground for their detention (NRC 2024). These practices resemble relevant practices already emerged in Greece for the management of refugee movements since 2015: More particularly, since 2017, a 'pilot project' known as the 'Low-Profile Scheme' has been implemented in Lesbos, Kos, and partly Leros (Leivaditi et al. 2020). It referred to a highly systematised and arbitrary practice of detention, not legally defined in the legislation, according to which newcomers belonging to particular nationalities, whose country of origin has low recognition rates in the EU, were immediately placed in administrative detention upon completion of reception and identification procedures and remained there for the entire asylum procedure (GCR 2018). Such practices constitute *ad hoc* decisions of actors in the field, giving room for arbitrary decisions to be made, by thus reproducing and redefining different categories of people; as categories that are highly fluid and unstable and may irregularise particular groups or individuals in not always visible ways (Papatzani et al. 2024). These doings, designed as pilot projects with an *ad hoc* structure, indicate that *informalities may form part of official*

practices, while at the same time include the element of political and policy *experimentation* and open future possibilities.

Informality also emerges at the level of information sharing. In the Netherlands, DTenV regievoorders and COA case managers use to combine fragments of information in order to decide or materialise return strategies, as part of their formalized practices of information sharing during meetings. These formal and *informal ways of information sharing* might be very practical, but they also raise serious ethical concerns. This is particularly the case for the COA case managers in question in the Netherlands as they play the role of trust persons, and claim to have a more holistic view on the people, while they also inform return strategies that are coordinated by DTenV regievoorders. At the same time, informal connections and informal sharing are part of the process too, especially when different actors share the same physical location for their doings, as also mentioned later in the Section ‘Materials and Technologies’.

Within the implementation of RMIs, these practices may also be seen as a *form of agency* of the actors involved. Such agency also impacts the RMIs themselves and constitutes a factor enhancing their dynamic and shifting character.

Apart from informalities emerging in the doings of AVRR and forced removals, probably the most indicative example of informal –*mainly illegal*– practices are the pushbacks and pushforwards, as they emerge from the cases of Poland, Greece, and Turkey. In this case, informality goes hand in hand with illegality, as these practices are allegedly at an institutional grey zone whilst violating international law. Pushbacks, by definition, involve forcibly returning individuals across borders without allowing access to asylum procedures or due process. Especially in the case of Turkey, it is argued that pushforwards have emerged as an alternative or as complementary to formal return mechanisms, functioning as a strategy that indirectly forces migrants towards the EU borders and other regions, and forces them to keep moving⁸.

5.2.3 The importance of ‘non-doings’

If, as determined by the very beginning, RMIs are constituted by the different doings (among other things) that put returns into practice, then non-doings become the shadow part of RMIs, with non-doings referring to practices that are ‘omitted’ from the abovementioned procedural steps and tend to concern returnees’ needs, as for example post-return health related monitoring (see Dutch and German reports). Interestingly, and considering the transnational context of migration governance, national sovereignty and non-interventionism return as arguments against post-return monitoring. Moreover, ‘sustainability’ of returns is put into question due to the lack of information about post-return trajectories.

Another characteristic example of doing via non-doing comes from Greece, where the implementation of AVRR remains blind to the issue of personal liberty of those registered. The programme’s participants may be arrested on the streets due to their irregular status and detained or, if already in detention, remain in the detention centres, during the implementation of the different steps of the procedure, ironically including ‘protection’ assessments. Implementing ‘protection’ as part of the AVRR process within a detention context creates an inherently problematic and contradictory situation, directly challenging the

⁸ Along with pushbacks, the case of the EU-Turkey Statement, facilitating forced returns of Syrians from Greece to Turkey, is a characteristic example of an informal readmission tool, rather than a legally defined framework. The EU-Turkey Statement can be considered as a crisis-driven readmission tool of a flexible and informal form.

voluntary nature of AVRR. Moreover, non-doings here concerns the lack of protection from arrest and detention that AVRR participants should have (irrespective of being already detained or not) and the lack of adequate accommodation, such as the OCAVRR, for the pre-return period. Thus, the application of a standardized procedure for all AVRR participants fails to address pre-existing unequal positions, particularly for those in detention, and as a result, AVRR does not protect migrants from detention in an official way.

Yet another non-doing has to do with clear information provision regarding crucial aspects of the return process to the migrants themselves. This lack of information, combined with sudden pick-ups (as in the case of Germany and the Netherlands) can be traumatic experience and provoke resistance during these rupturing events. Similarly, in cases of church asylum in Germany, the BAMF does not inform the person granted asylum on church premises about the termination of the time limit for their Dublin transfer. Instead, the BAMF expects the person to inquire about it personally and does not allow a third party to do so, citing reasons of data protection and data security, even though the information does not have to be passed on to the third person, but to the asylum seeker. As a result, there is a risk that church asylum cases are artificially prolonged by months, sometimes due to non-communication by the BAMF. Informed observers see this as a strategy to systematically delay the procedure and to cause additional hardship for the migrant and their support community (Mielke et al 2025, pp. 71-72).

Overall, these examples highlight that particular practices remain ‘invisible’ by choice, and thus they could be understood as non-doings or inactions. On the one hand, these non-doings may emerge as ‘gaps’ by flawed actions due to passive neglect or systemic failures of the procedures. On the other hand, non-doings may also emerge as purposeful ‘strategic moves’ or as systemic failures to address known problems despite their recognition (Barthoma and Tommos 2025). Such non-doings may also be seen as the Janus face of informalities: the latter trying to informally amend the gaps while the former widening them (or even co-creating them). Thus non-doings can be acknowledged as a form of governance, a policy of non-policy, a ‘strategic indifference’ as characterized elsewhere (Norman 2020), with parallels in how states approach ‘non-deportable’ migrants, through non-enforcement of deportation orders or the withholding of regularisation (Leerkes and Van Houte 2020) by contributing to the reproduction of irregularisation as a process (Papatzani et al. 2024).

5.2.4 Irregularisation in the RMIs

Besides detention, irregularisation also emerges as an inherent element of RMIs. Returns are interconnected with the irregular status of migrants, and even more crucially, with irregularisation as a process. Some examples are worth mentioning related to this:

First, in the case of the Netherlands, these are the cases of ‘evacuation’: In such a situation the 28-day limit has been exceeded, while there is no prospect of an assisted return or forced removal, and the person refuses to leave his/her room. People are then removed from their rooms and put on the street by the local police. They leave the asylum location (AZC) independently. In terms of administration, these cases are closed with the indication ‘termination of reception facilities’. This might imply a move to an unknown country or a move towards an irregular stay in the Netherlands. Another interesting aspect of irregularisation derives from the LVV programme in the Netherlands, in which the authorities prioritize, as the most sustainable solution, the (assisted) return, and only if this cannot be achieved, regularisation is considered to be a welcome alternative (Mack et al. 2022). In other words, the

authorities take an irregular stay for granted to facilitate/stimulate returns. Yet, NGOs involved in the programme usually insist on legal (re-)explorations after migrants' request, and 445 people have been regularized through the LVV programme, which is actually a higher number than the 208 people that have been returned through these programmes. Other forms of continued irregularisation occur when the authorities have no other option to release a migrant from detention after their failed attempts to deport a particular person within the detention time limit.

Moreover, in the case of Greece and Turkey, irregularisation relates to AVR. More specifically, the enrolment in AVRR in Greece presupposes that the applicants withdraw their asylum applications, and refrain from any rights coming with a real or potential regular status – either of an international protection beneficiary or a migrant with a valid stay permit or even the temporary 'regularity' of an asylum seeker. This process can be seen as a peculiar (self-)irregularisation, i.e., of accepting an irregular status, in order to take advantage of the benefits of AVRR. On the other hand, for some undocumented migrants approaching IOM to enroll in the programme it may be the first time they obtained any kind of 'document' in Greece, only to be officially recognized as 'irregular', and prepare them to return. Thus irregularity (and irregularisation) can be considered as constitutive of the AVRR's implementation: *Irregularity may be seen as an important pre-condition for the implementation and maintenance of AVRR*. Similarly, under the National Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (N-AVRR) Programme in Turkey, beneficiaries of international and temporary protection that wish to voluntarily return to their countries, and especially Syrians, have to accept the termination of the temporary protection status, and all rights afforded to temporary protection ID holders are consequently forfeited, and authorities thus take away their temporary protection ID card at the border.

The above examples illustrate the not always visible but existing relationships between returns and irregularisation as a process, rather than merely irregularity as a legal status.

5.2.5 Soft power techniques of enforcing collaboration

What is also interested in the actors' 'doings' in the continuum of coercion examined, is the use of soft power techniques the form of which may differ: it may include communicative practices of power, efforts of building trust at the same time that enforcing particular return options, the importance of the migrants' behavior in determining the type of return, and the efforts of enforcing voluntariness and collaboration, among others.

Soft power techniques also appear to be highly present in the process of identity confirmation. Migrants are occasionally persuaded and misled by 'the system' to reveal their identities (see also Schapendonk 2020). From the administrative point of view, this can be considered to be all 'part of the game' (see also Mielke et al. 2025, p.81). Acknowledging this deceiving strategy as an inherent part of the *regiming* of return migration is of crucial importance, as migrants are often blamed for 'absconding and deceiving migration authorities' (Borrelli 2021, p.3474).

In the case of counselling meetings in countries where they are an integral part of the procedure, soft power techniques are extensively used, as such meetings may define the type of return that will be followed for each returnee (either forced removal, or assisted voluntary returns). In such counselling meetings, it is obvious how voluntary return and forced removal are part of a continuum, rather than a strict dichotomy. As regards the use of soft power techniques, in Sweden, different persuasive techniques are used, emerging as communicative

technologies of power, and a range of supportive and punitive measures that exist reflect a carrot-and-stick approach. The nature of the conversation tends to be predominantly one-sided, with an inherent asymmetry emerging in the relationship that makes it unlikely for a rejected asylum seeker to effectively contest the negative asylum decision. Such practices of power are also implemented in the case of the Netherlands not only by the DTenV regievoorders, but also by non-state actors. Both state and non-state actors stress the importance of building trust as well as starting from a particular form of ‘honesty’ or ‘directness’ to migrants, at the same time that directness may be interrelated with confrontation. This is usually done by actively massaging the aspirations of migrants, by using either soft approaches, such as stressing people’s brighter futures in the process or stringent and directive conversations. Moreover, in the case of Poland, the behaviour of the migrants is one of the conditions upon which detention can be decided.

A commonality between the Swedish, Dutch, and German cases is that case workers of migration-related authorities regularly play a double role in return conversations. On the one hand, they try to perform a trust relation with migrants; on the other, they can be stringent and repressive (see also Cleton and Chauvin 2020). Due to relocations within the Dutch system, it also happens frequently that a migrant case is assessed/handled by a new DTenV caseworker. The mobility of dossiers creates a plurality of doings to materialise returns as new caseworkers study the dossier, come up with new interpretations of the situations at play, and try different methods in these return conversations. Recently, through the Frontex programme EURP/JRS, state authorities have broadened their instruments as this programme enables them to facilitate ‘voluntary’ returns. However, exactly because return counselling often relies heavily on trust and interpersonal conversations, this task is still outsourced to other non-actors, including the IOM, churches, and specialized NGOs. The doings most often concentrate on dissolving migrant reluctance through information, and more importantly, future orientation and training provisions.

Based on the above, it becomes evident how the continuum of coercion may take the character of enforced voluntariness, and –as the other side of the coin– *enforced collaboration*. In the Swedish case, the aforementioned soft power techniques aim to enforce the returnee to choose either to cooperate and return ‘voluntarily’ or face detention and forced deportation. The returnees’ ‘cooperative attitude’ is assessed as a crucial determinant of the next return steps to be followed: ‘collaboration’, as a key prerequisite for facilitating voluntary return, is that ‘the foreign national has an attitude that does not prevent a return’. Cooperation entails the individual acknowledging the rejection decision, obtaining necessary identity documents, and agreeing to return voluntarily. Similarly, detainees are presented with a clear choice: cooperate and return voluntarily, or face enforced deportation by the police. Even in instances of coerced returns, law enforcement agencies often attempt to engage rejected asylum seekers in a cooperative dialogue, encouraging them to depart voluntarily. Similarly, in the case of the Netherlands, the question of the returnee’s cooperation is central in different parts of the procedure. When there is no cooperation from the rejected asylum seeker, DTenV may legally arrange custody and transport them to Rotterdam Detention Centre, from where return and removal activities continue. Moreover, in all conversations that occur in the context of coercion, the possibility of a forced removal is always present in the background, thus, coercion is an inherent part of their conversations and relationship with migrants.

6. Places, materials and technologies

6.1 Places and spatialities of RMIs

The materialities of RMIs, include, first and foremost the places where the wide range of involved actors are located, as well as the places where these actors put returns into practice, including all necessary steps and procedural doings mentioned earlier. The diversity of places as well as their different scales create complex geographies for all RMI types (assisted voluntary returns, forced removals, and pushbacks). For example, these places may include from the *national borders* where irregular crossings take place and where forced returns and pushbacks are implemented, to a *public square* where undocumented migrants get arrested by the police, or even to the conversation room where return counselling is taking place in particular countries. Moreover, these places are subject to change over time, depending on the political, economic, and social context in question. In this section is probably impossible to mention and thoroughly discuss all places that form the diverse geographies of RMIs; instead we will discuss some of those emerging as most crucial in the majority of the country cases examined.

6.1.1 Borders and airports

The national borders, including the land borders, sea borders, as well as the airports as border zones, constitute significant places of the RMIs' geography. Borders are zones where a number of procedures take place, including – among others – rejections at the borders, fast-track border procedures, the issuance of deportation decisions and of course, detention. More particularly, in Greece, national borders are a key entry point in the infrastructure of forced removals since, with their control mechanisms and procedures, they aim at detecting those who arrive and at categorizing them through a process of identification and screening. Such processes take place especially at the so-called Reception and Identification Centres, located in particular border areas, especially the northern Aegean islands where Hotspots have been established. Moreover, particularly on these border islands, expulsion decisions are issued pre-emptively against TCNs entering Greece, before their identification, even if they subsequently apply for international protection and obtain a permit to stay in the country.

Pushbacks, also, takes place almost exclusively at the borders – with some exceptions as the Greek cases shows where pushbacks can also happen from the mainland, even days after border crossings. In Greece, the material spaces of pushbacks include border police stations, detentions centres, unofficial sites, as well as the Evros fence at the northeast borders of the country. In Turkey, pushforwards take place at the borders and can manifest, among others, through the easing of border controls at particular times. It is also worth mentioning, that especially in Edirne and Kırklareli, close relationships with the city of Istanbul also emerge, as it functions as a central hub in the coordination and operationalisation of migration control strategies. In such border areas, Turkey has implemented a range of measures to enhance border surveillance, including among others the construction of physical barriers and the establishment of specialized facilities such as liaison offices and guest houses. Specifically, at the Edirne-Greece border, the installed 2-meter-high panel fences mounted on 1-meter concrete blocks were visible. Concrete structures mark the Turkey-Greece border, and the barbed wire fences on the other side are also visible. Such measures are especially visible in the border villages, impacted particularly from the material aspects of RMIs. Landscape transformations are observed due to the range of measures, including the border stations as well as the

technologically equipped towers, standing meters higher than, have become the dominant structures, even higher than the mosque minarets that used to be the most distinctive feature of villages.

Picture 1. Border Villages and Surveillance Towers in Turkey. Source: Gökalp Aras et al. 2025.

Picture 2. Border Villages and Border Stations/Checkpoints in Turkey. Source: Gökalp Aras et al. 2025.

The *airports* of all countries, both those returning and those receiving migrants are also of crucial importance. During the departure days, a series of particular doings unfold in particular airport spaces to put returns into practice. Both in cases of forced removals and in cases of assisted voluntary returns, each examined country uses the airports spaces differently following particular procedures, as evident from the case of Greece presented below. In many cases, the airports are also detention spaces, as evident in the case of the Schiphol airport at the Netherlands which has its own detention centre specialized for border refusals.

Picture 3. A return operation of Georgian returnees carrying the IOM bag, at the Athens International Airport. Source Papatzani et al. 2025. – and usually reintegration – doings commence.

Picture 4. A return operation of Georgian returnees carrying the IOM bag, at the Athens International Airport. Source Papatzani et al. 2025. urn the

Baghdad Airport, the returnee is received by the relevant authorities to provide him the required services and implement necessary assessments. As argued, the airport transforms to the place where reception is centralized to ensure documentation and database maintenance, and provide immediate services. In Baghdad International Airport, as in most other airports, there is an airport police station, where deportees are detained for identification papers especially in cases they have been deported without prior knowledge of – and coordination with – the Iraqi authorities. In the case of Nigeria, too, the three particular international airports form the main node of the complex infrastructural network, and where the procedure starts by the provision of initial screening and support. Other spaces are then added in the necessary doings as the Migrant Transit Centre (MTC) in Lagos or the temporary holding facility in Kano, or in the case of Abuja, they are held in tents for one to two days for screening. Such spaces are absent in Morocco and Tunisia, as also mentioned later.

Textbox 4: Ethnographic notes from the observation of a departure of Georgian AVRR returnees at the El. Venizelos Athens International Airport.

On Thursday, November 2, 2023, a three-member team from EKKE had the opportunity to conduct ethnographic observation during the final procedures for the return of 37 migrants to Georgia from the Athens International Airport.

Our team arrives at the airport half an hour before the scheduled 9:00 p.m. meeting time. The flight departs at 11:45 p.m. thus leaving enough time to guide the group through the entire process. We immediately recognise those who have already arrived from their large white bags with the IOM logo. A few minutes after 9:00 p.m., the four-member IOM team arrives, consisting of two Outreach staff members from IOM headquarters to assist with crowd control, and two members from the Airport Team. They wear badges with IOM insignia around their necks, and as we were informed, they will soon also wear special vests displaying the new donor. One member of the IOM team explains the steps of the process to us while the other team members begin gathering the migrants around them: ‘Come over here, all those traveling’.

The IOM staff members provide instructions in Greek, occasionally switching to English for some individuals. The returnees are recorded on the list, and the return decision interoffice memo and AVRR cards are collected by IOM staff, who then hand out ticket copies to the migrants. In conversations among themselves, staff members refer to the participants by their identification codes. For example, they refer to a mother with a child as ‘636 is with 637’.

When the check is completed, the IOM team arranges the returnees in a line to count them: ‘We’ll do a cross-check to see if everyone is here. Let’s see if it’s 37!’ Instructions are given for those not traveling to stand separately. Here, the process takes on a sense of ‘crowd control’ for the first time. Once the count is completed, it is found that ten people are missing. They decide to move on to the next phase, leaving one IOM team member behind to manage the remaining ten individuals. The staff gives instructions to proceed to check-in, and the line starts moving.

In the queue for check-in, some people seem to know each other from before. A woman in front of us says she met the others during the IOM briefing, but there seems to be a greater familiarity between some of them. In the check-in line, some people goodbye their relatives and friends, and a few become emotional.

One from the IOM team takes us to the airport police office to hand over our IDs and receive the required tags to move freely beyond passport control. The same tags are used by police officers who are involved in the transfer of detainees.

This is followed by the police check of travel documents and return decision interoffice memos for the returnees. Throughout this process, IOM team members work closely with the police inside and outside the control booth, and there seems to be a strong rapport between them, as they are chatting and joking with each other. The file with the original stamped interoffice memo and copies of passports collected by the IOM employee is handed over to the police and locked in a police vault, the key being held by IOM. On the next day, the airport police duty officer retrieves the file and sends it to the Foreigners Department to register that these individuals have returned to their home country.

Next, the returnees proceed behind the booth where two other IOM staff members are handling the distribution of money to each individual passing through the check. One reads the identification code on the boarding pass. The other holds the folder, opens it in front of them, shows the two 500-euro notes, and hands it over. He repeats phrases such as ‘1,000 euros, please’ or ‘2,000 euros, please, thank you’ (for families). The migrants sign a receipt list. Some say ‘thank you’, while others remain silent. A few seem to feel awkward. The IOM employee maintains a detached demeanor. Some young Georgian women further down in the line made a breeze with the folder containing the money, laughing. We avoid looking at each transaction for more than a moment at a time as we also feel somewhat awkward, as if violating a private moment.

On the way to the departure gates, we pass through a ‘hidden’ door that had been locked until then, leading directly to the waiting area for the gates. A member of the IOM team explained that we used this door to avoid the group getting lost in the shops and causing delays and also to prevent the money given to the returnees from being spent in the stores. There is a clear instruction for returnees not to spend any amount of the financial assistance at the airport, because if the flight is cancelled, they would be required to return the entire amount. Aside from drinking water, they are not allowed to sit for coffee or shop at the duty-free stores while waiting.

When boarding starts, the migrants stand up without any special announcement. They now mix with the other passengers on the flight. The boarding process is completed in a few minutes, and the departure will occur with minimal delay. There are no strong displays of emotion, nor any notable farewells directed toward the IOM staff or us. We retrace our steps with the IOM staff. We all go together to the airport police office to return our identification tags. There are more police officers there now, both in uniform and one in civilian clothes, and they exchange friendly banter with the IOM staff, joking and discussing the schedule for the next day. (Papatzani et al. 2025).

6.1.2 Headquarters, offices, branches: from dispersal to the co-location method.

The *offices of involved actors* are worth mentioning. Even in cases when migrants do not have to visit them during the different steps of the return process, it is in these spaces where many crucial parts of the procedure are implemented. The offices of different types of actors are included in this regard, which may be both state and non-state ones, may include their local offices, central headquarters, branch offices, regional units, etc. Such places, thus, may range, also depending on each country’s migration system and general administrative organisation. For example, in the case of forced removals in Germany, federal system produces a complex interplay of multi-level authorities and offices, of which the higher federal authority of the

BAMF has branch offices in the major migrant reception facilities, mainly those accommodating more than 1,000 persons reaching the number of 60 local branch offices of the BAMF in 2023. In the case of AVR in Greece, IOM's presence includes the headquarters in Athens, an office in Thessaloniki, and the permanent presence in five towns of mainland Greece, Crete and the five 'hotspot' islands of the east Aegean where CCACs or Hotspots are operating (IOM 2023), showing a significant *dispersal*. If the police departments, the Asylum Service offices and the premises of various NGOs are also taken into account, a multileveled and diverse geography emerges.

At the same time, in many cases, such dispersal has proved to create difficulties in coordinating return procedures, especially in cases where many actors should closely collaborate to reach particular decisions, or to promote particular procedures and doings. In such cases, particular actors have chosen to work more closely, in physical terms, adopting the so-called '*co-location method*'. This means that the officers from the different actors started sharing the same office space. The co-location method is praised for facilitating shorter contact paths and an easier exchange of information, and planning and coordinating the return work. More particularly, in Sweden, in the context of forced removals, three key governance entities—the SMA, the Police, and the Prison and Probation Services—have recently intensified their collaboration through the co-location of their officers. Employees from the police and the Probation Service temporarily for a few days per week move into the premises of the Migration Agency Stockholm branch to work operationally together. Moreover, the Prison and Probation Service started an AMIF-funded project on 'Co-location with relevant border management authorities to increase capacity and quality of the return process'. In a similar fashion, at the initiative of the SMA and the Swedish Police Authority, the Ministry of Justice has set up the Officials' Network forum. The network aims at closer cooperation between authorities with a focus on selected countries to intensify the work on return.

In the Netherlands, the co-location is evident in both asylum spaces as well as detention spaces. The non-governmental actors are crucial in terms of monitoring migrant rights and needs. However, as mentioned, the proximity between the DTenV regievoorders, Vluchtelingenwerk, the COA case managers, and in many locations also the IOM, among others, is crucial, also to gain information needed for each case of returnees, sometimes through informal ways of sharing (as mentioned earlier).

[This proximity] works really well, because you can really collaborate to properly return a client ... or it is important to indicate that we need more time, to prevent them making a joyful jump because they can start the deportation process, that would be painful' (Schapendonk et al. 2025, p.43).

Proximity as the main aspect of co-location also emerged in the case of AVR in Greece. After a request from IOM, the Greek Asylum Service office located close to the IOM's headquarters, started to accept and provide services to applicants who needed to resign their asylum claims or statuses to avoid moving to the distant GAS headquarters, thus making the procedure faster and simpler. Apart from IOM's effectiveness in achieving small operational transformations in the Greek administrative system, the above highlights the dynamic character of AVR geography, constantly shifting to adapt to infrastructural needs with the aim to enhance collaboration and speed.

6.1.3 Detention spaces

Probably the most crucial material part of the RMIs in the spaces of detention which may be diverse depending on the particular context and migration/return system of each country case. Detention spaces may include *official pre-removal detention centres*, existing in all countries examined, but also *other types of detention-like facilities*. Detention centres range in terms of capacity and morphology, but usually share as common characteristics the prison typology, and they are consisted by fenced boundaries or walls, surveillance, and increased control.

In Turkey, 30 removal centres with a total detention capacity of 22,140 individuals existed as of 2023. Established also in the two provinces in which the fieldwork focused, they are designed to temporarily accommodate migrants who are subject to administrative detention prior to their deportation or voluntary return. They serve as a holding centres for migrants awaiting deportation or voluntary return, providing necessary services during their stay. In addition, other forms of detention emerge, including the *refurbished liaison offices and guest houses* at strategic border points, facilities that serve as contact points for the readmission of third-country nationals and are used for interviews, consular contacts, and document collection until transfer to removal centres or repatriation is arranged. In Greece apart from the pre-removal detention centres, various *police stations* around the country serve as detention spaces where migrants are detained in generally harsh and sometimes inhuman conditions (BVMN, 2023; GCR, 2024). Detention is also used *inside* the Hotspots especially at the border islands, particularly for those who just arrived, even before they manage to register an asylum claim. *Detention sectors* also exist in the two Reception and Identification Centres (RICs) operating in the mainland, where individuals wishing to apply for asylum arrange appointments to register their application, but until then, they are detained in the premises. Moreover, as already mentioned particular facilities at the border areas, functioning also in informal ways, not legally defined in legislation, exist to facilitate police operations, including pushbacks.

In the Netherlands, there are two prototypical migrant detention centres. The first is located at Schiphol Airport and detains so-called border refusals. The latter may also include people who ask for asylum at Schiphol. In addition, Rotterdam detention centre, which exists since 2010, is located at Rotterdam/The Hague Airport. It has a total capacity of 320 rooms (with a maximum of 2 persons per room). Other types of detention-like centres, in the Netherlands, include, for example, the *freedom restricted centre* in Ter Apel, and the so-called '*closed family location*' located within a detention facility which is less 'cell-like' including a large green area.

In Sweden, in June 2023, the SMA was assigned by the government to create 'return centres' that function as collective accommodations for individuals subject to enforceable transfer, expulsion, or rejection decisions; but what actually took place was a rebranding of existing *detention facilities*. Six return centres exist, mainly aiming at enforcing expulsion decisions, providing approximately 1,162 accommodations, targeting to increase capacity per 40-50 percent, to 1,800 to 2,000 places from 2023 to 2025. Fieldwork in Sweden focused at the detention centres of Gävle and Märsta which is the largest located near Stockholm-Arlanda airport. Detention centres are locked accommodation facilities where detainees can move freely within the premises, living in single or shared rooms and sharing common areas like bathrooms, living, dining, and exercise rooms. They accommodate men, women, and children, although there are designated areas where men may be restricted from entering under certain circumstances. Detention centres are characterized by a significant layer of security measures, they are enclosed by a cage-like fence, and the movement within the centre is restricted. While offering a semblance of controlled freedom, they function similarly to prisons, as the movement and interactions of detainees are regulated and structured according to specific protocols. To support

mental and physical health, detention centres offer a variety of recreational activities. Outdoor courtyards provide space for daily outdoor activity, and gyms are available for physical exercise, and organized activities such as bingo and table tennis. When detainees become aggressive or unmanageable, they may be placed in segregation rooms, which contain a bed, shower, toilet, and a projector screen for watching films.

Picture 5 - Detention centre in Sweden (Barthoma & Tommos, 2025).

In Poland, six detention centres exist and may accommodate single men, single women, unaccompanied minors, families, including families with children. The detention centre in Biała Podlaska is a facility for up to 150 male asylum seekers or persons before a deportation operation. The centre is a prison-like facility with bars in the windows and barbed wires on the top of the detention fence. Apart from the detention centres, rooms for detained persons operate within the structure of Border Guard facilities and within the

structures of Police units, when deemed needed to secure the presence of a foreigner for the purposes of the return procedure. In the first case, detention in the facilities of the border guard is used when the operational capabilities of the Border Guard allow the return procedure of a foreigner to be carried out within 48 hours of his/her detention. In the case of detention in police units, it is the Border Guard, under agreements between the Commanders of the Border Guard Branches and the Provincial Police Commanders that foregrounded such decision.

Ad hoc and pilot practices of detention, as mentioned earlier in Section 5.2.2, may become part of the doings consisting the RMIs of different types. Some of them concern even detention, as in the case of ‘pilot’ programmes enhancing detention in the case of Greece and the Netherlands. As regards the Netherlands, the pilot detention programme targeting North African asylum seekers that are often considered to be little-chance applications is implemented in the fenced-off spaces in the Ter Apel location. In Greece such pilot programmes have taken place in the Hotspots of border islands or the RICs on the mainland, where reception and identification activities also take place.

Picture 6, Picture 7, Picture 8. Photos of the detention centre in Biała Podlaska. Source: Krępa et al. 2025.

6.1.4 Other accommodation places and the overlap of reception and return

Apart from the detention centres mentioned above, a number of *other places* also emerge where returnees are provided with accommodation while waiting for their departure, mainly in the assisted voluntary RMIs. In many cases, such *accommodation spaces are part of the reception and accommodation system for asylum seekers who stay there while waiting for the decision in their asylum application*. This is the case, for example, of reception camps hosting asylum seekers in many European countries, where parts of the return process are also put into practice, even in these places that refer to other asylum procedures (and not return).

In the case of Greece, for example, the IOM outreach activity for AVRR often takes place in sites intended for asylum, such as the Hotspots and the Closed Controlled Access Centres (CCACs) on the border islands, and the mainland reception and accommodation camps, thereby targeting individuals who may still be in the asylum process and legally entitled to remain in the country prior to any removal order.

Another characteristic example exists in Germany, where the central or municipal accommodation facilities are crucial places of the return infrastructures. They constitute the places where return counselling is conducted and from where returnees are transferred to the airport. Also, the so-called AnKER facilities providing accommodation in asylum seekers have as a central characteristic and goal the bundling of all functions and responsibilities at one location: from arrival, asylum application and decision to municipal distribution, initial preparatory integration measures and the return procedure of rejected asylum applicants. Thus, even if they form part of the reception of asylum seekers and refugees they also serve for the implementation of returns, revealing also in this case the intersection and overlap of different processes (returns and asylum/reception) in the same places.

Seemingly, in the case of the Netherlands, the complex network of accommodation spaces may include – apart from detention centres – the regular asylum accommodation locations (AZC) and the LVV programme's locations in different municipalities. Regular asylum accommodation may include different types of accommodation, connected with the different steps of the asylum application procedure. A notable example is the *application centre in Ter Apel*

mentioned earlier, with a formal capacity of 2000 people which besides being a first point of entry, is also an exit centre, due to the fact that return counselling and removal activities for either assisted return or forced removal take place also there – apart from the procedures related to the asylum application. Another example on which the fieldwork also focused is a permanent *regular asylum accommodation centre* (AZC) operating since 1994 consisting of 7 buildings (former military terrain) with approximately 400 beds available, located in a thriving urban neighbourhood, with a primary school next door, from which return processes are coordinated. Based on these examples, it is evident that infrastructures of entry and exit strongly overlap also in the case of the Netherlands.

The facilities of the 5-years pilot *programme LVV* are also important in this regard, as accommodation facilities for migrants without the right to stay in the Netherlands. The LVV is the Dutch national pilot project offering supervision and shelter to undocumented migrants in five cities: Amsterdam, Rotterdam, Utrecht, Eindhoven and Groningen. The formalized objective of the LVV is to find sustainable solutions for irregular migrants, between the three identified: assisted return, onward migration and regularized stay. In these accommodation centres bedrooms and living spaces are shared among migrants, while it is common for a number of involved actors to struggle find creative solutions to make these accommodation liveable spaces, by making use of invisible words of depots, volunteers transporting furniture, concierges, handymen, medical assistance, and so on. Moreover, one of the physical characteristics of these shelter accommodations is that they often do not stand out in the neighbourhood. One NGO representative stated the following in this respect: ‘I don't think that the normal people living here that they know, that they are really aware, of the LVV’ (Schapendonk et al. 2025, p.71). At the same time, it has been argued that the LVV programme can be seen as the outcome of the state’s wish to fundamentally reduce the capacity of migrant shelters in the Netherlands, as they are seen as ‘counterproductive in the formation of effective return policies’ (Mack, Verbeek and Klaver 2020, p.1).

An outstanding example of accommodation space for returnees comes from the case of AVRR in Greece and concerns the Open Centre for migrants registered to AVRR (OCAVRR). It is an open facility for temporary accommodation of returnees in Athens, and was established in 2015 in collaboration with the Ministry’s Reception and Identification Service, as a separate programme from AVRR. OCAVRR is considered by IOM as an ‘*alternative measure to detention*’ (IOM 2023, p.32). It is located in in one of the city’s inner suburbs. It offers accommodation to the most vulnerable AVRR participants, such as single parents, pregnant women, migrants with medical needs, the elderly, and the homeless⁹, either for the whole return process or for part of it, (as in the case of people residing outside Athens but visiting Athens for the issuance of their documents). Certain rules and regulations apply in OCAVRR, as in other accommodation facilities, including their residents’ obligation to be present during regular population verification (Papatzani et al., 2022). IOM representatives consider OCAVRR as a key asset of AVRR and an exemplary facility altogether. As one of them commented,

‘the facility in Galatsi is a model one. I wish all European countries had similar facilities. It is unique in Europe’ (Papatzani et al. 2025, p.38).

OCAVRR has a capacity of approximately 100 people, and at the time of our research visit, it accommodated about 40 people. From September 2019 to August 2023, 2,482 migrants had

⁹ Unaccompanied minors and victims of trafficking are accommodated in other facilities under the responsibility of state authorities.

been accommodated (Papatzani et al. 2025). The rooms in OCAVRR may host from three up to eight or 10 people, especially in the case of families, respecting the criterion of preserving and protecting family unity. Gender also plays a role in the distribution of residents, while language or ethnicity are also considered to some extent. Medical issues as well as psychosocial criteria are also important. The facility follows particular rules for accessibility, including the existence of a room on the ground floor for people using a wheelchair, while rooms on the first floor accommodate those in need of closer attention, as they are closer to the services on the ground floor. OCAVRR is an open facility, meaning that those residing in it may enter and exit as they wish, yet after passing the control checks during their entrance and exit, and by using their AVRR card. It should be mentioned that OCAVRR is currently the most well-organized, and comprehensive urban accommodation facility in Athens and Greece, while addressed to people subject to return. In sharp contrast, urban accommodation facilities addressed to asylum seekers subject to protection and beneficiaries of protection subject to integration and housing services provisions have been absent since the termination of the ESTIA programme in late 2022 (Kandyliis et al. 2024) and the current termination of IOM HELIOS programme (IOM 2024).

Picture 9, Picture 10. The Open Centre for migrants registered in AVRR in Athens. Source: Papatzani et al. 2025.

Accommodation places may not only concern the pre-return face in the returning countries, but also the post-return in countries receiving the returnees. In many receiving countries, temporary accommodation centres are established offering the first shelter for a short period of time to people who have just returned, according to particular criteria.

In the case of a forced return to Iraq, for example, temporary shelter is provided through the Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs if the person is homeless upon arrival. This can be in government shelters or through partnerships with non-governmental organisations. In the case of Nigeria, there exists the *Migrant Transit Centre* which serves as a temporary residence for returnees and displaced persons. Funded by the EU and implemented by IOM, this centre provides immediate assistance to returnees for approximately five days upon their arrival, before they proceed home or are referred to relevant agencies. Lagos hosts a transit centre capable of accommodating up to 400 people, which became fully operational in May 2022 and has since welcomed over 1,000 returnees. A second one is being proposed in Kano thereby expanding Nigeria's RMI.

In contrast, in the case of forced removal of migrants to Morocco, there are not any reception centres at the ports and airports; rent and temporary housing support only exists in the

case of IOM assisted returning Moroccans, which, though refers to only a very limited percentage of returnees. Seemingly, in Tunisia there isn't any specific centre provided for returnees to benefit from temporary accommodation.

It should also be mentioned that places of accommodation before return, may also refer to doings and places contesting returns. This is the example of church asylum in the case of Germany

They may include the church asylum, as some parishes in NRW have been providing church asylum for many years, sometimes on a large scale, with at least ten people in church asylum at any one time, and sometimes as many as 35 people at the same time. At the same time they may concern aspects of proactive opposition to forced removals.

6.1.5 Other places of potential returnees' identification – expanding return geographies

The complex geographies of RMIs of different types also include the range of places where potential returnees can be identified, and possibly picked up or arrested.

In the aforementioned case of *pushbacks*, these places include mainly the national borders that become the primary sites of violent and unlawful return practices. In the case of both forced removals and assisted voluntary returns, RMIs are connected to the place where the enforcing actors pick up the returnee or a potentially to-be-returned migrant. In this regard, the materialities of return infrastructures extend beyond the official material facilities designed to serve the implementation of return (such as detention centres, other accommodation centres, etc.), since the returnees' identification may not be directly connected with a previous legal procedure and the individuals' stay in an official facility. A number of other spaces emerge as crucial: it is where police control practices are taking place even before identifying a to-be-returned migrant, or for this exact reason - but in any case, before the issuance of a return decision. This includes urban areas, public spaces, and sites of migrant concentration, including offices of migrant organisations, where regular police controls take place in the case of Greece. Moreover, they include markets, immigration offices or centres for asylum seekers, in the case of Poland. Also, such spaces may include the private place of residence of the designated returnee, or, in the case of Germany, even church premises as mentioned earlier.

In Turkey, related places include those determined as 'mobile migration points' (MMPs) which currently reach the number of 270, as well as Irregular Migrant Reception and Referral Centres (GOKSEM). These two new tools are particularly significant for controlling irregular migration and facilitating rapid deportation. The MMPs were first piloted in Istanbul in 2022 and expanded to other provinces. These units operate 24/7, conducting identity verification for apprehended migrants, especially in high-activity regions. It is interesting to mention that MMPs are not established in the Edirne and Kırklareli, the provinces which share borders with Greece and Bulgaria, respectively, on which the fieldwork on pushforwards focused. Instead, in these areas, military units are stationed, and military checkpoints are present serving as the primary enforcement mechanism for migration management in these border areas.

Picture 11, Picture 12. Mobile Migration Points in Turkey. Source: Ordu Valiliği 2023 in Gökalp Aras et al. 2025.

GOKSEM centres, established in February 2024, streamline the processing of irregular migrants, serving as hubs for admissions and referrals near removal centres. They operate with law enforcement agencies to handle identification, legal processes, and humanitarian aid in a coordinated manner. GOKSEM represent a key institutional innovation in Turkey’s return migration governance. Introduced as part of an effort to manage irregular migration more systematically, they serve as intermediary structures between apprehension and detention/deportation mechanisms. Unlike removal centres, their facilities are designed primarily for registration, biometric verification, status checking, and referral of apprehended individuals, especially those caught in urban areas or during street-level controls. Their growing importance lies in the fact that they operate as frontline screening and filtering nodes, enabling the state to determine the legal status of migrants (e.g. whether they are under Temporary Protection, International Protection, or completely irregular) and to refer them either to removal centres, temporary accommodation centres, or, in some cases, to reintegration services.

Picture 14. Irregular Migrant Pre-Admission and Referral Center (GÖKSEM). Source: Konya Valiligi 2024 in Gökalp Aras et al. 2025.

Picture 13. Irregular Migrant Pre-Admission and Referral Center (GÖKSEM). Source: Radyo80 2025 in Gökalp Aras et al. 2025.

6.1.6 Conversation (counselling) rooms

As already mentioned in section 5, in some countries, such as Sweden, Germany, and the Netherlands the stage and doings of counselling is crucial in determining –among others– the type

of return to be implemented, forced removal or assisted voluntary. Such practices are characterized by specific materialities, as they take place in the so-called conversation or counselling rooms.

In the Netherlands, such conversation rooms exist in the AZC on which the fieldwork focused and constitute one of the most important spaces in the centre. A number of actors involved, described the particular character of the rooms as a barrier to their work, as did the following COA case manager:

‘The conversation rooms are really empty, very sober. The chairs are fixated. The distance to the table is not very comfortable for the residents. The height of the chair is also far from comfortable. The priority is clearly security, and not whether somebody feels comfortable to talk. The distance to the Interpreter Telephone [tol-kentelefoon], basically everything is fixated. I cannot change anything. ... and there is this screen right in our middle, and when you have three interlocutors, you cannot see one of them because of the balk in the middle ... I remember how I started working here, with just a regular chair and a regular table’ (Schapendonk et al. 2025, p.46-47).

For the DTenV regievoerder the same conversation room had a different meaning. For him, it was an important requirement to have a large table with sufficient distance, and that there is literally a space for him ‘to escape’¹⁰. The difference in need for security can be explained for the different roles DTenV regievoerders embody, as in their experience, many migrants view them as the evil source that forces them to leave, and this leads to angry expressions and frustrations. All interviewees making use of similar spaces had their own tactics to deal with them. Some COA case managers, for example, look for more convivial spaces to talk to their clients (outside, in their rooms, or shared living spaces). Some DTenV regievoerders leave the door separating them from the migrant open, when they perceive they have a good relation with the to-be-returned migrant. In the detention centre, we spoke to one regievoerder who – against the protocol – sit at the same side of the separation screen to create a social atmosphere of closeness, if the situation allows for it. Thus, some material aspects of RMIs are actively shaped by the actors involved. In the future, this bending of spaces might work automatically, as indicated in the presentation of the ‘Conversation Room of the Future’ (see Textbox 5).

¹⁰ According to the DTenV, all workplaces must meet the physical safety standards. These standards are: a consultation room that is equipped to withstand molestation, an effective escape route, a suitable, intuitive alarm facility that is always responded to immediately and provided with adequate assistance, camera surveillance and/or physical surveillance in the vicinity.

Picture 15 (left): The open conversation room [no screens and no doors separating clients from authorities]. Source: Schapendonk et al. 2025.

Picture 16 (middle): The COA conversation room. Source: Schapendonk et al. 2025.

Picture 17 (right): The DTenV conversation room. Source: Schapendonk et al. 2025.

Textbox 5: The conversation room of the future. Hi-tech micro infrastructures

In October 2023, the DTenV organized its first Wetenschapsevent. This first time public event aims to bring together scientific insights and the daily realities of DTenV. The thematic focus of the day was *behaviour*, and it consisted of all kinds of sessions varying from intercultural dialogues to a lecture on motivating decision-making, and an interaction session on ethical questions (led by a specialist from Ministry of Defense). During this day, various designs of the ‘conversation room of the future’ were presented by the Technical University of Delft and

a design/development company (a project launched by COA, and co-funded by the EU). This particular design below caught our attention, as it is strikingly different from the current rooms that are used. The design of the room strives to create a safe space and the organic shapes seek to create comfort. We were told by the presenters that the light automatically becomes brighter in case a heated debate unfolds or somebody becomes angry or ‘very emotional’. The brighter light would make the person in question more docile, the argument was.

6.2 Materials

The materiality of return infrastructures also includes other non-human, physical and technological elements involved in encouraging, facilitating, regulating, implementing, enforcing or sometimes even contesting returns. The materials and technologies encountered in RMIs can be categorised according to the different actors involved, whether institutional actors and their personnel or the (returning, to-be-returned) migrants themselves, and to their doings that put returns into practice following standard procedures or applying ad hoc practices at various stages or moments. They also pertain to the different places and spaces described above, in all their diversity. Some materials are unique to specific RMIs as well as materials that are common among different RMIs in spaces, doings and activities that sometimes overlap.

Much of this materiality is about actual ‘things’, i.e. tangible objects, material resources, artefacts, specialised machinery and tools, various kinds of equipment, etc. which are there to serve a role, often in combination with other materials (as well as doings). Needless to say, that a full and detailed account of the entire universe of the materialities involved in RMIs would be an impossible (and possibly meaningless) task. Moreover, there are analytical difficulties in demarcating specific objects, equipment, etc., or even distinctive broad categories of materialities. In that respect, the observation made in the Swedish case holds general truth (despite its special reference to detention):

‘These elements exist in a co-constitutive relationship, meaning that the design and functioning of [...] infrastructures are continually influenced by the materialities and technologies embedded within them’ (Barthoma and Tommos 2025, p.61).

This echoes the argument emerged by the Dutch case, that the actors (including the actual persons involved) and their doings often imply ‘connecting materials to make returns happen’ (Schapendonk et al. 2025, p.51). So the materials listed below may be thought of as networked and interlinked components of integrated systems, composing thus both the ‘hardware’ and the ‘software’ of each particular RMI and shaping the overall return infrastructure at large. Although it is important to unpack the broader industrial complex behind this, it is beyond the scope of this report (but see for example Anderson 2014).

Security and enforcement

This category of materials includes specialised security and surveillance equipment, ranging from cameras and alarm systems at border posts and airports, detention centres, reception and other accommodation facilities, or the very premises of the different actors, as described above.

There is a diversity of such equipment, depending on the exact location and purpose. At the borders, for instance, the pushbacks infrastructure at the Evros borders of Greece include materials such ‘radars, thermal cameras, drones, thermovision vans, the automated border surveillance centre, five operational centres and the coordination centre at Nea Vyssa (several of them funded by EU funds) as well as Evros fence (2012) and its 2020 extension (not funded by the EU)’ (Papatzani et al. 2025, p.27). Similarly, at the other side of the border, where some of those pushed back may be returned through pushforward practices, the materials used include electro-optic towers, thermal cameras, and mobile surveillance units (Gökalp Aras et al. 2025).

At other places and scales, the materiality of security may also be reflected on the spatial design, layout and special arrangements that maintain physical and symbolic *distance*, by segregating and/or separating migrants. Nowhere is this more pronounced than in detention centres: for instance, in the ‘prison-like’ facility described in the case of Poland ‘with bars in the windows and barbed wire on the top of the detention fence’ (Krępa et al. 2025, p.24). But also in the ‘hostel’-like Swedish detention centres, characterised by ‘humane’ internal design and conditions where inmates have access to several amenities and are allowed to move freely, yet they are ultimately separated from the outside world by physical objects such as locked external doors and constantly monitored through equipment like alarms and surveillance cameras; while those ‘deemed disruptive or at risk of self-harm’ reside in segregated units (Barthoma and Tommos 2025). Other examples of objects and arrangements that separate may include the glass separators between bureaucrats and ‘clients’ in (some) Dutch return conversation rooms, or in the rooms where psychological counselling takes place in Polish detention centres, as well as the protective grid in vehicles separating drivers and officers from the transported migrants. A COA Case manager interviewee in the Netherlands study explained the fixated furniture as purposely undermining comfort and maintaining distance since security is the priority as mentioned earlier.

Finally, security-related personal equipment is of crucial importance. This concerns the gear of enforcement officers, such as police or border guards, e.g. their uniforms, (ballistic) vests, helmets or protective gloves, to bodycams, fingerprint readers, teasers, handcuffs (steel or disposable) or stick batons. But it may even include the uniforms, masks, weapons, immobilising devices, etc., carried by the undercover army/security personnel or paramilitaries in the case of illegal pushbacks at the Greek-Turkish border.

Transportation

This includes a range of different transportation means involved in different contexts and for different purposes. In the previous section, airports were highlighted as key locations; thus airplanes, whether in regular airline flights or charter flights, are key means of transport carrying deportees as well as migrants repatriated via assisted return schemes. From the point of view of the receiving country, in Tunisia, for example, increasing numbers of returns on regular or charter flights from Italy, Germany, France, with the support of Frontex are noted. More details are given regarding land transport, especially the various types of vehicles deployed to transport migrants from-and-to various places and locations. There are special vehicles for securitized or ‘high-security’ transport (Netherlands, Sweden), ‘prisoner buses’ (Poland), or police vans (Greece), in cases of arrests, detainees’ transfers or forced removals. In the Dutch case, such vehicles are unlabelled (without any official e.g. DV&O sign) and they are compartmentalized, with room for up to three officers to accompany even one individual

transportee. In some cases there have been improvements and adaptations to such vehicles to ensure some degree of comfort as regards specific needs. In Poland, for instance, as a former Border Guard officer told: ‘there are vehicles that are adapted to transport child seats, because you also need to be aware that the Border Guard sometimes deals with this, and these are air-conditioned vehicles’ (Krepa et al. 2025, p.23). In the Netherlands, the so-called ‘Luxe’ transport is deployed in case of exceptional situations such as precarious health conditions. The Dutch case also reports on circumstances when arrangements are made for people who need to be transported on a wheelchair. A rather distinct example of designated vehicle is to be found in the vans of the Turkish ‘mobile migration points’ that were discussed earlier. But there are also standard vehicles (vans, minibuses, or cars) designated for official use e.g. when transporting migrants to hospitals or embassy visits.

In some country cases non-designated means of transport exist which are occasionally being used, including public or private transport that e.g. AVRR beneficiaries may use themselves when travelling to and from their place of residence and the various offices and services they need to visit for administrative purposes. Taxis, for instance, and their drivers, are of particular importance in the case of pushforward practices from Turkey to Greece, linking main cities (e.g. Istanbul) and border towns (e.g. Edirne), ‘transporting migrants from designated meeting points, such as bus stations, informal gathering hubs, or smuggler-coordinated locations, to key border crossing zones’ (Gökalp Aras et al. 2025, p.78). Lastly, there are transportation means that are used or involved in the border control infrastructure encompassing pushbacks e.g. from Greece to Turkey: from official army and police vehicles (vans, cars, motorbikes) as well as Coast Guard vessels (depending on the location, land or sea borders), but also unidentified vehicles (and white vans) reportedly deployed during illegal covert operations.

Return bureaucracy and administration

In most country cases, a whole set of different documents emerge, which apply to different procedures, or different phases of those procedures, depending on the RMI in question. These include excerpts of migrants’ personal files stored by competent authorities, their passports or other travel documents, various forms that they have to fill-in, reports that the various actors have to draft and submit at different stages, a host of letters (of notification, of referral, etc.) and certificates from various services and for different purposes, including medical certificates, or the fit-to-travel certificate that is used in both assisted voluntary returns and deportations. Several such documents are e.g. listed in the German case-study of forced removals, as pertaining to the ‘identity clarification’ and ‘logistical organisation’ stages during the preparation phase, as well as the ‘clearance at airport’, ‘arrival and handover’ and ‘follow-up processing’ stages of the enforcement phase (Mielke et al. 2025, Table 3). At the other side of the spectrum, some of these documents e.g. concerning identification, health, legal status, criminal record and/or reasons for deportation are re-examined by the receiving country authorities, as reported in the doings of the National Referral Mechanism of Iraq. While many of these documents are in digital form, stored on databases (see below), quite a few appear to still be on paper, to be physically handed over or stored in folders. In addition, the everyday office work related to the day-to-day administration and bureaucracy of returns encompasses a host of mundane items such as furniture, telephones, computers, stationery, etc.

Advertising and promoting returns

This rather special category of materialities is observed especially in AVRR schemes. Implementing actors have set up an entire toolbox of such information and campaigning material provided by NGOs and international organizations, including posters, booklets, brochures and multi-language leaflets. Quite often, the logos of specific actors, chiefly IOM's, are omnipresent in this material, as well as in the respective places, ensuring visibility. In the case of the AVRR in Greece, for example, IOM AVRR advertisement panels exist on bus stops in Athens. In many cases such materials exist in both physical (paper) and digital form. Similar information/campaigning material features in the cases of other countries.

Everyday and mundane materialities

Apart from the mundane office items described above, the materials depicted in this category may include a range of amenities related to the everyday life in places as different as the OCAVRR in Athens, the shelters of the National Alien Service LVV programme for undocumented migrants, or detention facilities in Sweden. In the latter case, for example, one may observe various everyday items that 'underscore the dual objectives of safety and comfort' (Barthoma and Tommos 2025, p.63): from furniture (desks, beds, kitchen tables, etc.), to computers used for both the training and recreation of detainees, projectors for watching movies, or even soft cutlery to prevent harm. Such materials may be 'small things', seemingly unimportant, but nevertheless essential parts of the return infrastructures.

In some cases, 'small things' purposely arranged make up immaterial 'things', composing the particular atmospheres of specific places and circumstances. From the 'empty, really sober' conversation rooms in the Netherlands to the internal environment of Swedish detention centres aiming at balancing 'security with a semblance of normalcy' (Barthoma and Tommos 2025, p.62), or even to the landscape alterations in border villages of Turkey whereby tall surveillance towers overpass the minarets. Ethnographic fieldwork observations of the LVV programme in the Netherlands highlighted 'how seemingly meaningless artefacts may have a story to tell' (Schapendonk et al. 2025, p.71); it is worth quoting extensively from the example of an information desk for undocumented people, among others providing information on the option of assisted return:

'A colourful place, with some signs of food preparation, breakfasts perhaps, a coffee corner with a machine, a kitchen, a small corner for young kids to spend their time playing with a tiny kitchen, cuddly toys and tools. Two large tables for conversations. It resembled a living space, shared collectively. Close to them on the ground floor, and above them, were the office spaces. In and around the living space there were a lot of signs about the caring for the case of undocumented people. Most notably a City Rights App, Migrant Rights advocacy posters, and these signs were often not far away from signs about sustainable futures and return. For its more intimate appearances the exposed drawings (made by kids), touched me. A colourful heart, a flower, as warm responses to the services unfolding in this location. Finally, two portraits in black and white caught my eye, near the toilets: "Raise a Paper Monument for the Paperless. Give a face to the Undocumented" It said in very tiny letters to let the face speak out. This place had a soul, so it felt' (Schapendonk et al. 2025, p.71).

There are also the ‘small things’ used for specific purposes at certain places and moments, such as the time of departure at the airport, or during the flight on board. For example, migrants returning via AVRR schemes receive the cash assistance at the airport, together with some snacks or lunch vouchers for travel. In the German case, these include the food packages deportees receive on the return flight. An example of a mundane object in the case of AVRR schemes implemented by IOM is a plastic bag carrying the organisation’s logo, which, as described for the Greek case, returnees are provided before departure, and need to carry with them throughout their time at the airport and their journey until they reach their destination. It is a handy thing as it helps people to carry together all documents needed for travel; it is also a way to recognise returnees in a crowded environment, yet passes unnoticed from the untrained eyes mistaking it for a duty-free bag. The Greek study comments on its multiple practical as well as symbolic functions: ‘it may be seen as an element of crowd control at the airport, a sign of the migrants’ status as returnees, a tool to distinguish them, or a way to discreetly cover their identity’ (Papatzani et al. 2025, p.40).

Picture 18 - *The IOM returnees’ bag provided to returnees from Greece.*
Source: Papatzani et al. 2025.

Post-return materialities

These latest examples bring us to a set of *materialities extending to the places of destination*. In Nigeria, standby support at the destination airports exists, including water, food and ambulance, which is offered by the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) to returnees once they land to Nigeria. Similarly, the reception of migrants deported to Iraq involves a food ration card, giving them access to ‘basic food items such as rice, sugar, flour, lentils, cooking oil, tomato paste, etc.’ (Warda and Al-Bayati 2025, Fig.1). Moreover, several reports on AVRR refer to in-kind support that (eligible) returnees receive once back. Reintegration schemes also offer vocational training and financial assistance for business startups: In the case of Tunisia, a female returnee, mother of three, married to a German-Palestinian, received assistance to launch a library project upon her return. Sometimes in-kind support may come not from large schemes such the one

implemented by IOM, but from ‘benevolent’ actors in Europe, such as a Dutch NGO running a project that aims to prevent people to ‘*return home empty handed*’: they collect several materials, tools, machines (often second-hand) which they put in a large box and ship it to returnees in their country of origin.

Nevertheless, as also evidenced in the Netherlands, ‘*not all materials can be transferred to locations people are sent to*’ (Schapendonk et al. 2025, p.51), revealing practical challenges regarding *material leftovers*. Since deportees are not allowed to carry with them all their personal belongings, once they depart some end up ‘left behind in the asylum locations where people resided’ (*ibid.*). These items are packed by the respective authority (COA) staff and transported to their owners. There are particular spaces within asylum locations reserved for

Picture 19 - *Deportees' drawings on the wall: Georgian flag and names. Source: Krępa et al. 2025.*

these leftovers to be stored in case of unknown owners' destination, and if unclaimed within a couple of months, they are brought to a waste station. The study mentioned the story of a returnee who returned to the asylum location he once had stayed in order to claim personal items he had to leave behind. Yet another kind of 'leftover', not involving such complex logistics, may be found not in actual 'things' but other traces of people's presence, however short-lived this may have been. Such an example is given through the fieldwork material of the Polish study, with a photo of wall drawings *in the room* at the airport where migrants await to be deported (Krępa et al. 2025, p.24). Finally, forced removals lead not to leftovers of belongings or other things, but also to lives left behind. The Nigerian study (Textbox B) narrates the story of the eldest daughter of a family deported from Germany, who left behind not just material things but her entire childhood, having lived in that country since the age of nine, where she had completed primary school, middle school, and secondary school, and was scheduled to begin film school.

Absent materials

There are though other absences featuring in the RMIs, albeit scarcely; not of absent people, as above, but of absent materials. From the point of view of the migrants, for example, the German case mentions the confiscated mobile phones of migrants under deportation, while the Nigerian one reports to missing identity documents, such as e.g. 'a National Identification Number or a Bank Verification Number, which complicates the issuance of identity cards necessary for their return to Nigeria' (Uzomah and Madu 2025, p.23). From a different point of view, such as the perspective of officials, absent materialities may include security equipment. This is the case of staff in Swedish detention centres complaining about the lack of certain security tools—no pepper spray, no batons.

Contesting returns

If the above imply that materials are crucial for the realisation of returns, it should be mentioned that *materials are also crucial for contesting returns*. An outstanding example is the importance of contesting materials in the case of pushbacks. Contesting actors use a variety of materials to both resist and report pushbacks. These may range from mobile phones, social media and communications applications to appeals to the European Court of Justice for an injunction.

In the case of Germany, materialities contesting returns may be diverse. It has been reported that at the time of scheduled forced removal flights at airports, activists provide advice ('First Aid Deportation') and organise protests, e.g. by blocking roads to and runways at airports, e.g. in Berlin. Moreover, contesting materialities may refer to advocacy and information campaigns: Social media and internet platforms play an important role in the distribution of (often self-compiled) information material, e.g., lists of supporting institutions

and information about rights and processes in the German asylum and return regime, but also for mobilising donations to continue voluntary work for migrants or support their stay.

Compiling and putting together the findings reported in the country cases, and critically reflecting and combining the different approaches employed, proved to be a valuable exercise in operationalising the very concept of Return Migration Infrastructures itself. Rather than documenting in detail the entire set of materials and technologies of so radically differing RMIs such as covert illegal pushback operations or ‘humane’ assisted voluntary returns, which would be an impossible as well as purposeless task, a tentative conclusion of this exercise is that materialities matter, in both practical and symbolic ways.

6.3 Technologies

Many of the materials mentioned above also relate to the technologies involved in RMIs. Some of the very objects and devices earlier described are actually technological tools, ranging from ‘old’ technologies of statecraft and bureaucracy, e.g. like passports or various kinds of lists, to ‘new’ yet conventional ones such as computers used to process and store data, as well as ‘smart’ technologies including drones, thermal cameras and electro-optic towers at the borders. Nevertheless, the RMI technologies involve much more than the obvious artefacts and gadgets, and crucially include less visible aspects, such as online apps, digital platforms and interfaces.

Relevant examples range from military technologies to ‘common’ Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs): The former primarily refers to the *surveillance and security technologies* that go hand in hand with the militarisation of borders (Jones and Johnson 2016) and the ‘border industrial complex’ (Molnar 2024) involving private commercial contractors who specialise in ‘dual use’ or exclusively military-use products, including both hardware and software. Although not directly discussed as such, there is ample even if scattered evidence of such technologies employed not only to prevent migration, but also to enforce more ‘effective’ returns, e.g. with weapons and other military equipment in pushback operations, surveillance equipment in detention centres or biometric identity scanners at airports.

The latter entails various ‘common’ communication technologies and tools, also available for everyday usage. These may include digital material and websites to disseminate information, or videoconferencing and social media applications used for communication purposes. In Swedish detention centres, for instance, detainees are able to maintain contact with their families via Skype. The promotion of AVR in Greece largely relies on digital and online information dissemination material as well as the use of social media, while return & reintegration counselling uses communication platforms such as WhatsApp or Viber. In Nigeria, returnee information and reintegration activities are recorded in computers, while MDAs and CSOs also employ WhatsApp groups to communicate with them and inform e.g. about training possibilities.

Much of the relevant findings, however, foreground the ‘three Ds transforming migration management’ (Witteborn 2022): *digitalization, digitization and datafication* (see also Korkmaz 2023; Mutlu et al. 2025). Beyond specialized *digital technologies*, tools and interfaces employed to enhance border security, track individuals’ identities and control human mobility, these crucially involve various administrative and bureaucratic procedures to enter, register, process, catalogue, taxonomise, monitor and evaluate information, procedures and outcomes, but also finances and personnel - which have now become *digitalised*. Such procedures include online appointment applications, online registrations, digital identification

cards and/or ID numbers, digital lists, and many more. For example, appointments for registration to AVRR in Greece take place through an Online Scheduling Appointment (OSA) platform, while registration itself also takes place in digital form. Applicants receive a (digital) registration card, which is 'of particular importance, as it indicates that the particular person is in the middle of a return process. It notes their name, personal details, identification code, and photo, and it is used during the entrance and exit from OCAVRR. Recently, a reference to the residency of the migrant and a phone number of OCAVRR was added, to highlight that the migrant's residence is stable and known, and to provide the possibility to police authorities to contact IOM for identification during regular street controls' (Papatzani et al. 2025, p.41). Another example comes from the German REAG/GARP: applications are submitted through an online application module (OAM), which since 2024 requires the applicants' AZR number, having been connected with the Central Registry of Foreigners (AZR); the OAM includes a chat function to channel information exchange between return counsellors and BAMF (Mielke et al. 2025).

Clearly, these are closely linked to *datafication*, which has become an inherent part of migration governance (ibid.; Witteborn 2022; Korkmaz 2023; Frowd 2024) that extends to the infrastructures of return. It entails all kinds of technologies related to the *entry, storage, management and circulation of data and information* for various purposes and at various stages of the return process (before the return, while preparing for and implementing the return, post-return and reintegration phase), through the extensive use of specialised software and the proliferation of databases. Much of the information collected in the above-mentioned digital procedures is fed into online databases that are connected and interlinked. Several databases form part of the RMI infrastructures, whether indirectly (i.e. serving other aspects of migration management), or directly (i.e. specifically designed to support return and readmission policies). Examples of the former case include transnational or pan-European IT data systems, serving both member-state authorities and EU or international actors, such as the EU Visa Information System (VIS), the Schengen Information System (SIS), or the European Asylum Dactyloscopy Database (EURODAC).

There are however national IT systems used in specific countries for information storage and exchange. Examples here include the Polish POBYT system allowing 'for the storage and obtaining of knowledge on a person's entire migration history, including administrative procedures related to his/her stay in the territory of Poland or other EU member states' or the National Police Information System (*Krajowy System Informacyjny Policji* - KSIP) used by the Polish Border Guard 'to obtain information that may affect the implementation of return procedures such as quests or criminal records' (Krepa et al. 2025, p.25). The Greek Asylum Service uses an 'Integrated Asylum Management System' called Alkyoni II, also accessible by the Hellenic Police for the identification of (rejected) asylum applicants and potential returnees (Papatzani et al 2025). Similarly, COA in the Netherlands works 'with a country-wide system called IBIS ['integraal bewoners informatie systeem']' whereby 'IND can add legal outcomes... but cannot access the system and read reports of conversations between COA case managers and asylum seekers' (Schanpendonk et al. 2025, p.53).

On the other hand, there are also international/EU IT systems specifically serving the implementation of returns. In Germany, for instance, there exists the Integrated Return Management Application (IRMA): 'a web-based platform where member states, Frontex and the European Commission exchange strategic and operational information on return-related activities' (Mielke et al 2025, p.102). Another example is the Frontex Application for Returns (FAR), 'which allows for planning the date, return route, booking, and purchasing airline tickets for returnees, accompanying escorts and other staff' (Krepa et al 2025, p.25). In the

words of a Polish Border Guard officer, the FAR *'enables the exchange of information between entities involved in the return procedure regarding logistic aspects... [and also] serves to report the needs of specific EU member states regarding the organisation of joint charter flights aimed at organising the return to the country of origin'* (Krepa et al 2025, p.25). In addition, reference is made to the European Commission's Reintegration Assistance Tool (RIAT), 'a restricted, secure digital platform that provides functionalities for return counsellors in Member States and reintegration partners in Countries of Origin to support return and reintegration cases'¹¹.

It is perhaps needless to note that, in many cases, the aforementioned databases and online digital platforms are interconnected and feed into each other. The following extract explaining such interconnections and their functions in the case of the Netherlands is telling:

'The DTenV regievoorders mainly work with ISTV [Informatiesysteem Terugkeer en Vertrek], but their work also involves other software systems like TULP (from DJI in the detention centre), EU VIS (EU Visa System), SIGMA (information platform for migration chain partners), RIAT system of Frontex. For DTenV regievoorders, all relevant case information appears in ISTV: from the very first AVIM hearing, to EURODAC information, to police reports are accessible there. The personalized V-number [vreemdelingsnummer] – a kind of ID-number – is crucial for this system. DTenV regievoorders also referred to Vreemdeling in Beeld (others called it SIGMA) that they may consult through ISTV. This is considered to be a platform for information sharing of chain partners, like COA, KMar, DJI and AVIM. This may provide vital information for regievoorders, like health (not everything is visible due to privacy issues), contact details of lawyers or criminal records. Our interviews indicate that especially behavioral or situational information is interesting for DTenV regievoorders (DTenV Regievoerder 1, DtenV Regievoerder 2). Also relevant return information of ISTV feeds SIGMA' (Schanpendonk et al. 2025, pp.51-52).

Specific IT systems have been developed for the management of and information sharing regarding assisted returns. An example mentioned in the Greek AVRR case study is the 'Migrant Management Operational System Application' (MIMOSA) system 'used by IOM globally', which 'is the central IOM Greece digital platform for registering the demographic and biographical data of migrants and the whole process and steps of the return, accessible by IOM in different countries. Each entry for an AVRR applicant is given a personal identification number, functioning as a single and unique identifier of the person until the return to their country and the implementation of the reintegration' (Papatzani et al 2025, p.41). From the perspective of the countries receiving returnees, Krepa et al.'s (2025) case study of the AVR to Georgia reports on the IOM-developed and EU-funded Readmission Case Management Electronic System (RCMS), 'a web-based, secure platform to facilitate information flows between partner countries and Georgia concerning requests on readmission' (Krepa et al. 2025, p.32).

However, the proliferation of advanced digital IT systems does not yet seem to assemble a (return) migration panopticon. Several country cases reveal issues of inequities, deficiencies and inconsistencies in data collection and information sharing technological infrastructures. In non-European countries, such systems are not as developed: e.g. Warda and Al-Bayati (2025, p.16) refer to the 'weak information and data sharing among stakeholders', which leads

¹¹ For more, see: <https://reintegration-assistance-tool.ec.europa.eu>

in turn to inaccurate statistics about returns. Boubakri et al (2025) mention the lack of a centralized database dedicated to managing the returnees' processes once they arrive in Tunisia, resulting in fragmented information and an inability to monitor reintegration. Uzomah and Madu (2025, pp.12-13) highlight the systemic inequities and data deficiencies within returnee empowerment programmes in Nigeria, including poor data management, reliance on outdated data and the exclusion of new arrivals, which overall hinder effective reintegration and create a gap between programme goals and implementation. Yet, data deficiencies and inconsistencies may be encountered also in EU member states. Schanpendonk et al. (2025, p.62) commenting on the use of administrative software in the Netherlands point that 'it is somewhat confusing that some systems receive different names from different organisations, and some interviewees referred to previously used software, while others used the new name'. Mielke et al. (2025, p.61) discuss how 'every foreigners authority works with different specialised procedures (interview, 22 July 2024) that are hardly compatible with each other, even in the same administrative district', leaving space for employees to improvise (although there are moves towards a centralised federal database (AusreisePlanungStatistik', APS).

In some cases, such deficiencies may lead to administrative mistakes that can have serious consequences for the migrants concerned. Schanpendonk et al. discuss how, in the Netherlands,

'it happens that [...] crucial information is put incorrect in the system or is left unchanged with there is in fact a significant legal change. Sometimes a successful appeal is administrated as an unsuccessful appeal in the system, leading to very different legal outcomes. Or an application for a residence permit is not visible in the ISTV system since it is not 'asylum related', which may create the situation that the DTenV regievoorders is unlawfully continuing return activities' (Schanpendonk et al. 2025, p.54).

They reminisce the tragic case of Alexander Dolmatov, a Russian opposition activist seeking political asylum in the Netherlands who committed suicide in a pre-removal detention centre where he was unlawfully placed due to system mistakes. Nevertheless, beyond human rights violations that may emerge as a result of the shortcomings of information sharing between different state bodies, the very management of sensitive personal information is problematic in itself for violating privacy and the protection of personal data. Uzomah and Madu (2025, p.12) raise similar questions regarding data management, noting additionally 'a coerced element in the data collection process, where states feel pressured to use *EU-funded systems*, potentially compromising their control over *sensitive information*'.

Finally, datafication is not limited to the collection and processing of individual migrants' personal data, but to the *production and dissemination of data* at large. In the Netherlands, for instance '[...] it is telling that the DTenV does not only monitor actual returns, but also count and present even more detailed data. This can be seen as a way to produce public "proof" that they are doing good work. For instance, for the year 2023 the DTenV counted 19.990 return conversations, 15.390 return procedures. In the same year, there have been 5920 flights booked, and DTenV has requested 2020 travel documents ... Our interviews with DTenV regievoorders indicated that these numbers are extracted from the software system that does not only register statuses of return processes, but also monitor the performance of DTenV regievoorders' (Schanpendonk et al. 2025, p.17). Similar evidence derives e.g. as regards the data published by IOM Greece as regards e.g. the AVRR information activities and campaigning

material distributed, the numbers of returns and returnees' profile, or details on reintegration counselling sessions and in-kind assistance (IOM 2019). Among others, this points to 'an organization that does stuff' (Bradley 2024) and on this basis justifies its role as a legitimate, expert and effective actor that deserves more resources to do even more, as has been argued in relation to data production and publication by other actors such as Frontex (Savatic et al. 2024).

6.4 Funding, logistics and the migration industries

An important cross-cutting theme concerns the costs and finances of RMIs, and the question of funding: its sources, purposes and allocation, as well as the flows of funding between states but also between different actors –state agencies, private contractors, international organisations, non-profit service providers– and the relations these may create. State (central government) budgets are largely financing the various agencies and bodies involved in different aspects of migration policy at large, as well as returns in particular. The costs of forced returns appear to be mostly covered through national funds, while assisted returns increasingly rely on EU funds. While questions of funding allocation and cuts in the financing of e.g. NGOs involved in return counselling is reported in countries such as Germany, a common thread in non-EU countries concerned the overall shortage of financial (as well as material) resources, weak funding and zero-budgets. In the latter's case, this not only raises questions about the effective reintegration of returnees, but also challenges the policy and discursive shift linking return and reintegration to developmental goals in the countries of origin. Moreover, since EU is as a major funder of return programmes and infrastructures in transit or origin countries, EU funding may be considered as essential part of externalisation policies, as it actively shapes return migration infrastructures in those countries.

A related theme featuring in most country cases, even indirectly, has to do with the complex logistics as regards the material and technological aspects of the return infrastructures, but also their spatialities, the contracts with private companies, the human resources and personnel, or the overall financial costs related to the host of relevant doings earlier discussed. This points to recent scholarly debates on various aspects of logistics in migration management (Pollozek and Passoth 2019; Bradley 2024; Bosthworth 2025). But the involvement of various private actors, firms and contractors –e.g. in supplying equipment or software, building and managing facilities, providing catering or security services, arranging travel and operating flights, etc.– also pertain to the related yet broader topic of the migration industries (Nyberg-Sørensen and Gammeltoft-Hansen 2013; Cranston et al. 2018) and the political economy of border and migration controls, for instance in relation to detention (Conlon and Hiemstra 2022; Martin and Tazzioli 2023; Molnar 2024). Even if only marginally addressed in country dossiers, such issues are omnipresent as the 'elephant in the room' of the RMIs.

7. Conclusion

This report is the synthesis of the GAPS WP3, which was designed to study how return migration governance is *put into practice*, including how different actors collaborate or work against each other, and what discrepancies emerge and continue to exist in their daily *operation* of return migration. In so doing, we embraced the concept of Return Migration Infrastructures and we worked with the continuum of coercion in terms of return migration. By moving away from single and isolated agency of individual actors as well as the idea of large overarching structures, the notion of RMIs articulates relationality, complexity, non-linearity, transformation, and human/non-human interfaces. The operationalisation of this conceptualisation distinguishes *1. Actors, roles and relations; 2. Daily doings in this web of relations 3. Places, materialities and technologies*. In these three dimensions of RMIs, the presence of non-linearity, complexity, and a dynamic, multi-scalar character is consistently observed across the countries studied, summarized as follows.

Regarding the actors involved in RMIs, they operate across multiple scales and levels, engaging in a wide range of activities. These actors can be categorized according to the political–geographical scale at which they function. At the international level, key actors include organizations such as the IOM; at the supranational level, institutions and agencies of the European Union are prominent. National or federal actors include government departments, national authorities, and law enforcement bodies. At the sub-national and community/local levels, NGOs and private companies are active, while individuals also play a role. Many actors operate across more than one scales. For example, national governments maintain a presence internationally through bilateral agreements, diplomatic missions, and, in some cases, international development agencies. Local variations are also significant, as even international or national actors may adapt their activities to specific local contexts. Both state and non-state actors participate in RMIs, with the latter including private entities such as security companies and service providers. In addition to their multi-scalar operations, the configuration of actors involved is shifting and dynamic. Differences in the composition of actors across countries further reflect broader geopolitical patterns shaping contemporary return migration.

The relationships among the actors are often characterized by both competition and interdependence. These relationships are inherently complex and dynamic, shaped by three main dimensions. First, they reflect asymmetric power relations that fluctuate in response to shifting political priorities and perceived ‘crises’. Such asymmetries reinforce and reproduce entrenched inequalities between the Global North and the Global South, between wealthier and poorer countries, and between the core regions of the EU and its peripheries. Second, competitive dynamics emerge among actors seeking to demonstrate greater effectiveness in implementing return programmes. This competition often manifests in tensions between assisted and non-assisted return schemes. Third, informal relationships play a significant role, influencing actors both implicitly and explicitly. Informal relations may involve support mechanisms for migrants throughout the return process but can also include, on the contrary, informal persuasion techniques, and unlawful activities such as arbitrary detention and even illegal pushbacks and pushforwards. Between these extremes lies a vast and ambiguous field of informal practices, shaped by legal grey areas and unfolding among actors operating at different scales and with varied mandates.

Concerning the complex ‘doings’ within the RMIs examined, these are not characterized by a linear sequence but rather by increased complexity and a dynamic circuit involving multiple steps, varying temporalities, dead ends, points of exit, circularities, and feedback loops. Four broad categories of doings can be identified, common across all types of RMIs and unfolding along the examined continuum of coercion: i) The detection and differentiation of return cases, referring to the various administrative procedures through which migrants targeted for return are identified; ii) The preparation for return, which includes all pre-departure doings, such as identification, logistical preparations, and importantly detention or the use of ‘alternative’ accommodation practices (which vary across the countries studied and may be prolonged); iii) The enactment of return itself, comprising the concrete doings carried out on the day of return; and iv) Post-return doings, including follow-up interventions such as post-return care, monitoring, and reintegration support.

Across all categories of doings within RMIs, several cross-cutting issues emerge that warrant attention. First, a dual process often unfolds on the part of the various actors consisting, on the one hand, of standardized, uniform, and seemingly ‘one-size-fits-all’ regulations, and procedures, and on the other hand, of a ‘case-by-case’ and individualized assessment approach. This duality produces inherent tensions within the return process and results in differentiated treatment and unequal positions among returnees. Second, informality—often accompanied by a lack of transparency—is a pervasive characteristic of various doings across all types of RMIs. From the establishment of deportability mechanisms in Europe to reintegration practices in countries of return, informal practices are of key importance. Third, the notion of ‘non-doings’ emerges as equally important. ‘Non-doings’ refer to policies of inaction or to the absence of formal procedures, which can have significant implications. While in some cases, informal or ad hoc practices may be applied to protect migrants’ well-being or allow for humanitarian exceptions, the lack of clearly defined procedures can also result in the erosion of returnees’ rights. In such contexts, the failure to act—or to institutionalize certain protections—poses serious threats to human rights considerations. Fourth, in addition to detention, irregularisation also appears as an intrinsic element of RMIs. Irregular status is not only a precondition for return but is also reproduced—both directly and symbolically—through the very workings of return mechanisms. Fifth, the deployment of soft power techniques to enforce collaboration plays a crucial role in RMIs. These strategies aim to build trust while simultaneously steering migrants toward specific return options. The perceived ‘collaborative’ behaviour of migrants often influences the type of return they are subjected to, with voluntary return increasingly shaped by subtle forms of enforced cooperation.

Regarding the material aspect of RMIs, the report highlights the multiple spaces, material components, and technologies that shape return processes. These include, for instance, the physical sites where various actors operate and where return procedures are enacted—ranging from national borders and airports to detention centres, public squares where undocumented migrants are apprehended, and even consultation rooms where return counselling takes place. The report also reveals an increasing overlap between return (exit) and reception (entry) spaces and infrastructures, along with other spatial arrangements designed to improve coordination—such as the ‘co-location method’ aimed at minimizing dispersal. The diversity of these places, their varied scales, and their evolving nature contribute to the formation of complex, shifting, and expanding geographies across all types of RMIs. The materiality of return infrastructures also encompasses non-human, physical, and technological elements that enable, facilitate, regulate, enforce, or in some cases, challenge return practices. Such materials range from security and enforcement equipment, transportation means, and

bureaucratic documents (e.g. forms, certificates, and case files), to promotional materials used to advertise return programmes—especially in the context of AVRR. They also include mundane, everyday items, post-return materialities in the countries of return, as well as absent materials and symbolic remnants. Technology plays a central role, particularly through what is often referred to as the ‘three Ds’ of migration management: digitalization, digitization, and datafication. These technological practices contribute to the structuring and monitoring of return processes.

In our conceptualisation of RMIs, the relational starting point could be regarded as a decentred approach in studies on migration governance as it inherently moves away from the central narrative of ‘safe, orderly and regular migration’ (Triandafyllidou 2022a; Samaddar 2020). Instead, the conceptual approach can be seen as a mode to empirically unpack the daily realities of polycentric (Koinova et al. 2024) or messy governance operations (Triandafyllidou 2022b). Moreover, there are two reasons that put this objective firmly in perspective. First of all, we noted that the entire field of return migration governance is a power-ridden landscape with powerful ‘Western’ (if not European) institutions at the top of a complex ‘migration governance food chain’ (see also Andersson 2014). In other words, European actors and stage agencies of individual EU member states direct and shape many of the practices under study. Moreover, many of the doings and materials of RMIs, are built on imperial ruins of the past (Morris 2021) mainly for its foundational imaginary that the countries of the majority world (‘Global South’) are places to get things done according to ‘Northern’ agendas (Bradley 2024; Uzomah 2024).

With this statement in mind, we would like to reflect on three main concluding cross-cutting findings: 1. The unbound character of RMIs vs. fragmented analysis; 2. The instrumentalisation of informalities; 3. The force and power dynamics. In each of it we also propose some preliminary insights on policy recommendations that will be further elaborated in a future policy brief.

7.1 RMIs unbound vs. fragmented analysis

Conceptually, RMI is an ‘unbound’ concept in the sense that it lacks clear demarcations. Where does the RMI start and end? These are questions that are difficult to answer. Collaborations cross state borders, alliances and collaborations move from local to global levels, and financial flows move the other way around, and possibly back again. This unbound nature is also reflected in the empirical sense as this reports foregrounds how *infrastructures of exit and return overlap* heavily with infrastructure of entry and protection. Moreover, across the entire continuum of assisted/coerced return, RMIs should be considered as part of a border control regime that seeks to ‘purify’ European societies from its unwelcome Others. In other words, any attempt to distinguish *return* migration infrastructures may be confronted with grey zones, analytical edges and crossovers.

In this respect, it is important to underline that return migration infrastructures do carry transnational continuities. Forced removals and push-backs, but also assisted returns, cause effects at the other side of the borders: many deportees are confronted with trauma, stigma and loss that echo in the countries of return, while assisted returnees may be cared for and monitored after the moment of return or instead feel failed and abandoned. Unfortunately, the set-up of our research did only allow us to analyse infrastructural (dis)continuities across borders to a limited extent, as we mostly limited our unpacking of the relations, materials and doings to a national context. In that sense, it is worthwhile to read the country dossiers in line

with each other, as return trajectories do not stop or end at the borders. Instead, RMIs continue across borders to countries of return, where returnees carry the experience of return or the stigma of deportation while simultaneously a range of other actors, activities, geographies and materialities emerge. In our research, three country cases emphasise this relational space: Poland-Georgia (Krepa et al. 2025) and Turkey-Greece (Gökalp Aras et al. 2025; Papatzani et al. 2025). At the same time, however, the possibility of investigating such transnational and cross-border infrastructural discontinuities remains open for future research.

Policy Recommendations

- 7.1.1 Enhance multi-level international cooperation in monitoring and evaluating the operation of RMIs, especially incorporating voices from the civil society in countries of return and transit countries.
- 7.1.2 Make sure that infrastructures of entry and international protection are not used in practice as grey zones of coercion to return.
- 7.1.3 Invite and incentivize actors in RMIs to better demarcate their objectives, rules of operations and accountability, especially in terms of respecting returnees; rights.

7.2 Instrumentalisation of informalities

As has been observed throughout this research, return processes are ridden with informalities, not only concerning the processes themselves but mostly the actors' practices within such processes and the relations among the actors involved. Such informalities may entail the illegal/irregular practice of pushbacks/forwards (or other such practices) which are legitimized in the minds of those involved as well as to the public as necessary due to an emergency. Thus, in this sense informality becomes institutionalized.

In a way, we could argue that informalities are almost interwoven with the return process as people try to circumvent obstacles to their migration trajectories via multiple ways. In this route, informal actors and networks –especially, but not only, in border areas– provide a variety of services that facilitate transport and livelihoods of those informally on the move (in pushback, pushforward and return mobility trajectories). Similarly, apart from the constellation of 'receiving' actors in Third Countries, informal networks become also involved in re-integrating and supporting (or conversely exploiting) returnees.

From yet another perspective informality can be intentionally employed and operationalized in order to establish more 'humane', trusting and cooperative relations among return professionals and migrants that could facilitate the consensual or cooperative return process – as for example in the case of Sweden but also encountered in other, mostly North European countries. In this case, actively encouraging informality (or actually the feeling of informality) in relations among actors becomes a soft power strategy of persuasion. Or in other words informality becomes instrumentalised within return processes.

In a way we could argue that not only are return processes interwoven with informalities, but that they are generators of informalities. Moreover, as illustrated by informality, despite discourses and argumentations over efficiency and security concerning returns, there are 'gaps' and 'cracks' within the different apparatuses from where some actors manage to exert (even more) violence. Conversely, there are also different actors for whom these 'cracks' offer an

opportunity for challenging the violence and the rigidity that RMIs entail – especially regarding migrants’ support and human rights protection.

Policy Recommendations

- Make sure that out-of-law return practices such as pushbacks are strictly avoided by state and supra-state authorities and any violations are effectively discouraged.
- Recognize soft-power coercive techniques in the daily operation of RMIs and make sure that potential returnees have access to free and reliable legal aid and can freely consult actors that contest returns.
- Enhance NGOs and CSOs that provide advocacy and legal aid.

7.3 Power imbalances and force

All RMIs in every single country and at the transnational level consist of wide networks of involved actors. Several procedures are usually performed by multiple collaborating and/or competing actors and RMIs are generally complex, multilevel and multiscalar. This complexity has certain implications regarding the questions of various actors’ responsibility and accountability, as the boundaries of actors’ mandates and performances are not always easy to demarcate and assess.

However, a complex landscape of actors is by no means an unstructured landscape. Structuring takes place through power relations. In general, we may conclude that we do observe an increased Europeanisation of returns, namely the increased involvement of certain countries (particularly from the North of the EU) into shaping the agenda and processes of returns as well as the infrastructures (within national, EU, extra-territorial, third country places). The Europeanisation of returns is reflected in charter flights, EURP assisted migration programmes (formerly JRS) and the more prominent role of FRONTEX in both assisted and forced returns.

It follows that actors in RMIs are of different size, scope, capacities, potential and are thus tied with each other in networks characterized by power imbalances. Minor actors, such as local civil society organisations and local migrant communities may develop their own agendas and initiatives, and create alternative infrastructuring practices (Wajsberg and Schapendonk 2022). They may respond to return policies and their implementation in several different ways, for example translating existing legal safeguards to specific legal aid and advocacy activities, collaborating with state authorities in campaigns of soft coercion, or on the contrary contesting and resisting return decisions. But in general, minor actors are restrained by opportunities offered and limitations set by major ones, as for example by specific funding schemes provided by AMIF in accordance with EU priorities or by changes in the national legal framework of a specific country that extend the maximum period of migration detention and so on.

There seem to be three basic sources of power in RMIs. The first is obviously *funding*, since organized return migration, either forced or assisted, is costly. It is so, both in terms of resources needed for return operations per se and in terms of developing mechanisms and materials for so diverse and spatially dispersed activities, such as data management, accommodation, detention, counselling etc. The importance of EU funding tools and initiatives, especially through AMIF, cannot be overstated but the costs of forced returns appear to be mostly covered through national funds.

The second is *knowledge and knowledge production* (see also Radziwinowiczówna 2024). Return migration governance is imbued with a general *urge to know* (Bartels 2024; Yilmaz-Elmas and Schapendonk forthcoming), amplified by the creation of datasets, the circulation of data and the expansion of surveillance infrastructures (Tazzioli 2020; Dijstelbloem 2021; Frowd 2024). This datafication strengthens the agenda of powerful institutions and functions first and foremost as a justification for stringent return migration measures. It turns return migration into ‘a knowledgeable and manageable object’ (Bartels 2024, p.2209). Datafication, for instance, helps to identify a ‘deportation gap’ and as a consequence it creates more governmental devotion to resolve ‘deportation obstacles’ (Scheel 2025). At the same time, data bring a huge potential to monitor – from the level of EU member states (whose return infrastructures is the most effective) to the street-level bureaucrat (whose return practice is the most effective).

When it comes down to knowledge, it is worthwhile to reflect further on the role of the IOM as one of the main actors in the return migration landscape today. IOM is an exemplary intergovernmental organisation with a long record of involvement in return migration, crucially involving the development of specific technologies, guidelines and established collaborations which are used in order to disseminate its approach on assisted voluntary return. With its knowledge and expertise, IOM has emerged as a key actor internationally, able both to attract funding and to allocate resources to other actors. The crux is that has become a ‘logistical expert’ and ‘epistemic authority’ at the same time (Bradley 2024), creating its own demand for more governance and hence more data (Bradley 2020). Evidently, knowledge is also instrumentalised as power in daily practices of RMIs, from the detection of potential pushbacks to the fact of uninformed migrants about particular details of their deportations (see also Borrelli 2021). The latter is in line with a more general observation that inaction and ‘institutional ambiguity’ (Nassar and Stel 2019) is an important migration governance strategy.

The third source of power is force, in its physical sense. Force basically lies with national law enforcement authorities that can use it (or threaten to use it) in order to impose deportations, including their prior steps of arrest and detention. It is telling that detention is part of the RMIs of both assisted and coerced returns, showing again the blurred lines between the presumed binary of voluntary vs. forced returns. Apart from being effective when actually used, physical sovereign force renders national authorities powerful in terms of setting the hard limit of the sociomaterial context in which RMIs operate.

The infrastructural violence (including its physical dimension) of returns is articulated in the pushbacks/pushforwards in the Turkey-Greece case and is key to deportation practices of powerful states and supra-states (see Radziwinowiczówna 2022). In both cases, violence brings its transnational echoes in the sense that a) violence may cross borders through continued displacement and enforcement and b) return migration practices echo to different places. Tunisia is in that sense a case in point. Being strengthened by a new EU migration deal, Tunisian authorities have started large-scale deportation operations of sub-Saharan populations, being fuelled by racist speech acts of its president and police forces (Şahin-Mencütek 2024). The use of force has often a material dimension too. Blinded vans, prisons, fences, razor wire, handcuffs, body-cuffs, guns, drones, body scanners, may all enter scripts of forced removals and, as such, intensify and prolong experiences of displacement of many migrants. This, so we feel, is an important shadow-narrative of the centred storyline of ‘sustainable returns’ and ‘safe and orderly migration’.

Evidently, returns create their own ‘ecosystem’ (to use a business term) that generates employment and profit, (re)produces relationships of dependency and power imbalances whilst providing, whenever necessary, the suitable ‘devil’ for political motives. Naively asked,

is this impressive number of actors and institutions and the funds spent on these in 'proportion' for the return processes of a few thousands of people? Or is the aforementioned ecosystem very valuable and thus its perpetuation vital?

Policy Recommendations

- Delineate clear rules and guidelines applicable to all actors in RMIs.
- Increase measurability, transparency and accountability in funding mechanisms.
- Make sure that actors are held responsible for the data they collect and create and data production is discussed negotiated among actors with different points of view.
- Make sure that returnees and their representatives (legal or otherwise) have access to their own data.
- Strictly avoid and punish the use of physical violence as a means of enforcement.

References

GAPs WP3 Country Dossiers

- Barthoma, S. and S. Tommos (2025) *Return Migration Infrastructures in Sweden – WP3 Country Dossier*. GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15712758>
- Boubakri, H., Ben Othmen, H., and Jedidi, M. (2025). *Return Migration Infrastructures in Tunisia - WP3 Country Dossier*. GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15852188>
- Gökalp Aras, N. E., Yüksel, U., and Ünay, H. (2025) *Return Migration Infrastructure in Turkey from Europe to Europe - WP3 Country Dossier*. GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15850973>
- Krepa, M., Pachocka, M., Trylińska, A., Sieniow, T., and Jaroszewicz, M. (2025). *Return Migration Infrastructures in Poland and Georgia - WP3 Country Dossier*. GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15750564>
- Lahlou, M. and K. Belhaj (2025) *Infrastructure for Returns /Readmission from EU Member States to Morocco - WP3 country snapshot*. GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15856666>.
- Mielke, K., Vollmer, R., Wolf, D., and Şahin-Mencütek, Z. (2025) *Return Migration Infrastructures in Germany – The Case of the Federal State of North Rhine-Westphalia*. GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15193348>
- Papatzani, E., Kandylis, G., Hatziprokopiou, P., Koutrolikou, P., Psallidaki, T., Varouxi, Ch., and Vezyrgianni, K. (2025). *Return Migration Infrastructures in Greece - WP3 Country Dossier*. GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15705012>
- Schapendonk, J., Ebrahim, S., Blanken, S., and Son, R. van (2025) *Return Migration Infrastructures of the Netherlands*. GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14919887>
- Uzomah, N. L., and Madu, I. A. (2025) *Reassessing Return Migration Governance: Insights on Nigeria's Return Migration Infrastructures - Country Dossier WP3*. GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15222377>
- Warda, W., and Al-Bayati, K. (2025). *Return Migration Infrastructures in Iraq – Country Dossier WP3*. GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15447578>

Other references

- Achieme, T. (2019). Migration as decolonization, *Stanford Law Review*, 71.
- Ahouga, Y. (2024). *Between Discipline and Biopolitics: The Role of IOM and UNHCR in the Return of Crisis-Affected Populations*. GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns

- and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13880119>
- Andersson, R. (2014). *Illegality, Inc.: Clandestine migration and the business of bordering Europe*. University of California Press.
- Aparna, K. and Schapendonk, J. (2020). Shifting itineraries of asylum hospitality: Towards a process geographical approach of guest-host relations. *Geoforum*, 116, 226-234.
- Ben Othmen, H., (2025). "The European Border and Coast Guard Agency, a Main Actor of the Return Policy". GAPs Blog Article, May 20, 2025. Available at: [<https://www.returnmigration.eu/gapsblog/the-european-border-and-coast-guard-agency-a-main-actor-of-the-return-policy/>]. Accessed 15/05/2025.
- Borrelli, L. M. (2021). 'They know the procedure; they just don't know when we will come': uncovering the practice of unannounced deportations. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 47(15), 3473-3491.
- Borrelli, L., and Lindberg, A. (2025). Making (in) formality work in a multi-scalar European border regime. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 51(2), 445-463.
- Bosworth, M. (2025) *Supply Chain Justice: The Logistics of British Border Controls*. Princeton University Press.
- Bradley, M. (2020). *The International Organization for Migration: challenges, commitments, complexities*. Routledge.
- Bradley, M. (2024). 'We're an Organization that *Does Stuff*': The International Organization for Migration, Logistics and Expert Authority in Migration Governance. *Geopolitics*, 30(4), 1680-1709.
- Broeders, D., and Dijkstra, H. (2015). The Datafication of mobility and migration management: The mediating state and its consequences. In I. van der Ploeg and J. Pridmore (Eds.) *Digitizing identities* (pp. 242-260). Routledge.
- BVMN [Border Violence Monitoring Network] (2023). Dark Rooms, Degrading Treatment and Denial: The Use of Violence in Greece's Pre-Removal Detention Centres. Available at: [<https://shorturl.at/BsZee>]. Accessed: 25/04/2025.
- Carrera S., den Hertog A., Panizzon M., Kostakopoulou, D (2019). *EU External Migration Policies in an Era of Global Mobilities: Intersecting Policy Universes*. Brill.
- Chiti, E. (2021). The Agencification Process and the Evolution of the EU Administrative System. In P. Craig, and Gráinne de Búrca (Eds.) *The Evolution of EU Law, 3rd edition* <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780192846556.003.0005>. Accessed: 25/04/2025.
- Cleton, L., and Chauvin, S. (2020). Performing freedom in the Dutch deportation regime: Bureaucratic persuasion and the enforcement of 'voluntary return'. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 46(1), 297-313.
- Conlon, D., Hiemstra, N. (2022). 'Unpleasant' but 'helpful': Immigration detention and urban entanglements in New Jersey, USA. *Urban Studies*, 59(11): 2179-2198.
- Cranston, S., Schapendonk, J., Spaan, E. (2018). New directions in exploring the migration industries: introduction to special issue, *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 44(4): 543-557.
- Davies, T., and Isakjee, A. (2019). Ruins of Empire: Refugees, race and the postcolonial geographies of European migrant camps. *Geoforum*, 102, 214-217.
- De Genova, N. (Ed.). (2017). *The Borders of "Europe": Autonomy of Migration, Tactics of Bordering*. Duke University Press.
- Deutscher Bundestag (2025). Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Abgeordneten Clara Bünger, Dr. André Hahn, Gökay Akbulut, Anke Domscheit-Berg, Nicole Gohlke, Susanne Hennig-Wellsow, Jan Korte, Ina Latendorf, Petra Pau, Martina

- Renner, Dr. Petra Sitte, Kathrin Vogler und der Gruppe Die Linke, Drucksache 20/14492, Abschiebungen und Ausreisen im Jahr 2024, Drucksache 20/14946, 11.02.2025. Available at: [<https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/20/149/2014946.pdf>]. Accessed: 25/03/2025.
- Dijstelbloem, H. (2021). *Borders as infrastructure: The technopolitics of border control*. MIT Press.
- DTenV (2019). Methodische Handleiding DT&V. Werken in Gedwongen Kader. Ministerie van Justitie en Veiligheid.
- Düvell, F., and Preiss, C. (2022). Migration Infrastructures: How Do People Migrate?. In: Scholten, P. (Ed.) *Introduction to Migration Studies. IMISCOE Research Series*. Springer, Cham. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-92377-8_4]
- EMN (2023). Ad-Hoc Query on 2023.7 Policies and practices on return and reintegration counselling for migrants in EU+. Available at: [https://www.emn.lt/uploads/Products/product_2021/78348b01-ae12-43da-ad79-cd7e542b8c72_en.pdf]. Accessed: 25/04/2025.
- Faist, T. (2010). The crucial Meso Level. In: *Selected Studies in International Migration and Immigrant Incorporation*, pp. 59-90, Amsterdam.
- Frowd, P. M. (2024). The ‘Datafication’ of Borders in Global Context: The Role of the International Organization for Migration. *Geopolitics*, 1-19.
- GCR [Greek Council for Refugees] (2018). Borderlines of Despair: First-line reception of asylum seekers at the Greek borders. Available at: [<https://bit.ly/39So4Oy>]. Accessed: 13/02/2025.
- GCR [Greek Council for Refugees] (2024). Country Report: Greece. Available at: [<https://shorturl.at/3S2kh>]. Accessed: 13/02/2025.
- Gill, N., Hoellerer, N., Hambly, J., & Fisher, D. (2025). *Inside asylum appeals: Access, participation and procedure in Europe*. Taylor & Francis.
- Gkliati M. (2024). Decoding Frontex’s fragmented accountability mosaic and introducing systemic accountability - System Reset. *Eur Law J.*: 30(1-2): 197-216. DOI:10.1111/eulj.12514.
- GNCHR [Recording Mechanism of Informal Forced Returns, Greek National Commission for Human Rights] (2024). Recording Mechanism of Incidents of Informal Forced Returns. Annual Report 2023. Available at: [https://nchr.gr/images/pdf/RecMechanism/Final_Annual_Report_202311.pdf]. Accessed: 13/02/2025.
- Godin, M., & Donà, G. (2020). Rethinking transit zones: migrant trajectories and transnational networks in Techno-Borderscapes. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 47(14), 3276–3292.
- Gökalp Aras, N. E., Öztürk, N. Ö., Strik, T., Thorburn Stern, R., Trylińska, A., & Yüksel, U. (2024). Legal and Policy Infrastructures of Returns in the EU - Comparative Report (WP2). GAPs: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11222075>
- Greek Ombudsman (2019). Return of Third Country Nationals. Special report 2018. Available at: [old.synigoros.gr/resources/english-final.pdf]. Accessed: 13/04/2025.
- Greek Ombudsman (2023). *Returns of third-country nationals. Special report 2022*. Available at: [<https://shorturl.at/Ngcj3>]. Accessed: 15/04/2025.
- Gutiérrez Rodríguez E. (2019). Conceptualizing the Coloniality of Migration. In D. Bachmann-Medick, and J. Kugele, (Eds.) *Migration: Changing Concepts, Critical Approaches*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter.

- Hom, S. M. (2019). *Empire's Mobius Strip: Historical Echoes in Italy's Crisis of Migration and Detention*. Cornell University Press.
- Infantino, F. (2023). The interdependency of border bureaucracies and mobility intermediaries: a street-level view of migration infrastructuring. *Comparative migration studies*, 11(1), 1.
- IOM [International Organization for Migration] (2019). The Implementation of Assisted Voluntary Returns Including Reintegration Measures (AVRR), Final Report: 1 June 2016 – 31 May 2019, Bulletin #3. Available at [https://greece.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbd11086/files/documents/IOM%20Greece%20Implementation%20of%20AVRR_EN.pdf] (accessed 20.06.2025).
- IOM [International Organization for Migration] (2022). Return and Reintegration. International Organization for Migration. Available at: <https://www.iom.int/return-and-reintegration>. Accessed: 15/04/2025.
- IOM [International Organization for Migration] (2024). Hellenic integration support for beneficiaries of international protection and temporary protection (HELIOS), Announcement. Available at: [<https://greece.iom.int/el/hellenic-integration-support-beneficiaries-international-protection-and-temporary-protection-helios>]. Accessed 22/11/2024.
- Iwuoha, V. C., and Doevenspeck, M. (2025). Dilemmas of 'biometric nationality': migration control, biometric ID technology and political mobilisation of migrants in West Africa. *Territory, Politics, Governance*, 13(3), 279-304.
- Jones, R. and Johnson, C. (2016), Border militarisation and the re-articulation of sovereignty. *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, 41: 187-200. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tran.12115>.
- Kandylis, G., Papatzani, E., Polyzou, I. (2024). Between coexistence and marginality: migrants and socio-spatial change. In Maloutas, Th. (Ed.) *Athens A Rapidly Changing Metropolis in the European South*, pp. 63-78. Routledge: London and New York.
- Karamanidou, L. and Kasperek, B. (2020). Fundamental Rights, Accountability and Transparency in European Governance of Migration: The Case of the European Border and Coast Guard Agency Frontex, Available at: [<https://respondmigration.com/wp-blog/fundamental-rights-accountability-transparency-european-governance-of-migration-the-case-european-border-coast-guard-agency-frontex>]. Accessed: 15/04/2025.
- Khosravi, S. (2009). Sweden: Detention and deportation of asylum seekers. *Race & class*, 50(4), 38-56.
- Kleist, N., and Bjarnesen, J. (2023). Mediating mobility in West Africa: Improvisation, culture, and volatility in migration infrastructures. *International Migration Review*, 01979183231205563.
- Koinova, M., Deloffre, M. Z., Gadinger, F., Mencutek, Z. S., Scholte, J. A., & Steffek, J. (2021). It's ordered chaos: What really makes polycentrism work. *International Studies Review*, 23(4), 1988-2018.
- Konya Valiligi. (2024). Valimiz İbrahim Akın, Düzensiz Göçmen Ön Kabul ve Sevk Merkezi'nde (GÖKSEM) İncelemelerde Bulundu. 1 October 2024, Available at: [<http://konya.gov.tr/valimiz-ibrahim-akin-duzensiz-gocmen-on-kabul-ve-sevk-merkezinde-goksem-incelemelerde-bulundu>]. Accessed: 15/04/2025.
- Korkmaz, E. E. (2023) *Smart Borders, Digital Identity and Big Data: How Surveillance Technologies Are Used Against Migrants*. Bristol University Press.

- Krepa, M., Pachocka, M., Trylińska, A., & Sieniow, T. (2024). *Externalisation of EU Migration Policies: The Case of Cooperation in the Georgian Citizens' Returns from Poland*. GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13134919>
- Lahlou, M. (2021). EU-Africa Partnership on Migration and Mobility in Light of COVID-19: Perspectives from North Africa. Rome, IAI, 20 p. (IAI Papers; 21|03). <https://www.iai.it/en/pubblicazioni/eu-africa-partnership-migration-and-mobility-light-covid-19-perspectives-north-africa>
- Landau-Donnelly, F., Carlsson, H., & Lagendijk, A. (Eds.) (2024). *Reflecting on Practices: New Directions for Spatial Theories*. Agenda Publishing.
- Lauser, A., Fuhse, A., Bräunlein, P. J., & Yi-Neumann, F. (2022). Introduction: From 'bare life' to 'moving things': on the materiality of (forced) migration. In: Yi-Neumann, F., Lauser, A., Fuhse, A., & Bräunlein, P. J. (eds). *Material Culture and (Forced) Migration: Materializing the Transient*. UCL Press.
- Leerkes, A., and Van Houte, M. (2020). Beyond the deportation regime: differential state interests and capacities in dealing with (non-) deportability in Europe. *Citizenship Studies*, 24(3), 319–338.
- Leivaditi, N., Papatzani, E., Ilias, A., and Petracou, E. (2020). *Refugee Protection. Greece Country Report*, RESPOND Working Papers, Global Migration: Consequences and Responses (#770564 Horizon 2020), Paper 2020/31, January 2020, University of the Aegean. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613733>
- Leurs, K. (2023). *Digital Migration*. London: Sage
- Lietaert, I. (2017). Transnational knowledge in social work programs: Challenges and strategies within assisted voluntary return and reintegration support. *Transnational Social Review*, 7(2), 158-173.
- Lighthouse reports (2022). 'We were slaves'. Greece uses asylum seekers to forcibly return migrants to Turkey. Available at: [<https://www.lighthousereports.com/investigation/we-were-slaves/>]. Accessed: 09/04/2024.
- Lin, W., Lindquist, J., Xiang, B., & Yeoh, B. S. (2017). Migration infrastructures and the production of migrant mobilities. *Mobilities*, 12(2), 167-174.
- Lindseth, P. L., (2014). Supranational Organizations. In I. Hurd, I. Johnstone, and J. Katz Cogan, (eds.), *Oxford Handbook of International Organizations* (OUP, 2016), Available at [<https://ssrn.com/abstract=2517896>]. Accessed: 15/04/2025.
- M'Charek, A. (2020). Harraga: Burning borders, navigating colonialism. *The Sociological Review*, 68(2), 418-434.
- Mack, A., Buimer, L., Rog, J., and Witvliet, M. (2022). *Eindevaluatie Landelijke Vreemdelingenvoorziening*. Amsterdam: Regioplan
- Martin, L. L., & Tazzioli, M. (2023). Value extraction through refugee carcerality: Data, labour and financialised accommodation. *Environment and Planning D: Society and Space*, 41(2), 191-209.
- McNeill, H. (2023). Deportation as a neo-colonial act: how deporting state influence extends beyond the border. *Political Geography*, 102.
- Meeus, B., Arnaut, K., van Heur, B. (2019). *Arrival Infrastructures. Migration and Urban Social Mobilities*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Molnar, P. (202) *The Walls Have Eyes: Surviving Migration in the Age of Artificial Intelligence*. New York: The New Press.
- Morris, J. (2021). Colonial afterlives of infrastructure: from phosphate to refugee processing in the Republic of Nauru. *Mobilities*, 16(5), 688-706.

- Mutlu, C. E., Frowd, P. M., & Muller, B. (2025). The application of borders: Data, migration and digitalization. *Big Data & Society*, 12(2).
- Nassar, J., and Stel, N. (2019). Lebanon's response to the Syrian refugee crisis—Institutional ambiguity as a governance strategy. *Political Geography*, 70, 44-54.
- Norman, K. P. (2020). *Reluctant Reception: Refugees, Migration and Governance in the Middle East and North Africa*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- NRC (2024) *Hoe een schaduwteam van Yesilgöz een omstreden asielaanpak doorvoerde*, acces Hoe een schaduwteam van Yesilgöz een omstreden asielaanpak doorvoerde – NRC. Accessed 9/9/2024 .
- Ordu Valiliği (2023). “Mobil Göç Noktası Aracı,Ordu’da Hizmet Vermeye Başladı”, 18 December 2024. Available at: [<http://www.ordu.gov.tr/mobil-goc-noktasi-araci-orduda-hizmet-vermeye-basladi>]. Accessed 4/2/2025.
- Papatzani, E., Psallidaki, T., Kandyliis, G., Micha, I. (2022). Multiple geographies of precarity: Accommodation policies for asylum seekers in metropolitan Athens, Greece. *European Urban and Regional Studies* 29 (2): 189-203.
- Papatzani, E., Hatziprokopiou, P., Kandyliis, G., Koutrolikou, P. (2024). *Procedures of irregularisation in Greece: spatial, carceral and temporal aspects*. WP2 Working Paper. GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13135269.
- Pollozek, S., and Passoth, J. H. (2019). Infrastructuring European migration and border control: The logistics of registration and identification at Moria hotspot. *Environment and Planning D: Society and Space*, 37(4), 606-624.
- Radyo80 (2025). “Osmaniye'de Düzensiz Göçmen Ön Kabul ve Sevk Merkezi (GÖKSEM) açıldı.” 20 February 2025. Available at: [<https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=1559147614794948>]. Accessed: 15/04/2025.
- Radziwinowiczówna, A. (2022). Violence that builds sovereignty: the transnational violence continuum in deportation from the United States. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 48(5), 1095-1112.
- Radziwinowiczówna, A. (2024). A power-knowledge approach. In *Research Methods in Deportation* (pp. 2-27). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Rajaram, P. K. (2024). “They abscond’: migration and coloniality in the contemporary conjuncture in Europe. *Cultural Studies*, 39(1), 20–37.
- Rose, S., and Schießl, S. (2024). Abschiebungen in Nordrhein-Westfalen. Ausgrenzung-Entrechtung-Widerstände. Köln: Abschiebungsreporting NRW & Komitee für Grundrechte und Demokratie e.V. <https://www.abschiebungsreporting.de>
- Şahin-Mencütek, Z. (2023). *The Role of Return Preparedness, Assistance and Networks in Returnees’ Reintegration in Origin Countries: Synthesis Report*. BICC. Available at: [https://www.bicc.de/Publikationen/WP_Synthesis_Report_neu.pdf~dr1760]. Accessed: 15/05/2025.
- Şahin-Mencütek, Z. (2024). Spillovers of EU externalization policies on coerced returns from transit countries. Commentary on Externalizing Asylum web page. Available at: [https://externalizingasylum.info/spillovers-of-eu-externalization-policies-on-coerced-returns-from-transit-countries/#_ftnref4].
- Şahin-Mencütek, Z. and Barthoma, S. (2025). “Why the EU’s migrant 'return hubs' are doomed to fail”. The Loop. Available at: [<https://theloop.ecpr.eu/why-the-eus-migrant-return-hubs-are-doomed-to-fail/>]. Accessed: 12/6/2025.

- Şahin-Mencütek, Z., and Triandafyllidou, A. (2025). Coerced return: formal policies, informal practices and migrants' navigation. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 51(2), 483-500.
- Şahin-Mencütek, Z., Siddıkoğlu, H., & Barthoma, S. (2025). Return governance and diplomacy between Türkiye and Afghanistan. *International Migration*, 63(3), e70037.
- Samaddar, R. (2020) *The Postcolonial Age of Migration*. Routledge.
- Sánchez-Querubín, N., & Rogers, R. (2018). Connected Routes: Migration Studies with Digital Devices and Platforms. *Social Media and Society*, 4(1).
- Savatic, F., Thiollet, H., Mesnard, A., Senne, J.-N., & Jaulin, T. (2024). Borders Start With Numbers: How Migration Data Create "Fake Illegals". *International Migration Review*, 0(0).
- Schapendonk, J. (2020). *Finding ways through Eurospace: West African movers re-viewing Europe from the inside* (Vol. 7). Berghahn Books.
- Scheel, S. (2025). The deportation gap as a statistical chimera: How nonknowledge informs migration policies. *Geopolitics*, 30(3), 1028-1050.
- Schmeer, L. (2022). Depoliticization through agencification in the EU's Area of Freedom, Security and Justice. In A. M. Houde et al (Eds). *The politicization of the European Union*. Éditions de l'Université de Bruxelles.
- SCMI [State Commission on Migration Issues] (2020). Migration Strategy of Georgia 2021-2030. Unofficial translation of the encyclopedic version. Available at: [https://migration.commission.ge/files/ms30_eng_web2.pdf]. Accessed: 25/5/2025.
- Shrestha, T., & Yeoh, B. S. A. (2018). Practices of brokerage and the making of migration infrastructures in Asia. *Pacific Affairs*, 91(4), 663-672.
- Simone, A.M.M. (2004). People as Infrastructure: Intersecting Fragments in Johannesburg. *Public Culture* 16(3), 407-429.
- Sørensen N.N. and Gammeltoft-Hansen T. (2013). Introduction. In: Gammeltoft-Hansen T. and Sørensen N.N., eds., *The Migration Industry and the Commercialization of International Migration*. London: Routledge.
- Stel, N., van Houte, M., and Blanken, S. (2025). *Synthesis report – Return migration governance in the African and Middle Eastern regions and the role of the EU*. GAPs - Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15166876>.
- Tazzioli, M. (2020). *The Making of Migration*. London: Sage.
- Teunissen, P. (2020). Border crossing assemblages: Differentiated travelers and the viapolitics of FlixBus. *Journal of borderlands studies*, 35(3), 385-401.
- Teunissen, P. (2025). Infrastructures, Riverscapes, and the Governance of Mobility: The Evros/Meriç River and the Infrastructuring of Nature. *Antipode*, 57(2), 691-713.
- Triandafyllidou, A. (2022a). Decentring the study of migration governance: A radical view. *Geopolitics*, 27(3), 811-825.
- Triandafyllidou, A. (2022b). The global governance of migration: Towards a 'messy' approach. *International Migration*, 60(4), 19-27.
- Uzomah, N. L. (2024). European Union border technology in Africa: Experiences en route. *Population, Space and Place*, 30(8), e2824.
- Van Riemsdijk, M., Marchand, M. H., and Heins, V. M. (2021). New actors and contested architectures in global migration governance: continuity and change. *Third World Quarterly*, 42(1), 1-15.
- Vollmer, R., & Şahin-Mencütek, Z. (2023). Experimentation and Extraction in Reintegration Governance: the case of Kosovo. *sozialpolitik. ch*, (2/2023), 2-2.

- Wajsberg, M. (2025). Migration Infrastructures at the Edge: (Re)making Arrival Infrastructures in Hamburg. *Nordic Journal of Migration Research*, 15(2): 3, 1–19.
- Wajsberg, M., and Schapendonk, J. (2022). Resonance beyond regimes: Migrant's alternative infrastructuring practices in Athens. *Urban Studies*, 59(11), 2352-2368.
- Walters, W. (2015). Migration, vehicles, and politics: Three theses on viapolitics. *European Journal of Social Theory*, 18(4), 469-488.
- Walters, W. (2024). The deportation plane: charter flights and carceral mobilities. *Mobilities*, 1-17.
- Walters, W., Heller, C., & Pezzani, L. (Eds.) (2021). *Viapolitics: borders, migration, and the power of locomotion*. Duke University Press.
- WAM [We Are Monitoring] (n.d.). 'Data', Available at: [https://wearemonitoring.org.pl/en/statistics/interactivedashboards/]. Accessed: 12/5/2025.
- Witteborn, S. (2022) Digitalization, Digitization and Datafication: The "Three D" Transformation of Forced Migration Management, *Communication, Culture and Critique*, 15 (2): 157–175.
- Xiang, B. and Lindquist, J. (2014). Migration infrastructure. *International Migration Review*, 48(1_suppl), 122-148.
- Yilmaz-Elmas, F. and J. Schapendonk (forthcoming). Circulation, Fragmentation and Foregrounding: Doing Data as Part of Return Migration Infrastructures. In Barthoma, S and Şahin-Mencütek, Z. (Eds.) *Revisiting Return Migration: A decentring approach to concepts, methodologies and processes*. Springer.
- IOM [International Organization for Migration] (2023). The Implementation of Assisted Voluntary Returns Including Reintegration Measures and Operation of Open Centre in the Prefecture of Attica for Applicants of Voluntary Return (AVRR/OCAVRR). September 2019-August 2023. International Organization for Migration-IOM Greece: Alimos, Athens. Available at: [https://shorturl.at/TlmgY]. Accessed: 18/09/2024.

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